

The application of model-based image processing to the interpretation of maps

Rik D.T. Janssen

Stellingen behorende bij het proefschrift:

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1. Het vakgebied modelgestuurde beeldbewerking wordt enorm vooruit geholpen door een éénduidig taalbegrip. *Dit proefschrift*
2. In vectorisatie bestaat er zeker geen eenduidige oplossing. De enige zekerheid is: de computer doet het nauwkeuriger dan de mens per tijdseenheid. *Dit proefschrift*
3. Een goede vectorisatie kan verkregen worden door het invoeren van een maat voor de 'gevoeligheid' voor verschuiving van nodes. *Dit proefschrift*
4. Evaluatie van een systeem kan op vele manieren. Murphy's corollary hiervan: de reviewer vindt altijd weer een andere beter.
5. Bij kunsttentoonstellingen worden kunstwerken over de hele wereld gezonden omdat mensen originelen mooier vinden dan kopieën. Resultaten van automatische interpretatie worden ook mooier door gebruik van originelen.
6. Lange mensen trekken vaak aan het kortste eind.
7. De door de computer waar te nemen werkelijkheid wordt beperkt door de vooroordelen van de ontwerpers, de programmatuur en de sensoren.
8. Regelgeving wordt vaak gekenmerkt door het genereren van te veel regels: lost de eerste regel uit een serie meer problemen op dan dat hij genereert, de laatst toegevoegde regel genereert vaak meer problemen dan dat hij oplost.
9. De laatste jaren is er een betere analogie dan vroeger tussen dansen en de natuurkundige wet die zegt dat gassen zich gelijkmatig verspreiden over de beschikbare ruimte.
10. Het kan aanbeveling verdienen Geografische Informatie Systemen (GIS) van een spellingscontrole te voorzien.

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The application of model-based image processing to the interpretation of maps

De toepassing van modelgestuurde beeldbewerking op interpretatie van kaarten

PROEFSCHRIFT

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Preface

This thesis describes various aspects of model-based image processing. The model-based approach is different from the 'classical' approach of bottom-up or top-down interpretation, because the latter do not allow extensive use of a-priori knowledge such as the characteristic features of the objects to interpret, the (valid) relations between the objects, the consistency of the interpretation, and the anticipation of errors which can be made during the interpretation process. The model-based approach in this thesis gives a solution for several of these problems.

The approach is implemented in an interpretation system for two types of images: cadastral maps and large-scale base maps. Such a system needs a subsystem for accurate vectorization, preferably able to correct for errors which can be made during the vectorization process. This has been accomplished by using the original line drawing for making the vectorization more precise and to correct for errors. The method is therefore called 'adaptive'. Another subsystem is able to form one large mosaic from separately scanned line drawings.

We have chosen to interpret maps instead of other images because maps are artifacts, made according to rules. Thus, in interpreting these types of images, a clear definition of what to interpret is known in advance and this can be used as a-priori knowledge. This a-priori knowledge describes the 'expectations of reality', which can be represented with a model.

Unfortunately, draftspersons do not always draw according to the rules. This complicates the interpretation system considerably because all kinds of unexpected results will occur. This should be anticipated, and subsequently should form part of the a-priori knowledge. Thus, a sort of circular 'learning' process can be observed: constructing a model, observing that it cannot anticipate certain situations, constructing a new (adapted) model, etc.

Another complication of the interpretation system is caused by storage and usage of the drawings. The drawing material can be torn during its lifetime, spots may appear on it by e.g. spilled coffee or by the influence of light, or copies can be made which are to be interpreted because the owner of the drawings does not allow the use of the originals. Often, the copies are of worse quality than the originals, especially if the original is not on (transparent) film or if it has a colored background. Difficulties will also arise if parts of the drawing are on the back of the drawing material.

A different complication of the interpretation system is caused by some of the image processing algorithms involved. For instance, to be able to interpret an image with a computer, it has to be scanned. Then, at some time, it has to be segmented. These two processes can give rise to all kinds of distortions of the input image.

Thus, interpretation of images is a complicated process, even if drawing rules exist or if they

are relatively simple. Therefore, for the evaluation of the model-based approach, an interpretation system for cadastral maps and large-scale base maps was built. Since these types of maps are not very complicated, it may be expected that the above mentioned problems only divert our attention slightly from the development of an interpretation methodology.

Introduction to 'model-based' and its vocabulary

1

This chapter describes a notion of 'model-based'. First a literature review is presented, as a starting point for our definition of model-based. For clarification, a subdivision has been made into approaches which describe the objects with a model, approaches which base the interpretation method on a model, and approaches combining these two. Next, a model-based interpretation methodology is discussed. An interpretation system for two types of maps based on this methodology is presented in chapter 5. This chapter is concluded with a proposal for a common vocabulary in model-based image processing.

1.1 Literature review

This section reviews the published approaches of several authors to the problem of model-based interpretation. The emphasis is on describing their notion of model-based. Because there is no commonly used definition, a subdivision has been made into authors who describe the objects to interpret with a model, authors who base the interpretation method on a model, and authors who combine these two.

1.1.1 Object description based on a model

Several authors use the term 'model-based interpretation' to refer to an algorithm in which the description of the objects to interpret is based on a model. This is done because the form or other features of the objects can be difficult to describe with fixed parameters. Thus, a possible reason to use a model-based description of objects is that the variance within the same class is large. Another reason is that the objects to represent are too detailed and that a simplification is desired.

Cooper, Bryson, and Taylor (1989) describe a system to locate boundaries of overlapping and touching chromosomes. The chromosomes are described by a shape model which captures their size and shape, and the variation along the boundary. This model is obtained in a learning process in which example chromosomes are presented to a user, who draws an axis. From this axis the boundary of the chromosome is derived automatically. Any errors made are corrected interactively, which are then used to update the statistics.

A similar method is described by Staib and Duncan (1989). They describe a method for segmenting natural objects whose diversity and irregularity of shape is difficult to represent in terms of fixed features or form. Instead, they use a parametric model based on elliptic Fourier decomposition of the boundary. Parameters of the algorithm are found automatically with an

optimization algorithm which finds the best values with some example images. Next, the parameters are used to find the parameters for the segmentation of the test images. As an application of this method a system to track the motion of the left ventricle is described (Duncan, Owen, Staib, and Anandan 1991).

Rohr (1994) describes a system for recognizing movements of pedestrians. He uses an approach which models the pedestrian by simplifying him to 14 cylinders with elliptic cross sections (for the head, torso, arms, and legs) (this originates from the cylinder model with circular cross sections from (Marr and Nishihara 1978)). The parameters necessary to describe the sizes of the cylinders and their movements with respect to each other are initially set using averaged results from a medical study. Then, these parameters are refined by estimations from both single and consecutive images.

1.1.2 Interpretation method based on a model

Other authors use the term 'model-based interpretation' to refer to an algorithm in which the interpretation method is based on a model. Often, this is done because it structures the interpretation algorithm. The system consists of different levels, usually arranged: one low level, zero or more intermediate levels, and one high level. These refer to the 'basicness' of the objects and the operations at each level. Low level objects and low level interpretation refer most often to objects as pixels or objects directly derivable from the pixels, and to operations processing these kind of objects. High level objects and operations refer to the representation of the most abstract objects in the application, and to the reasoning with these kind of objects. Their representation is completely dependent of the application. Most often, each level has its own knowledge repository, which can sometimes be accessed from higher levels.

Mayer, Heipke, and Maderlechner (1992) (see also Maderlechner and Mayer (1994)) present an interpretation system for a Bavarian cadastral map. Their model is organized in four levels (from high to low): semantic objects, graphics and text, image graph, and image. It is represented with a semantic network inspired by ERNEST (Niemann, Sagerer, Schröder, and Kummert 1990).

The semantic object level contains all objects from the map legend. In the graphics and text level, mainly neighbor relations and operations analyzing the thickness, position, etc. of objects are used. The image graph level consists of separated attribute graphs, each corresponding to a connected component in the image, and the image level contains the (binary) raster input image.

Puliti and Tascini (1993) present an interpretation system to support diagnostic biomedical image analysis (support the physician's clinical diagnosis of diabetes or systemic sclerosis diseases). It consists of three levels (from high to low): high level biomedical object interpretation, low level object interpretation, and image segmentation. A distinction is made between generic world knowledge (knowledge about visual perception, necessary for determining some meaning about the initial tokens supplied by the segmentation process), and specific problem-domain knowledge (knowledge about nail fold capillaries of the human finger, to determine the final interpretation and to solve possible ambiguities in the token detection).

The segmentation module generates an initial segmentation, which is refined by the low-level interpretation module to give more meaningful objects. In turn, it interacts with the segmentation module to e.g. compute necessary feature values. The recognition module attempts to

recognize objects or parts of objects with a goal-driven approach. After the generation of a hypothesis, attempts are made to falsify it. If that is not possible, it is accepted. The recognition module may influence the segmentation and the low-level interpretation by modifying control parameters.

1.1.3 Both object description and interpretation method based on a model

The approaches from the previous two sections can be combined. Then, the description of the objects to interpret is based on a model, and the interpretation method is based on a model (not always consisting of different levels). This is done because e.g. a structured interpretation is desired, and the variability of the objects is large. Several combinations can be made: the model of the object can consist of several layers and the model of the interpretation is not-layered (Denisov and Dudkin 1994), the model of the interpretation can be layered and the model of the object not (Kise, Yamaoka, Babaguchi, and Tezuka 1992), and both can be layered (den Hartog, ten Kate, and Gerbrands 1995, Schreiber, Wielinga, and Breuker 1993).

Some authors define a model-based method as consisting of a separate learning stage and matching stage. This is seen as a special form of the interpretation method, and therefore described in this section. In the learning stage, a model is constructed from each object to interpret. The model should be able to accurately describe the object, including the variation in which it can appear in the 'real world'. Robust detection methods are provided. Then, in the matching stage, the objects are interpreted. If objects are rejected they may be saved for later processing, e.g. by consideration of an operator or by an automatic procedure. This may be followed by changes in the model or in the values of the parameters. In this way, the model 'learns' to adapt on specific properties of the data.

Chang and Leou (1992) are an example of authors belonging to the last category. They describe an approach to representation and matching of object shape patterns. In the learning stage, all the available information is used to construct a model of the object. The model consists of a shape description of each object, together with statistical properties on the shape (allowed variability, etc.). In the matching stage, a set of object shapes extracted from input images is matched with corresponding shapes stored in the model.

Denisov and Dudkin (1994) describe a method for recognition of chromosomes. They use a model of a chromosome consisting of several layers, from bottom to top on the lowest layer the size, shape and brightness, then on a higher layer constraints on these values (a-priori information), next a layer considering the density profile, and finally a layer with predicates allowing e.g. direct access to information about band position and brightness intensities.

The interpretation method used is hypothesis construction/verification. Construction is done with a classifier trained on cell metaphase images, while verification is done with a-priori knowledge from the model. Different verifiers exist: if one fails another is used.

Kise et al. (1992) describe a frame based system for analyzing office document images (a frame describes a collection of attributes that a given object normally possesses and thus allow us to reason with 'commonsense knowledge'). Its aim is separation of layout and contents (no interpretation is done), and it is based on their analysis system for business (visiting) cards (Kise, Momota, Yamaoka, Sugiyama, Babaguchi, and Tezuka 1990). They define a (hierarchical) model that represents the layout structure and the logical structure of the target documents. The model is constructed automatically by generalizing instances of sample documents, and incrementally

refined by error feedback. Two kinds of frames are used: layout frames (to describe features of a distinct layout object) and similarity frames (to describe spatial similarity, difference or relation between layout objects).

In (den Hartog et al. 1995) an interpretation system for utility maps is described. They have an explicit description of the knowledge necessary for recognition of the different objects (houses, pipelines, arrows, etc.) and the relations between these objects (an arrow is next to a pipeline, etc.), in a specially designed high level language. Then, a semantic network is constructed from this description. This network consists of nodes describing the geometrical properties of the objects, and links describing the spatial relationships between these objects. The interpretation flow is guided by the semantic network because priorities are attached to the links. These links generate the search actions, and they determine the execution order of the search actions. Thus, this is a system with a layered object model and layered interpretation model because both the objects on the map and the interpretation flow are based on the same semantic network, and a semantic network is a multi level structure.

Schreiber et al. (1993) describe KADS (Knowledge Analysis and Documentation System), a structured methodology for the development of knowledge-based systems. Its development started in 1983. KADS is based on two central principles: multiple models are used to cope with the complexity of the knowledge engineering process, and knowledge-level descriptions are used as an intermediate model between expertise data and system design.

Models can be found in every part of a knowledge based system designed with KADS: from the knowledge acquisition process to a model which defines the problem to be solved formally. Knowledge acquisition often encounters the 'knowledge acquisition bottleneck': the problem to extract knowledge from an expert about how to perform a certain task efficiently. This knowledge should be extracted in such a way that it can be formalized in a computer system. Therefore, the approach taken in KADS is to make a distinction between the several activities in the process of knowledge acquisition: eliciting the knowledge in an informal (usually verbal) form from an expert, interpreting that data using some conceptual framework, and formalizing the conceptualization in such a way that the program can use the knowledge.

Objects are also represented with a model: such a model describes the objects and the operations working on these objects. The model is formulated in such a way that they capture the intuitions that humans have of this behavior.

In KADS, a model is defined as a reflection of selected characteristics of an empirical system in the real world by abstraction of detail. Thus, every model in KADS emphasizes certain aspects of the system to be built, and abstracts from others. Models are used to decompose the knowledge-engineering tasks: while building one model, the knowledge engineer can temporarily neglect certain other aspects. The complexity of the knowledge-engineering process is reduced through a divide-and-conquer strategy.

1.2 Discussion

The basic idea of model-based image interpretation is to approach interpretation problems in a different way. One of the usual interpretation methods is a bottom-up strategy: starting with the pixels on the lowest level, objects are formed, which are further grouped on higher levels, until a satisfactory interpretation has been found. However, this does not offer possibilities to use a-priori knowledge extensively, nor does it allow recognized parts on higher levels to solve detection problems on lower levels. Also, it can be very difficult to change an interpretation al-

gorithm for one type of application to a similar, but slightly different, other type of application.

The model-based approach is a combination of bottom-up and top-down strategies which can be intertwined. A-priori knowledge about the images or the objects in the images ('expectations of reality') can be used at various places and on various levels: on a low level e.g. to group pixels, to guide the segmentation, or to correct the vectorization, and on higher levels to guide, improve, correct, or simplify the interpretation. If anomalies are detected the top-down link allows to influence low level processes, for example by starting a renewed search for objects which must be present at some place in the neighborhood.

Ideally, the a-priori knowledge must be specified explicitly in some way. When changing to a similar application, the model for the basic interpretation flow should be easy to change, and it should be possible to re-use parts. In this section, a structure for model-based interpretation is proposed. In chapter 5 an implementation is given for the interpretation of two types of maps.

1.2.1 Proposed model structure

The model-based interpretation structure is based on the principle 'both object description and interpretation method based on a model' from section 1.1.3. The object description is based on a model because then the objects can be described in a modular way and variation between objects of the same class can be described more easily, and the interpretation method is based on a model because it structures the interpretation algorithm and because objects found on a higher level can influence the construction of objects on lower levels.

The following models are defined.

Model of the interpretation flow. This model describes the flow of the interpretation process. It describes what modules are present, how these are connected, and what the information flow is during the interpretation process. It does not describe the implementation of the modules, only a description of their functionality.

Model of the map. This model specifies which objects can be found in the map, the relation between the objects, where they must be found, and what can go wrong in this process. It also specifies which structures must be found (e.g. for cadastral maps: lots), how they must be found, and what can go wrong. A number of methods are provided to solve problems.

Model of the object. This model describes how the object can be found. This model is closely intertwined with the model of the map.

The model of the interpretation flow can be independent of the application, while the model of the map and the models of the objects are very dependent on the application. However, it is very well possible that parts of the model of the map can be used for different models of the map: for instance, in the map interpretation system in chapter 5, the module which finds line objects in the image is exactly the same for both types of maps, while the module that finds numbers is only slightly different.

Other modules are not present in one model of a map, but can be present in another, or they can have the same functionality but a different implementation because of specific characteristics of that map.

Details on the construction of the models and their implementations are given in chapter 5.

We have chosen to emphasize on maps, rather than on other kinds of line drawings or grey value or even color images. Grey value or color images were not considered because the first problem to be solved before all others is the segmentation problem, which is very difficult. Rather than solving this problem, another interesting problem of how to interpret images was chosen. For being able to concentrate on this problem, the segmentation should not be really difficult. Therefore, binary images were chosen.

The emphasis in interpreting images in this thesis was on maps rather than on other kinds of line drawings (e.g. schematics, CAD drawings, etc.). This was done because cadastral maps (the first problem attacked) are relatively simple compared to other line drawings. Also, cadastral maps are made with a model (the rules used when drawing the map). These rules are even laid down in a regulation by the Dutch Government (Minister van VROM 1989) (in English: the Minister of Public Housing, Zoning, and Environment).

Another reason to emphasize on maps is because it is an economically interesting problem. Still a large number of maps only exist on paper or film, and do not have a computerized representation (in spite of the accessibility and the simplicity of incorporating changes in the latter representation). The reason for this is that the most straightforward method for converting from paper to the computerized representation is by redrawing the map (with a mouse on a digitizing table) and interpretation by hand, but this is cumbersome and laborious. Since computers have not succeeded very well (yet) in the automatic interpretation of maps it is also a very interesting research problem.

1.3 Overview of the thesis

Chapter 2 describes an initial approach to the interpretation of cadastral maps. This is done completely bottom-up, but there are two separate paths in the interpretation flow which can be used to correct the interpretation. A small pilot study was done to investigate this. However, results of this pilot study have not been evaluated since a new (model-based) approach with better results is presented in chapter 5.

The interpretation is based on vectorization of the maps. However, vectorization can give rise to a number of problems: for example lines may be discontinuous due to the scanning process, and too many nodes and edges can be generated. Solutions are proposed for solving these problems.

An important contribution of this chapter is the evaluation strategy. It consists of two parts: evaluation of the vectorization and evaluation of the interpretation. Both are used in subsequent chapters.

Chapter 3 presents a method for compilation of mosaics from separately scanned line drawings. The model used is low level: finding matching edges in the vectorization. Compiling mosaics is an important problem: the algorithm described offers a possibility to scan line drawings separately, to combine them, and then to provide the interpretation process with the resulting image (as if it were one large image). The use of (costly) A0 size scanners can be avoided.

The algorithm is not only applicable to maps, it can be applied to all kinds of line drawings. It may even be applicable to other types of drawings. The only restriction is that the algorithm has to find matching vectors in the overlap area, so there have to be lines in the overlap area.

Chapter 4 describes an algorithm for the vectorization of line drawings. The method is model-based (or adaptive) because the original input image is used for improving and correcting the vectorization. Vectorization is a very important step in the interpretation process, and it should be done very precisely. Therefore, a thorough analysis of the vectorization method is presented and evaluated on various line drawing images (not only on maps). A comparison with approaches described in the literature is given.

Chapter 5 presents a model-based interpretation algorithm for two types of maps: cadastral maps and large scale base maps. It uses the model structure from section 1.2.1. First, an interpretation system for cadastral maps is constructed. Then, to show that the method can be applied to other types of maps, the algorithm is changed for interpretation of large scale base maps. The models, the algorithms, and the changes necessary are discussed in detail. It appears that the changes are relatively straightforward.

For evaluation of the performance on cadastral maps, (among others) the same maps as in chapter 2 are used. A better performance can be observed.

1.4 Vocabulary used in model-based image processing

This section summarizes the vocabulary used in this thesis. Most definitions are from two dictionaries (Houghton Mifflin Company 1985, Fontana/Collins 1986), from a thesaurus (Houghton Mifflin Company 1988), or from two textbooks (Rich 1988, Gonzalez and Woods 1992), but this will not always be mentioned. If standard meanings are not available, a personal interpretation will be given.

1.4.1 Model, knowledge

Model. In the literature, a model is described with several definitions:

1. A tentative description of a system or theory that accounts for all of its known properties (Houghton Mifflin Company 1985).
2. A representation of something, designed for a special purpose. This representation may take many forms, depending on the purpose in hand, e.g.: (1) to remind ourselves of something we already know about (a model airplane); (2) for discovery (a model airplane placed in a wind-tunnel); (3) for explanation (the solar system as a model of the atom). Models have one characteristic in common: the mapping of elements in the system modeled onto the model (Fontana/Collins 1986).

In our research this last definition can be extended to: (4) simplification, (5) clarification and (6) structuring. The model is the formulation of the expectations of reality. It includes the methodology to interpret. Objects and the relations between objects are also described with a model. This has been described above, and will be further described and defined more precisely in chapter 5.

Different kinds of models. Different kinds of models can be considered:

1. The *real world* or *scene model* (where are we looking at): this includes models which describe the shape or visual appearance, and models for capturing knowledge concerning the relations of the objects to be seen.

2. The *sensor model*: this describes the way the sensor 'projects' the scene on the image. Each sensor has its own specific characteristics, which can be anticipated if known.
3. The *image data model*: this describes the way the data actually looks like (not every 2D or 3D function is an image).
4. The *model of the interpretation flow*: this describes the flow of the interpretation process. It describes what modules are present, how these are connected, and what the information flow is during the interpretation process. It does not describe the implementation of the modules, only a description of what they are supposed to do.
5. The *interpretation model* or the *model of the map*: this specifies which objects can be found in the map (considering maps), the relations between the objects, where they must be found, and what can go wrong in this process. It also specifies which structures must be found, how they must be found, and what can go wrong. A number of methods are provided to solve problems.
6. The *model of the object*: this describes how the object can be found. This model is closely intertwined with the model of the map.

The last three models are discussed in detail in this chapter and in chapter 5.

Knowledge. In literature: cognitive or intellectual mental components acquired and retained through study and experience.

This is simplified to: a proposition that is considered to be true. For example: 'grass is green', or 'a connection sign consists of ≥ 2 blobs of size ≥ 1 pixels arranged in a serpentine like shape crossing a line'. Sometimes, knowledge can be verified to reality, but in practice it is assumed to be true.

Different kinds of knowledge exist: knowledge about the application, about the model, about the objects in an image, etc. Other kinds of knowledge are procedural knowledge, which deals with operations like selecting algorithms and setting parameters for these algorithms (e.g. setting a threshold value for an image thresholding algorithm), and visual knowledge, which deals with aspects of image formation (e.g. when scanning a line drawing it is best to set the resolution of the scanner to at least twice the thickness of the thinnest line in the line drawing because otherwise lines may 'disappear'). A distinction can be made in a-priori knowledge and knowledge generated during interpretation. For simplicity, real world knowledge (knowledge about 'every day life') is incorporated in the a-priori knowledge.

Knowledge is acquired from e.g. an expert or from an expert system. It can be represented e.g. with logical systems (predicate calculus), with semantic networks, or with production systems (expert systems).

Expectations. Things that can be verified (and falsified) with reality. For example: 'today it is dry weather', or 'every parcel has exactly one number'. An expectation can be an instantiation of knowledge: knowing that something specific is grass, and combining that with the knowledge 'grass is green', one can conclude that that specific object has the color green.

Information. Knowledge resulting from the interpretation.

Predicate calculus. Predicate calculus is a system which allows to process statements whose truth depends on variables, e.g. 'X gives Y to Z'. These kinds of statements are called 'predicates', and their theory is called predicate calculus. The system is capable of handling a broad range of mathematical expressions, such as Boolean expressions.

Semantic networks. Semantic networks are labeled, directed graphs in which the nodes usually represent objects or variables, and the arcs represent relationships between the nodes. They have an intuitive and visually effective way of representing knowledge. Because the representation is a graph, graph matching and labeling techniques may be used to manipulate the elements in the graph or the graph itself.

Production systems, expert systems. Production systems or expert systems offer an alternative to predicate calculus or semantic networks. As with these two, production systems require matching in order to identify which inference to make. However, the actions of a production system after a match has been found can have arbitrary complexity.

1.4.2 Reasoning

Hypothesis. An explanation that accounts for a set of facts and that can be tested by further investigation.

During interpretation, hypotheses are generated. Hypotheses can be confirmed or rejected with different methods: as soon as they are generated, they are tested (a sort of depth-first search, 'jumping to conclusions'), or they can be saved for later testing (a sort of breadth-first search, 'postpone the decision'). In this thesis, the latter approach is taken because this allows to search for the 'easy to find' objects first. The former approach has as disadvantage that in case of errors in the interpretation a whole tree of (possibly wrong or invalid) hypotheses may be generated and such a tree must be traversed immediately. Checking all these hypotheses may be computationally expensive.

Ground truth. That, what is *really* true. Considering interpretation of maps, one can think of two different things: first what is shown on the paper map, secondly what was meant by the drawer of the map when it was drawn (in case of drawing errors this may be different from what is actually on the map). In the context of this thesis, the first definition is used.

1.4.3 Learning

Prototype. Typical or representative object that is used with a classifier to learn that class of objects.

1.4.4 Recognition, interpretation, understanding

Recognition. An awareness that something perceived has been perceived before, or to perceive something to be similar with something held in memory.

Interpretation, understanding. Interpretation is the act, process, or result of explaining to oneself the meaning of something. Understanding means to perceive and comprehend the na-

ture and significance of something; to know, or: the faculty (in the mind) of thinking, reasoning and acquiring and applying knowledge. In image processing, giving meaning to an image is often called: image understanding.

Gonzalez and Woods (1992) consider interpretation and understanding synonyms. This is also done in the context of this thesis.

Recognition vs. interpretation, understanding. The difference between recognition on one side and interpretation or understanding on the other, is that with recognition the object is only recognized (i.e. it is detected that the object is known because it is seen before in, for instance, a learning phase). Recognition can happen locally. Interpretation or understanding is more than recognition: after recognition, reasoning can take place, new knowledge can be generated from the interpretation of an object, and eventually self-learning can happen.

1.4.5 Domain, application, generic, specific

Domain. A domain is a sphere of activity, concern, or function; a field. Thus, the domain is the larger of the whole: e.g. the domain of map interpretation.

Application. An application is a task in a certain domain. For instance, the application is cadastral map interpretation in the domain of map interpretation. In one domain different tasks can exist: e.g. interpretation of cadastral maps and interpretation of large scale base maps are both tasks in the domain of map interpretation.

Generic. Relating to or descriptive of an entire group or class. For example: generic interpretation is a kind of interpretation easily adaptable for different kinds of objects and different kinds of maps.

Specific. Relating to or descriptive of one object. For example: specific for one object or application means that a set of properties are only valid for this one object, and not for others.

1.4.6 Objects

Primitive object. A primitive object is the basic object for recognition: it cannot be decomposed into other (sub)objects or primitives. The application specifies whether an object is a primitive object or not.

Compound object, entity. A compound object or an entity is built from one or more primitive objects (and subsequently can be decomposed into primitives).

Symbol. A symbol is a primitive or a compound object with some kind of meaning attached. For example, the symbols in the legend of the map or characters designating objects in the map.

Pixel object, connected component. Set of connected pixels. At some place in the interpretation process, an interpretation will be attached.

Vector object. Object described by vectors. For example, a polygon can be described with vectors.

Pixel object vs. vector objects. Sometimes, objects can be described both as pixel objects and as vector objects. For instance, the lines in a binary image can be described by both. An advantage of using the pixel representation is that pixel based operations as dilation and erosion can be used, which provide e.g. a simple method for determining the distance to other pixel objects. An advantage of using the vector representation is that vector based operations can be used. This is very useful in e.g. determining the intersection of two lines.

Pixel objects can be approximated by their minimum bounding rectangle or by their convex hull (although not always very accurate). In this way an approximation in vectors can be obtained so that vector operations can be used. The reverse is also true: by drawing the minimum bounding rectangle or convex hull of a vector object in an image, a pixel object can be obtained so that pixel operations can be applied.

Point feature. Features which can be localized in one point on the map. Examples of these are characters, poles, manhole covers, or more abstract: small squares or circles.

Line feature, curve feature. Features which can be localized on a line (respectively on a curve) and have a certain length. Examples are (dashed) lines, boundary lines or railroads.

Area feature. Features which can be localized on an area on the map. Examples of these are parcels.

1.4.7 Processing methods

Bottom-up processing. Bottom-up processing starts with the (raw) data (this is necessarily at the lowest level). After subsequent processes, possibly organized in different levels, the image has been processed and more abstract descriptions are formed. There is no feedback from higher layers to lower layers.

Top-down processing. Top-down processing starts on the highest level with an abstract object. Then, after subsequent processes possibly organized in different levels, a low level representation of the object is found. The object is often represented on the low level by pixels.

Model-based processing. The interpretation flow is directed by the model, specifying which objects can be expected, how they look like (e.g. compared to prototypes), and how they should be detected.

Data-driven processing. Data driven processing reasons from the data (which may be structured in one way or another) to the interpretation desired.

Bottom-up processing vs. data-driven processing. Data-driven processing is not necessarily the same as bottom-up processing since the data may be organized in some way so that the interpretation can be more structured. This is in contrast with the data in raw form used in bottom-up processing.

1.4.8 Humans

Expert. The expert provides the knowledge for the model-based or knowledge-based system. There are different experts: the expert on the domain, the expert on the application, and the expert on building models or designing a knowledge base.

Operator. The person who is operating the system. Most often, he/she is the casual user.

1.5 Conclusion

In this chapter, several notions of model-based have been described. Unfortunately, there is no common notion. There is not even a classification of the different approaches. The same is true for a number of words used in this field. Therefore, in this chapter proposals are made for a (coarse) classification of model-based strategies, and for a common vocabulary. The classification of the different interpretation methods is: object description based on a model, interpretation strategy based on a model, and both the object description and the interpretation method based on a model. The method proposed by the author of this thesis is in the last category.

That it is necessary to define a common vocabulary can be seen for example at meetings of people working in the field of model-based image processing. One extreme example was a lecturer who was not able to give his talk, because after the first few words he was interrupted by someone from the audience who had a completely different interpretation of one word. The time given for the presentation was filled up with a discussion between the lecturer and the audience on this one word, instead on the topic he was invited to talk about.

Evaluation method for an automatic map interpretation system for cadastral maps

2

This chapter discusses a base line system for automatic interpretation of Dutch cadastral maps. Basic knowledge of the rules for drawing these maps is incorporated in the system. Vectorization is the basis for the interpretation process. Problems in vectorizing line drawings will be discussed, and solutions will be proposed. Also, a method for evaluating the system is presented. This method consists of different parts which subsequently evaluate the vectorization, the performance on finding lots, and on finding lot numbers. Parts of this evaluation method may also be applicable for other line drawing interpretation systems, and forms the basis for evaluation in the remainder of this thesis.

Keywords: Automatic Map Interpretation, Evaluation, Vectorization.

2.1 Introduction

Automatic map interpretation is a relatively new field in image processing (Ejiri, Kakumoto, Miyatake, Shimada, and Iwamura 1990, Suzuki and Yamada 1990). Until recently, maps like cadastral maps were mainly drawn by hand on paper or film, and then stored in large cabinets. The disadvantage of this compared to computer accessible maps is the large cost for drawing, storing and maintaining them, and their fragility since paper maps are easily torn. After some updates a completely new map must be made to incorporate these changes.

By contrast, computer stored maps are readily accessible, changes are very easy to incorporate, and they can be accessed from different locations using graphic terminals. Information can be processed using e.g. Geographic Information Systems (GIS) (Hickin, Maguire, and Strachan 1991, ESRI 1992).

Nowadays, new maps are often made with the computer. Old maps (drawn on paper or film) can be acquired by scanning them and storing them on disk or tape. However, for meaningful queries some kind of interpretation is necessary. This can be done in several ways, of which human interpretation is the most obvious, and, because of the time required, also the most expensive.

In this chapter, a base line system for cadastral map interpretation is presented. The basic knowledge of rules cartographers use for drawing is incorporated in the system. This high level knowledge enables us to anticipate the objects that are to be recognized. Problems associated with a good vectorization are discussed. Several 'clean up' rules to improve the vectorization are proposed, and their net effect is evaluated. This is different from the approach followed in

⁰This chapter is an enlarged version of (Janssen, Duin, and Vossepoel 1993).

e.g. the map recognition system of (Ejiri et al. 1990), in which a human operator is needed for improvement of the vectorization generated by the computer.

Another contribution of this chapter is an evaluation method for the system presented. It is the basis for the evaluation of algorithms further on in this thesis. The emphasis is on vectorization because we believe this is an essential first step in interpretation of line drawings. Vectorization gives a large reduction in storage and processing time of data. Its result is scale independent and allows easy computation of e.g. intersection points or angles between lines.

The system as described in this chapter is the base line system for algorithms described in the remainder of this thesis. Vectorization and its associated problems will be described in more detail in chapter 4, and a more elaborate interpretation system is presented in chapter 5.

In the next sections, first a description of the base line map interpretation system is given, including problems encountered during vectorization and possible solutions for this. This is followed by our evaluation strategy. Maps used, results and a discussion of the results are reported.

2.2 Base line map interpretation system

The system is depicted in figure 2.1. In the following sections the different parts are described.

Figure 2.1: the base line map interpretation system.

Inputs to the system

The inputs are cadastral maps, scanned with high resolution, high quality binary scanners (specifications follow in section 2.3.3). We call these scanned maps *bitmaps*. Typical sections of the maps used in evaluating the system are shown in figures 2.2 and 2.3.

On cadastral maps *parcels* are drawn. A parcel has one *parcel number* (no more, no less). The

Figure 2.2: section (1970 × 2000 pixels) of map geo.

Figure 2.3: section (2000 × 2000 pixels) of map leiden.

Figure 2.4: examples of connection signs. The five on the left are from map 'geo', the five on the right from map 'leiden'.

Figure 2.5: examples of building hatches in map 'geo'. Building hatches may have crossing lines or can be drawn through connection signs as shown.

cadastral map specifies where this area can be found in the real world. The number, which is usually in the middle of one of the polygons of the parcels, is used for reference. Different polygons which belong to the same parcel are connected using *connection signs* (small dotted S-like shapes). Examples are shown in figure 2.4.

A parcel number of a parcel is sometimes written outside the polygon(s) of the parcel: if the polygons are too small so that they cannot contain the parcel number, the parcel number is written next to the parcel, enclosed with dots, and a dotted line is made from this dotted circle to the inside of one of the polygons of the parcel. This happened only once in our maps: see parcel 3568 in the top rightmost corner of map 'leiden' in figure 2.3. We decided to not interpret this kind of parcel because there is no possibility to make a separate learn and test set.

Sometimes, *building hatches* are found on cadastral maps (figure 2.5). Map 'geo' has some of them. These are short parallel lines pointing to the inside of the buildings on a parcel.

The rules for drawing cadastral maps are laid down in a regulation by the Dutch Government (Minister van VROM 1989).

Outputs from the system

The outputs of the system are parcel descriptions consisting of nodes, edges and numbers. These are represented with a data structure containing an array of parcels and an array of polygon numbers. Each element of the array of parcels consists of a list of polygon numbers part of that parcel. Each element of the array of polygon numbers refers to a parcel number in that polygon, or NIL if the polygon does not contain a parcel number. Using these two arrays, the parcels and their numbers can be reconstructed.

The vectorization is stored in a special graph representation data structure which topologically represents the graph. That is, nodes are a special data type, and edges are a special data type, and these are connected with pointers as the nodes and edges in the graph. Polygons are identified with a label associated with the edge data type (each edge allows two such labels for

a polygon at each side of the edge). Given a polygon number, using the vectorization structure the vectors of the polygon can be reconstructed.

Noise removal and skeletonization

Because our scanned maps are almost noise free, a median filter suffices to close small irregularities in the bitmap caused by e.g. pixels having 'wrong' values (figure 2.6(a)–(c)) (this happens for approximately 25 pixels in a block of 1000×1000 pixels). Figure 2.6(d) shows an example of an irregularity caused by a non-continuous flow of ink from the drawing pen, and figure 2.6(e) shows a very special case of an irregularity. These will influence the vectorization algorithm. However, rules described below are provided to correct for this.

Following the noise removal, a pseudo Euclidean skeleton is used (Verwer 1988). This is an improvement of the Hilditch skeleton (Hilditch 1969) because a better (almost Euclidean) metric is used. This ensures that the skeletonization is less sensitive to rotations when compared to the Hilditch skeleton. Another advantage is that the skeleton is more 'straight' (see figure 2.7).

Figure 2.6: examples of fractions of maps with pixels having 'wrong' values. In the last example, the pixels do not really have a wrong value but a gap is introduced because the building hatches and the lines are intersecting.

Vectorization algorithm

Following the skeletonization, the resulting image is vectorized with the Douglas-Peucker algorithm (Douglas and Peucker 1973) as implemented in the CARV (Cartographic Raster-to-Vector) package (Moore 1992). This algorithm is explained in more detail in chapter 4. The results of the vectorization (*nodes* and *edges*) are stored in a special graph representation data structure as discussed above.

Figure 2.7: differences between the Hilditch and the pseudo Euclidian skeleton.

'Clean up' rules for the vectorization

Due to the use of skeletons, the vectorization may have short unnecessary or spurious edges. We have designed rules (the *clean up rules*) to refine the vectorization.

The rule to close gaps in the vectorization finds two end nodes on distance $\leq 3w_{glob}$ pixels (w_{glob} is the global line thickness). If their edges make a bend angle of $|\alpha| \leq 5^\circ$, the two nodes are replaced with a new node in their middle. For an example, see figure 2.8. The nodes (i) and (ii) are removed and replaced by (iii).

Another rule removes link nodes whose two edges make an angle of almost 180° . This is done if the bend angle between the edges is $|\alpha| \leq 5^\circ$. This is shown in figure 2.9. Node (i) is removed in the process.

In corners in the vectorization, often a short unnecessary line is generated. The procedure to correct these corners is illustrated with figure 2.10. The following have to be satisfied for firing this rule:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{length}(ii) &\leq 10 \text{ pixels,} \\ \text{length}(i) &\geq 3 \times \text{length}(ii), \quad \text{length}(iii) \geq 3 \times \text{length}(ii), \\ 95^\circ &\leq \angle(i, ii) \leq 175^\circ, \quad 95^\circ \leq \angle(ii, iii) \leq 175^\circ, \quad 45^\circ \leq \angle(i, iii) \leq 135^\circ \end{aligned}$$

The new node is the intersection of the base of the two long edges (i) and (iii). It replaces edge (ii) as shown in the figure.

T-junctions usually consist of three long edges, but sometimes spurious short edges are generated. An example is given in figure 2.11 with three short edges ((iv), (v) and (vi)), but it can also happen that there are only one or two short edges. The following have to be satisfied for

Figure 2.8: example of the rule to correct gaps in the vectorization. (a) shows the skeletonization plotted on the bitmap, (b) the raw vectorization from the skeleton, and (c) the resulting refined vectorization.

Figure 2.9: example of the rule to remove certain link nodes. The top figure shows the skeletonization plotted on the bitmap, the middle figure the raw vectorization from the skeleton, and the bottom figure the resulting refined vectorization.

firing this rule (rules for edges (iv), (v) and (vi) only if they are present):

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{length}(iv) \leq 10, \text{ length}(v) \leq 10, \text{ length}(vi) \leq 10 \text{ pixels,} \\ &\text{length}(i) \geq 3 \times \text{length}(iv), \text{ length}(ii) \geq 3 \times \text{length}(v), \text{ length}(iii) \geq 3 \times \text{length}(vi) \end{aligned}$$

Next, the two long edges making a bend angle of $|\alpha| \leq 10^\circ$ are determined (in the example edges (i) and (iii)). The intersection of the base of each of these two edges with the base of the remaining long edge is computed, and the new point is the geometrical average of these two intersection points. This will be the new node to replace all the nodes in the center of the T. If the bend angle of all the long edges is $|\alpha| > 10^\circ$, the base of each long edge is intersected with the base of each other long edge, and the geometrical average of these three intersection points becomes the new node.

X-junctions are sometimes vectorized as two separate T-junctions as shown in an example in figure 2.12. Then, the two T-junctions are connected with a very short line. The rule to correct X-junctions uses the length of the edge between nodes (i) and (ii). If this length is shorter than 4 pixels, the two nodes are snapped to a new node in the middle of the two old ones.

The results of these refinements are a reduction in the number of nodes and edges, at the cost

Figure 2.10: example of the corner clean up rule. (a): a small part of map 'geo'. (b): enlargement of the skeletonization of (a) plotted in black on it. (c): the raw vectorization from the skeleton. Nodes are white, edges black. Edge (ii) is unnecessary because it is short. Using constraints as described in the text, the vectorization can be corrected as shown in (d).

Figure 2.11: example of the rule to correct T-junctions. (a) shows the skeletonization plotted on the bitmap, (b) the raw vectorization from the skeleton, and (c) the resulting refined vectorization.

Figure 2.12: example of the rule to correct X-junctions. (a) shows the skeletonization plotted on the bitmap, (b) the raw vectorization from the skeleton, and (c) the resulting refined vectorization.

of a small increase in vectorization error (see the 'results and discussion' section). The thresholds above are not chosen with a theoretically founded method. They produced satisfactory results. A vectorization algorithm having less thresholds to adjust and producing better results than the Douglas-Peucker algorithm combined with clean up rules is described in chapter 4.

Detection of the connection signs

Connection signs consist of small blobs which are located near to each other. If we dilate the original image, the connection signs will become connected to the other lines, and after skeletonization the short lines are part of the connection signs. Next, they can be isolated. This is illustrated with an example in figure 2.13.

Figure 2.13: example how connection signs are found. (a) the original connection sign (excerpt from a larger image), (b) the dilated connection sign, (c) the pseudo Euclidian skeleton, (d) only the branches from the skeleton, (e) the branch points from the skeleton in (c) that touch (d), (f) dilation of the branch points, (g) OR of (d) and (f), (h) pseudo Euclidian skeleton from (g).

Detection of the parcels

The parcels are detected with a propagation of the connection signs in the original bitmap. Propagation is a process for extracting connected components (Serra 1982, Gonzalez and Woods 1992). The term 'propagation' was used by for example (Goetcherian 1980) and (Preston and Duff 1984).

Detection of the parcel numbers

To find the parcel numbers, small objects in the bitmap (i.e. numbers and characters, see below for their detection) are AND-ed with the inverse of the street image to remove the small objects that are in the street (i.e. the street names). If the parcel numbers and the street names are put in small, separate images, they can be sent to a character recognition system.

The parcels are not used for detecting the parcel numbers (see figure 2.1). Thus, the parcel numbers found can be used for correcting errors in finding the parcels, or vice versa. A small pilot study was done to investigate this. That system had additional postprocessing. The postprocessing consisted of constructing a list of parcels having no parcel numbers. For each parcel in that list, a local search with changed thresholds was done in each polygon of the parcel to find parcel numbers or to find missed connection signs. From a small experiment on a 1150×1270 pixels sized image it appeared that parcels incorrectly found before were found correctly.

However, this pilot system has not been evaluated because another (model-based) system was developed which is described in chapter 5.

Small object removal

To detect the small objects in the image, a histogram is made from the length of the diagonal of the bounding box of each connected component (the bounding box has axes parallel to the x- and y-axis). Small objects (characters, small blobs, etc.) are divided among the lower bins while the larger (lines, etc.) are divided among the upper bins. The bin of the first peak in the histogram is used to find the bin separating the small and large objects: from the bin of the peak a search is done for a series of consecutive empty bins. This number of consecutive empty bins is determined by the minimum of the bin number having the peak, and the value of the peak.

The last bin of the series of empty bins is used to separate the small objects from the large objects. Next, the small objects can be isolated or removed.

2.3 Evaluation

2.3.1 Evaluating the vectorization

Because vectorization is very important for both data reduction and for reasoning, it should be checked thoroughly. To review the effects of the 'clean up' rules, both the raw (not cleaned) vectorization and the refined (cleaned) result are evaluated. To prevent border-effects all edges which have an endpoint are removed. Only polygons will remain. Desired are both long edges and high accuracy of the vectorization.

At the base of the scoring mechanism is our *vectorization evaluation criterion*:

We consider the vectorization satisfactory if, when it is plotted in the original image, the original image overlaps the plotted vectorization.

An example of this is shown in figure 2.14. The error is measured in two ways: the number of pixels wrong and the number of lines wrong. The number of nodes and edges in the vectorization is also reported.

Figure 2.14: (a): example of a correct vectorization, (b): example of a wrong vectorization (next to the dashed arrow). Nodes of the vectorization are white, edges black. The original bitmap is given in grey.

map	figure	drawing method	x size	y size	# pixels		res. (dpi)	scale
					total	object		
geo	2.2	template	1970	2400	4 728 000	364 198	508	unknown ¹
leiden	2.3	hand	2800	2700	7 560 000	571 297	400	1:1000

Table 2.1: general information about the maps used.

Number of pixels wrong in the vectorization

A 'wrong pixel' is defined as a pixel of the vectorization which is not covered by the original bitmap. The percentage wrong is calculated with $\frac{N_W}{N_T} \times 100\%$, with N_W the total number of wrong pixels, and N_T the total number of pixels in the vectorization. In figure 2.14(b), 11 pixels are wrong on a total of 56.

Number of lines wrong in the vectorization

A 'wrong line' is defined as a line of maximum length which can be formed from connecting 'wrong pixels'. Such a line is always part of an edge of the vectorization. Reported is the number of wrong lines of each length, and their length. In figure 2.14(b), there is one line wrong with a length of 11 pixels.

2.3.2 Evaluating the interpretation

Evaluation of the parcels

The correctly found parcels (N_C) are given relative to the number of parcels completely in the field of view (N_T). N_T is called the total number of parcels, and can be seen as the 'ground truth'. Some parcels consist of more than one polygon. For counting a parcel as correctly found, all of its polygons have to be found.

Evaluation of the parcel numbers

Only the parcel numbers of the parcels completely in the field of view are evaluated. The following symbols are used: N_T (total number of parcel numbers, the 'ground truth'), N_C (number of correctly found parcel numbers by the system), N_I (number of insertions or false positives), and N_D (number of deletions or false negatives). The percentage correctly found parcel numbers is calculated according to $\frac{N_C}{N_T} \times 100\%$, and the percentage corrections necessary is calculated according to $\frac{N_I + N_D}{N_T} \times 100\%$.

2.3.3 Description of the maps used

For evaluation, two different maps were used. See table 2.1. These maps are both cadastral maps. From map 'geo', a small part of size 700×700 pixels (shown in figure 2.10(a)) was used for development. Map 'leiden' was not used for development, so evaluation gives an indication of the performance of our algorithm on independent cadastral maps. Map 'geo' was scanned with a Scitex ELP 2 scanner, and map 'leiden' with a Vidar A0 scanner. The entry 'template' in

¹The scale is not written on the map. Unfortunately, its location is also unknown, thus it is not possible to determine the scale by measurements in the real world and comparing this with measurements on the map.

map	# pixels			# nodes	# edges	# of lines of length				
	in vect.	wrong	%			≥ 1	≥ 2	≥ 3	≥ 5	≥ 10
geo raw	45 020	36	0.1	1764	1852	20	12	4	0	0
geo refined	45 351	368	0.8	1412	1499	55	32	20	12	5
leiden raw	89 709	69	0.1	2400	2692	41	14	7	2	0
leiden refined	90 574	1119	1.2	1653	1945	315	156	85	49	17

Table 2.2: the number of pixels wrong in the vectorization, the number of nodes and edges, and the number of lines wrong sorted on their length in pixels.

map	N_T	N_C	%
geo	40	29	72.5
leiden, all parcels	104	71	68.3
leiden, only with cosi	86	69	80.2

Table 2.3: the evaluation of the parcels found.

the column 'drawing method' indicates that the map was drawn by hand, but that the characters and numbers were written using a template.

2.3.4 Results and discussion

Evaluation of the vectorization

Table 2.2 shows the results on the evaluation of the vectorization. The error *increases* after refinement of the vectorization. This is caused for instance by cut-off corners or curves where many short edges are substituted by one or two longer ones. Another possibility why the error may increase is illustrated with figure 2.15. In that figure, the line in the bitmap is very slightly curved. The raw vectorization had two nodes in that curve (see figure (a)), but one of the clean up rules (the rule to remove link nodes whose edges make an angle of almost 180°) did remove these two nodes, as shown in (b). Thus, the number of nodes and edges decreased with two, but the number of pixels wrong increased with 144, and one new line wrong was generated with a length of 144 pixels. In chapter 4, a new vectorization algorithm is presented which ensures that the error of the vectorization does not increase using the clean up rules.

In table 2.2, the number of pixels in the refined vectorization increases. This is caused e.g. by small lines which are removed: see figure 2.16.

The benefit of the refinements is mainly a substantial reduction in the number of nodes and edges at the cost of a small increase in error.

From the table it follows that the lines which are formed by the pixels that are wrong according to our criterion, are generally very short. Of the lines that are wrong, 90% are shorter than 10 pixels (for map 'leiden' 10 pixels is approximately 0.6 mm).

Evaluation of the parcels found

Only parcels which are completely in the field of view are evaluated. See table 2.3. For map 'leiden' we decided to either count all the parcels, or to count parcels having one or more connec-

(a)

(b)

Figure 2.15: one of the reasons the error increases using the clean up rules.

Figure 2.16: one of the reasons the number of pixels of the refined vectorization increases. The left figure has 45 pixels in the vectorization, and the right 47 pixels.

map	N_T	N_C	%	N_I	N_D	necessary corrections %
geo	40	40	100	1	0	2.5
leiden, all parcels	103	86	83.5	3	17	19.4
leiden, only with cosi	85	70	82.4	3	15	21.2

Table 2.4: the evaluation of the parcel numbers found.

tion signs (abbreviated as cosi). This has been done because the development map only contained parcels with a connection sign. Map 'leiden', however, contained 18 parcels without a connection sign (e.g. parcels 3534, 3535 and 3528).

Errors in finding the parcels have two different causes. Since a connection sign is necessary for finding a parcel, the algorithm fails if a connection sign cannot be found. The other cause is that propagation is used in finding the edges of the polygons which belong to the same parcel. If the polygon is not closed (this may have been caused by a digitizing error), the propagation proceeds into other parcels, and subsequently causes errors in the detection of these parcels.

Note that the number of correctly found parcels for map 'leiden' is two less when only parcels with connection signs are counted. This is caused by two parcels without connection signs which were accidentally detected correctly (by erroneously interpreting part of a parcel number for a connection sign).

Evaluation of the parcel numbers found

For the performance on finding the parcel numbers, see table 2.4. For map 'leiden', the total number of parcel numbers is one smaller than the number of parcels (table 2.3). This is due to a (human) drawing error in the map: one parcel does not have a number. In fact, this is a violation of the drawing rules.

Errors in not finding the parcel numbers are caused by parcel numbers attached to the parcel boundary they belong to. The method for finding parcel numbers presumes that they are isolated, and it will fail to find them if they are not.

2.4 Conclusions and summary

This chapter discusses a base line automatic map interpretation system. Also, it presents a method for evaluating the performance of this system. Parts of this method may also be use-

ful in evaluating other line drawing interpretation systems.

Different performance methods are presented: for the vectorization we report on the number of nodes and edges in the vectorization, and we measure the number of pixels wrong, and the size distribution of the lines that are wrong. Next, the number of correctly classified parcels and correctly classified parcel numbers is reported. We think that the performance of an automatic map interpretation system can be estimated reliably from these parameters.

This system is a base line system for cadastral map interpretation. In the following chapters, we will describe methods and algorithms for a better map interpretation system, in which a more extensive integration of top-down and bottom-up processing can be found. Also, more context will be used for the interpretation.

Compilation of mosaics from separately scanned line drawings

3

In automatic line drawing interpretation (e.g. map interpretation), one of the problems encountered is the finite size of scanners, or that scanners of the required size are not available. Often, one large scan is necessary for the interpretation process, instead of several smaller ones generated by the usual scanning in parts.

This chapter describes a method for automatically compiling mosaics from separately scanned line drawings. A mosaic is a collection of separately obtained images which are combined to form one larger image. The method is based on vectorization of the line drawings. The vectorization is used to automatically select the control points for a geometric transformation. It is not necessary to specify the overlap area between the line drawings.

The resulting system is evaluated using large scale maps. Experiments with different overlaps between the line drawings are performed. Results are good: the algorithm succeeds in finding accurate parameters for the transformation.

Keywords: Mosaic Construction, Vectorization, Evaluation.

3.1 Introduction

Compilation of mosaics from separately scanned line drawings has a parallel to photogrammetry. There, one of the activities is to combine several aerial photographs to form one larger (single) photograph. This photograph can then be used for the construction of topographic maps or surveys.

Until the beginning of the eighties this compilation was tedious work (Slama 1980, Alberda 1983). After photographs were taken from an airplane, they had to be transformed photographically to a single coordinate system. For this, an overlap is necessary. Similar tone and contrast were important so that adjacent prints would give the appearance of a single photograph. Prints were combined by selecting *control points* (points common in pairs of photographs), and then they were photographed (and corrected again) to form one large print.

With the introduction of computers, this task has been simplified. Photographs are scanned separately, and control points are selected by hand. Using a coordinate transformation based on these control points, the influence of warping, rotation and translation (caused by the position of the airplane), is eliminated.

The process of making mosaics to get one large photograph has been developed because it is

⁰This chapter is an enlarged version of (Janssen and Vossepel 1994).

impossible to make such a large photograph by taking only one exposure.

In automatic line drawing interpretation, a similar problem can be observed. To get the line drawing into the computer, it has to be scanned. Especially with large scale maps it is almost impossible to obtain the whole map in one scan (scanners have a finite size, or scanners of the required size are not available). Consequently, different scans of the same map have to be made, and they must be combined in the computer to get one continuous representation. With each scan, rotation and translation errors can be introduced.

The usual compilation procedure is that after selection of control points, a coordinate transform is applied to convert the coordinate system of one line drawing into the other (again, an overlap between the drawings is necessary). However, the main problem is the selection of these control points. Doing this manually is not difficult, but it is a tedious task. This chapter describes an automatic approach. Because our method is based on vectorization, the drawings must contain lines. For evaluation, large scale maps were chosen. The overlap area between the maps was varied.

In the following section a description of the mosaic construction algorithm is given. This is followed by a description of the evaluation approach and a discussion of the results. Finally, the robustness of our algorithm is discussed, and improvements are described. An outline for a method for compilation of mosaics from line drawings without overlap is proposed.

3.2 Mosaic construction algorithm

The algorithm to construct a mosaic from two line drawings is depicted in figure 3.1. It is illustrated with two adjacent parts (1000×1000 pixels each) of the same map in figure 3.2. To construct a mosaic from more than two line drawings, the process can be iterated.

Inputs and output of the system

The inputs to the system are two binary line drawings of the same scale and scanned with the same resolution, map I and map II. They need to have an overlap. The output of the system is map II transformed to the coordinate system of map I. Map I is not changed by the algorithm.

Coarse vectorization

For vectorization, the Douglas-Peucker algorithm (Douglas and Peucker 1973) is used. *Nodes* and *edges* are generated. The algorithm uses a threshold which is the maximum allowed (perpendicular) distance from the vectorization to the lines in the original image. This distance is measured perpendicular to the edges of the vectorization. For a more detailed explanation, see chapter 4. Usually, a small value (e.g. 1.5 pixel) is chosen because this ensures a precise approximation. We use a large value (10.0) however, because for identifying the control points only a coarse outline is necessary. The result of this procedure can be seen in figure 3.2.

Identification of control points

For transforming one coordinate system to another, control points in both systems have to be associated with one another. The problem is how to find these points automatically. It is not known in advance in which part of the image they will be found.

First, *valid edge pairs* are determined (a valid edge pair is a pair of edges common in the vectorization of both map I and map II which are associated with each other). The method is illus-

Figure 3.1: the mosaic construction algorithm applied to two example maps.

Figure 3.2: the mosaic construction algorithm applied on two adjacent parts of the same map. These maps were preprocessed automatically to remove small, isolated objects. The bitmap is plotted in grey, the vectorization in black. The hexagons connected with dashed arrows indicate corresponding control points. The pair connected with the leftmost dashed arrow is caused by a gap in the original bitmap.

Figure 3.3: example plot of length vs. angle for each edge. + and x are edges from map I and map II respectively.

Figure 3.4: identification of corresponding control points. The thick edges (1 and 1') form the edge pair to be tested.

trated with figure 3.3, where '+' are from map I, and 'x' from map II (this plot is not from the same maps as in figure 3.2). Edges from a valid edge pair should have approximately the same orientation and length (for accuracy longer than 50 pixels). To find these, for each edge from map I a search is done to the closest edge in map II. This is done by finding the closest in a circle of radius 5 pixels around the edge from map I. The angle and the translation vector between the two edges is computed.

Then, for all the different rotation angles a histogram is computed to find the approximate rotation (which is at the maximum). Also, each translation vector is plotted in a x/y -space. A cluster will appear near the approximate translation vector.

In addition, valid edge pairs which satisfy both the approximate rotation angle and the approximate translation vector, are also required to satisfy the following additional rules (see figure 3.4):

1. Each edge must have a different number of edges at its nodes. This is necessary for determining the orientation. Thus, for edge 1 the number of edges at A (2) and at B (3) must be

different. The same must be true for edge 1'.

2. The number of edges at corresponding end nodes must be equal. Thus, the number of edges at A and A' (both 2), and B and B' (both 3) must be equal. Using the first two rules, the orientation of the edge pair is determined.
3. The number of edges from the edges at A and A', and B and B' must be equal (i.e. the number of edges at C and C', D and D', and E and E' must be equal).
4. The length of the edges at A and A', and B and B' must be approximately equal (maximum length difference 5 pixels to allow for discretization effects, see page 43).

Finally, for each valid edge pair one point is chosen as control point. The pairs of control points for the example are indicated with hexagons connected with dashed arrows in figure 3.2.

Computation of the parameters of the geometric transformation

The general affine transformation (3.1) is reduced to (3.2) because only rotation and translation are possible (our assumption is that line drawings are scanned, and that scanners only introduce rotation and translation errors, but no warping).

$$\begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} t_1 \\ t_2 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & b_1 \\ a_2 & b_2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.1)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} t_1 \\ t_2 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \cos \varphi & -\sin \varphi \\ \sin \varphi & \cos \varphi \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.2)$$

Using the control points the parameters t_1 , t_2 (translation) and φ (rotation) are computed. (u, v) and (x, y) are control points from map II and map I, respectively.

Finally, the transformation of map II is computed accordingly.

3.3 Evaluation

3.3.1 Error measurements

The outline of the evaluation strategy is given in figure 3.5. It has been developed because a quantitative measurement is necessary for evaluation. Note that in real life usage, it is difficult to obtain results on the whole map II, because in that case a reference map (the 'ground truth') to which results can be compared is not available.

Initialization

A single scanned map is used for evaluating the algorithm. Small isolated objects in the map (characters, etc.) are automatically removed. This was done with the algorithm as described in chapter 2 on page 25.

Rotation and translation

The map was rotated 0.1° , and then translated. A small study has been conducted to determine a reasonable angle of rotation to be used for testing our algorithm. This simulates the rotation error made in real life usage. A straight line was drawn on a piece of paper. Then, the straight line was scanned and the angle of rotation was computed. Next, the piece of paper was removed, and replaced on the scanner. Again, the angle of rotation was computed. This procedure was repeated for a total of 10 times. To prevent an artificial method of aligning the paper, it did *not*

Figure 3.5: the evaluation strategy.

touch the side of the scanner. The average angle was 0.1° , the largest 0.2° , and $\sigma = 0.071$. The bias of the scanner was computed as follows.

With a drawing program, a pattern of six lines was drawn like a rosette on a piece of paper (they were crossing in the middle). Each line made an angle of 30° with its neighbor. This was printed on a 600 dpi postscript printer. Next, this pattern was scanned twice with a 400 dpi scanner: first with an angle of 0° to the top of the scanner (*scan1*), and then with an angle of 15° (*scan2*). Then the angle of each line with respect to the x-axis was measured in the digital image. The average angle of 'scan1' respectively 'scan2' was 30° ($\sigma = 0.217$), and 30° ($\sigma = 0.223$). It appeared that the maximum deviation (shrink) was at an angle of 30° to the top of the scanner (measured angle 30.34°), and the minimum (stretch) at an angle of -30° to the top of the scanner (measured angle 29.74°). It is difficult to give the significance of these numbers, for many factors must be accounted: is the 30° angle in the drawing program accurately translated to angles between lines in the image? Are these lines translated correctly into Postscript code? How much is the paper stretched or shrunk in the printer while printing?

Selection of map I, map II and the reference map

A part of the map without small objects was selected for map I. From the rotated and translated map a part was selected for map II. The reference map included both map I and the area of map II that was supposed to be 'found' by the algorithm. Because map I and the reference map have the same origin there are no errors between them.

Evaluation of the transformed map II

The deviation and distance (in pixels) is calculated between the projection of map II computed with our algorithm and the projection of map II from the reference map (a raster-to-raster comparison is done). This distance is calculated with a distance transform (Verwer 1991).

The total number of pixels in the lines of the projection of map II (N_T), the number of pixels of the computed projection which are wrong (N_W) (i.e. pixels which are not on the place they are supposed to), and the distance of these wrong pixels from their actual position (D_W) are determined. The performance is calculated with $\frac{N_W}{N_T} \times 100\%$.

Evaluation of the overlap area of map I and map II

The overlap area is evaluated because control points are found only in this area. The same method is used as for the evaluation of the whole transformed map II.

3.3.2 Description of the maps used

Table 3.1 gives general information about the maps used. Map 'leicad' is a cadastral map of Leiden, and map 'leighbkn' is a large scale base map (in Dutch abbreviated as G.B.K.N.) of Leiden, The Netherlands. The same scanner was used for both maps: the Vidar A0 scanner. The percentage overlap is given for the direction with the largest overlap. w_{glob} is the global line thickness.

It is argued in (Slama 1980, Alberda 1983) that an overlap of 60% is necessary to obtain an accurate correction for rotation and translation. To see if this condition also holds for our situation, experiments with different overlaps were done.

3.3.3 Results and discussion

The results are split into two tables: for the overlap area only and for the whole transformed map II. See tables 3.2 and 3.3 respectively. Counts are given in pixels. Columns 3 and up give the deviation from the reference map. The influence of the size of the overlap area is not impressive: most deviations are 1 pixel (the lines in the original image are thicker). A practical advantage of using a smaller overlap area is that less scans are necessary.

In figure 3.8 a fraction of the overlap area of experiment *leicad_20* is given. The discretization errors caused by the rotation of a discrete image (and other errors) are illustrated. To measure the influence of discretization errors, map II is rotated -0.1° (i.e. it is rotated back): the difference in pixels between the $+0.1^\circ$ and then -0.1° rotated map II, and the reference map for experiments *leicad_20*, *leicad_60*, *leighbkn_25*, and *leighbkn_60* is respectively 371, 413, 1276 and 639 pixels (this accounts for 0.1%, 0.1%, 0.2% and 0.1% of the errors in table 3.3).

In previous experiments, the general affine transformation in equation (3.1) was used. Then, the error was larger, especially for the experiments with small overlap. This was caused by a parallelogram-like transformation of map II: the control points gave a correct transformation in the overlap area, but they did not provide enough information to ensure a correct transformation outside the overlap area.

3.4 Robustness

Influence of the size of the overlap area

The length of the diagonal of the overlap area (or, more precisely, the largest distance between the control points) restricts the smallest rotation angle which can be detected. In our experiments, this condition was met, because for each experiment there were always at least two control points that were $1/\tan 0.1^\circ = 573$ pixels apart.

It is difficult to give a general statement on the required size of the overlap area, because the largest distance between the control points may be too small to detect the rotation, or the control points may even be absent.

map	figure	size parts (pixels)	overlap pixels	%	res. (dpi)	w_{glob} (pixels)
leicad.20	3.6	2500 × 3500	500 × 3100	20	400	5.6
leicad.60			1600 × 3100	64		
leighbkn.25	3.7	4000 × 4000	1000 × 3000	25	400	4.7
leighbkn.60			2400 × 3000	60		

Table 3.1: general information about the maps used.

Figure 3.6: section (2000 × 2000 pixels) of map leicad.

Figure 3.7: section (2000 × 2000 pixels) of map leighbkn.

map	N_T pixels	total wrong		N_W		$D_W \geq 2$	
		pixels	%	pixels	%	pixels	%
leicad_20	113 002	4130	3.7	4130	3.7	0	0
leicad_60	397 372	4103	1.0	4103	1.0	0	0
leighbkn_25	201 867	1656	0.8	1656	0.8	0	0
leighbkn_60	529 886	3187	0.6	3187	0.6	0	0

Table 3.2: evaluation of the overlap area of both maps.

map	N_T pixels	total wrong		N_w		$D_w \geq 2$	
		pixels	%	pixels	%	pixels	%
leicad_20	593 682	10821	1.8	10804	1.8	17	0.0
leicad_60	671 689	6752	1.0	6752	1.0	0	0
leighbkn_25	798 733	6246	0.8	6079	0.8	167	0.0
leighbkn_60	1 029 410	7930	0.8	7924	0.8	6	0.0

Table 3.3: evaluation of the whole map II.

Figure 3.8: example of the result of the mosaic construction algorithm after the coordinate system of map II has been transformed to the coordinate system of map I. (i) and (ii): 14 pixels wrong on distance 1 from the desired position. The errors at (i) are discretization errors caused by the transformation of map II, (ii) are pixels misprojected. Note that pixels at (iii) are not wrong, these are from map I. This is an example of the overlap area of experiment leicad_20.

Influence of rotation

The selection of control points is based on a vectorization, followed by application of several rules to reduce the number of edge pairs that eventually generate the control points for the geometric transformation (see section 3.2).

In the current implementation, the maximum rotation angle is required to be smaller than a fixed value ($|\Delta\phi| \leq 2^\circ$, a conclusion from the small study to determine a reasonable rotation angle: $28\sigma \approx 2$).

In one experiment map 'leicad' was rotated 1° ($14\sigma \approx 1$, less than the fixed angle) to see the influence on the system with larger rotation angles. A 20% overlap was used. Results are given in table 3.4. A comparison with experiment leicad_20 from tables 3.2 and 3.3 is given. It can be

evaluation	rotation map II	N_T pixels	N_W			
			$D_W = 1$		$D_W \geq 2$	
			pixels	%	pixels	%
overlap	0.1°	113 002	4130	3.7	0	0
overlap	1°	112 477	631	0.6	0	0
whole	0.1°	593 682	10804	1.8	17	0.0
whole	1°	591 839	6302	1.1	805	0.1

Table 3.4: evaluation of a larger rotation of map leicad. A 20% overlap was used.

observed that the error for larger angles is smaller (although not significantly smaller; errors are mostly one pixel). This may be explained by a more accurate estimation of the rotation angle.

Influence of digital vs. analog rotation

As discussed in section 3.3.1, a digital rotation of the image was used to be able to evaluate the algorithm (a reference map is necessary for the evaluation). To ensure that the evaluation results in this chapter are not dependent on a digital or analog rotation, an additional experiment was done.

Map 'haarlemmermeer' was scanned twice (both scans covered the same area) with a resolution of 400 dpi. A Hewlett-Packard Scanjet IIC scanner was used. Map 'haarlemmermeer' is a map of Hoofddorp, The Netherlands on scale 1:1000. The orientation difference angle was measured at 0.4° . The evaluation results of two experiments were compared (see figure 3.9):

Figure 3.9: to illustrate the difference between experiments digrot and anrot. The reference map is enclosed with a dashed rectangle, map I and map II with a dotted rectangle.

experiment	evaluation	N_T pixels	N_W			
			$D_W = 1$		$D_W \geq 2$	
			pixels	%	pixels	%
digrot	overlap	55 960	1661	3.0	0	0
anrot	overlap	55 900	3728	6.7	0	0
digrot	whole	186 095	11 439	6.1	0	0
anrot	whole	186 029	14 294	7.7	0	0

Table 3.5: comparison of a digital vs. analog rotation.

experiment *digrot*: the mosaic construction algorithm applied to map I, map II and the reference map from scan 1;

experiment *anrot*: the mosaic construction algorithm applied to map I from scan 1, map II from scan 2, and the reference map from scan 1.

The difference is that the rotation for map II is digital for the first experiment, while it is analog for the second. Results are given in table 3.5. Map I and map II have a size of 1800×2500 pixels and an overlap of 600×2000 pixels (33%).

It can be concluded that rotating map II digital or analog is not really different on the whole map (although the difference is larger for evaluation in the overlap area only). Thus, a digital rotated image can be used for evaluating the algorithm.

When these results are compared to the results of the experiments with maps 'leicad' and 'leighbk' (tables 3.2 and 3.3), the latter are better. This may be caused by the use of a different scanner, or by the relatively small size of the overlap area compared to the other experiments. Also, in the overlap area a few blocks with parcels can be found of which most lines have the same number of neighbors on both sides. Since for a valid edge pair edges with different number of neighbors on both sides are necessary, these lines cannot generate control points.

Influence of translation

Different translations of map II with respect to map I only influence the algorithm by different values for the parameters in formula 3.2 (the rules to obtain the control points are not sensitive to translation). This may cause round-off errors during computation of the transformation of map II with this formula.

Influence of scale change of the original line drawing or resolution change

Several parameters in the algorithm are dependent on scale or resolution. For instance, the vectorization uses a threshold (in pixels) to indicate the maximum allowed perpendicular distance from the vectorization to the lines in the original image. In identifying control points, the candidate edge pairs are selected using a minimum length criterion. Valid edge pairs are found in a circle of a fixed radius, and the length of the edges from the edges of a valid edge pair are allowed a fixed deviation. This is done to compensate for discretization effects.

Moderate resolution changes (e.g. from 400 dpi to 300 or 500 dpi) will probably not affect the algorithm. However, larger changes probably will, because the variation mentioned in the previous paragraph will change. If parameters are made dependent on the thickness of the lines in the image, it may be possible to eliminate these problems. Experiments to verify this are not

possible because the highest resolution of our scanner is 400 dpi, and scanning with a lower resolution would cause lines to become discontinuous (the pen used for drawing is too thin to be captured by a lower scanning resolution).

3.5 Extensions

An extension to the algorithm is to use a special marker which can be placed (before scanning) a few times in the overlap area. After corresponding markers have been automatically found, they can be used as control points. This method may be useful if a large line drawing is scanned in parts, because in that case markers can be placed in overlap areas which are otherwise empty (i.e. where no control points will be found, or where the largest distance between the control points is too small to detect the rotation). A disadvantage of this method, however, is that the markers must be removed from the scanned image afterwards. Another disadvantage is that if line drawings are scanned from separate papers, this method does not compensate for the absence or unfavorable position of control points (markers have to be placed at exactly the same location on the two separate maps, and this may be difficult to obtain).

3.5.1 Use of a-priori knowledge

Another extension to the algorithm is the use of a-priori knowledge. The use of specific features of the line drawings may improve the performance. The maps in figure 3.6 and 3.7 have such a property: the small circles give the base for the measurements when the map was drawn. So the location of these points is very accurate. If they can be found (e.g. with template matching), and used as control points, better performance may be observed.

A-priori knowledge can also be useful in the compilation of several contiguous drawings to one mosaic. It may happen that no objects are present in the overlap area. This problem can now be solved by matching through a series of other drawings which overlap both drawings.

Sometimes, it may happen that some parts in the mosaic are not covered by one of their components, i.e. some parts remain empty. Since this is not allowed, a search should be done to find a less perfect compilation, but with a fully covered mosaic.

3.5.2 Compilation of line drawings without overlap

If the line drawings do not overlap, the method presented in this chapter cannot be used. A possible other method is outlined below. It is assumed that the drawings are really contiguous, i.e. that no parts are missing at the boundary and that there is no overlap. This assumption is true for most large scale maps split over separate sheets of paper (e.g. for cadastral maps, if this were not true a parcel crossing the boundary would not have a unique size).

Given two line drawings to be compiled together, from each drawing four *boundary signatures* are composed from the lines at the boundary. See figure 3.10, where they are drawn at the top, bottom, left and right side of two example maps. Each signature of one drawing is matched with each signature of the other drawing, and a measure of correspondence is computed. The best match is chosen. Computationally, this procedure is not extraordinarily expensive because for each boundary signature there are only four signatures to compare.

With binary drawings, the signature consists of a string of ones (representing the lines in the drawing) and zeros (the background). As a measure of correspondence, the XOR combined with

Figure 3.10: two maps with their boundary signatures.

a summation of the remaining ones can be used (a form of binary correlation). The lower the score, the less difference between the two signatures.

To improve the likelihood of a correct compilation, for the few best scoring matches a 'sanity check' is done. For each compilation, the resulting image is vectorized, and analyzed around the boundary to determine which one is best. Usually there are only edges crossing the boundary. However, sometimes nodes are found exactly on the boundary. In those cases, one of the following is true (the list is sorted in decreasing order of innocence):

1. The edge from one drawing continues with an angle on the other drawing.
2. One or several edges of one drawing continue as one or several edges on the other drawing.
3. The edge ends on the boundary.
4. There is an edge on, or just parallel to the boundary, with nodes and edges extending in one or both drawings. See figure 3.11.

There is no influence on the match value for 1 and 2. For 3, the influence will be small, but for 4 it can be substantial. However, in that case a correction is possible because the substantial change in match value is known.

A problem encountered during this compilation is noise. If the noise level is high on the

Figure 3.11: an example of a few lines (in grey) near the boundary (dashed in black). The edges of the vectorization are in solid black. The vertical edge is near the boundary. Depending on the position of the boundary (either left, right or through the vertical grey line), the boundary signature, and thus the measure of correspondence, will change significantly.

boundary, the match value can be significantly influenced. However, a vectorization analysis as described above can probably solve this problem. Noise does not give meaningful vectors.

The vectorization around the boundary can also be used to check the direction of the vectors in that area. Usually, the direction will not change abruptly on the boundary. Under this assumption, it might even be possible to compile a mosaic from two drawings which miss a very small part at their boundary.

3.6 Conclusions and summary

This chapter presents a method for automatically compiling mosaics from separately scanned line drawings. A coarse vectorization is the basis for this method: the edges of both vectorizations are compared to each other and matching edge pairs are found. From these edge pairs control points for a geometric transformation are obtained.

An evaluation of the resulting system is given. Most errors are one pixel away from the desired position. Finally, the robustness of the algorithm is discussed and suggestions for improvement are given.

Adaptive vectorization of line drawing images

4

A novel method for vectorizing line drawing images is presented. The method is based on a sequence of a standard vectorization algorithm and maximum threshold morphology, which can be iterated until a fitting criterion is met.

First, 'anchor points' are found in a coarse vectorization. The position of each anchor point is corrected by means of morphological operations, after which it is fixed. Next, the vectorization is refined between the anchor points.

The method is adaptive because the original input image is used for correcting and improving the vectorization. Postprocessing modules can be added to anticipate specific properties of the line drawings to be vectorized. The vectorization method is evaluated using line drawings differing in scale and resolution.

Different methods described in this chapter may be called model-based vectorization, because expectations of reality (the original bitmap) are used to improve the vectorization. However, we prefer to call it adaptive vectorization because it is model-based at a low level and to avoid confusion with the more intuitive high level notion of model-based.

Keywords: Vectorization, Maximum threshold morphology.

4.1 Introduction

Vectorization is an often used approach for both reduction of data and interpretation of line drawing images (Ejiri et al. 1990, Suzuki and Yamada 1990, Janssen et al. 1993). It can also be used for constructing mosaics from separately scanned line drawings (Janssen and Vossepel 1994). The vector representation has some distinct advantages over encodings by chain-elements, run-lengths, or skeletons. It is a sensible solution because the 'lines' in the original scanned image (which are just adjacent pixels with no other mutual relation) are represented as geometric lines which can be used for shape representation or feature extraction. Another advantage is that the vectorization of an image is scale independent.

The reduction of pixels in a scanned image to lines with start and end coordinates is a non-trivial process due to the thickness of the lines, the angles of the lines, possible corruption of the input image ('missing' object pixels, etc.), and the size of the images. For an A0 sized image (1 m²) hundreds of megabytes are involved.

This chapter presents an adaptive vectorization algorithm consisting of three parts (mod-

⁰This chapter is a modified version of (Janssen and Vossepel 1995).

ules): an initial coarse vectorization, followed by determination of 'anchor points', and finally re-vectorization between these anchor points. The results will be improved by adding an adaptive clean up part (see section 4.6.3).

Anchor points are called that because of two aspects: first, they are fixed at a certain stage of the algorithm, and second, they capture the gross structure of the lines in the original image. They describe the end points, corners, junctions, and other special points in the image, i.e. the obviously important (dominant) points of a vectorization.

The algorithm has been developed in the context of a map interpretation system. Therefore, examples are illustrated with this kind of line drawing. Of course, the algorithm can also be applied to other types of line drawings such as CAD/CAM drawings, schematic diagrams, lines extracted from an image with an edge detector, etc. Indeed, one of the experiments is with an electrical diagram. There is no significant difference between the performance of the algorithm on maps or on diagrams. Between the different modules in the algorithm there are possibilities to anticipate specific properties of the line drawings.

This chapter is divided into five parts. First, a classification of vectorization methods is described. Then, a short overview of published approaches to the automatic vectorization problem is given. This is followed by a description of our algorithm. Possible extensions are described and evaluated. Results, robustness and improvements are discussed.

Paradigm

This chapter focuses on approximating lines in a scanned image by straight line segments, called *edges*. Edges are specified by their start and end points, called *nodes*, and stored in a special data structure which topologically represents the graph. We explicitly chose *not* to use curve segments for approximating curves, because approximating with curve segments is even more difficult than approximating with lines. Curves are represented with sequences of short straight lines.

4.2 Classification of vectorization methods

Converting line drawings from paper or film to a computerized representation can be performed in a number of ways. Lammerts van Bueren (1993) considers the following methods.

'Blind' vectorization

In this method, the drawing to be vectorized is pasted on a digitizing table. The operator uses a mouse for entering the start and end points of each line by clicking on them. He (she) is concentrated on the drawing and has no direct feedback on the result.

'Interactive' vectorization

The above procedure is used, but the operator is given feedback by displaying entered points and lines on a high resolution computer screen. The disadvantage is that the operator constantly has to move his head between the screen and the digitizing table. This may not be desirable from a human engineering point of view.

Scanning and 'heads-up' vectorization

After scanning, the map is displayed on a high resolution screen and vectorization is done manually using a mouse as above. The difference is that the result is displayed in an overlay on the map, giving a better opportunity for error detection. Some additional features, such as 'snapping' of points on a grid, may be available in such a system.

Scanning and 'interactive' vectorization

After scanning, software and an operator are necessary for the vectorization process. When the software is not able to make a 'good' decision as how to go on with the vectorization, the judgement of the operator is asked. The advantage is that some vectorization is performed automatically, the disadvantage is that — depending on whatever one considers 'good' — numerous parameters have to be chosen in advance to obtain a satisfactory vectorization (there is no uniform procedure for each type of map).

Scanning and automatic vectorization

After scanning, the map is vectorized automatically. This method is sometimes called 'batch vectorization'. This is what we aim for in this chapter: in ambiguous situations, the system has to make decisions independent of an operator. This independence calls for the optimization of a distinct measure which has to be selected with great care, because if the wrong measure has been optimized, the interactive correction of the result may require even more effort than the interactive vectorization of the original drawing.

4.3 Overview of automatic vectorization approaches

In this section, published approaches to automatic vectorization will be described. Most methods will be analyzed to indicate why they are not fully suitable for solving the problem of vectorizing line drawings (specifically maps).

It should be noted that all but one algorithm in the following paragraphs describe vectorization approaches for line drawings with lines of one pixel thickness. Such lines can be acquired interactively, e.g. by using a drawing tablet or digitizing table (but then no automatic vectorization is necessary). The usual procedure to acquire line drawings is to scan them. In this case, to prevent discontinuous lines, the thickness of the lines after scanning should be at least one pixel. However, in the scanned image lines with a larger thickness can appear since lines in the original image may be of varying thickness.

To apply the algorithms to this type of drawings, the lines in the scanned image have to be reduced to one pixel thick lines. This is usually done with an eight-connected skeletonization algorithm. However, this has several disadvantages: corners and T-junctions are often distorted because they may consist of very short spurious or unnecessary lines, and skeletonization is sensitive to rotation. These small lines can often be removed with specially designed rules, see for example figures 2.8–2.12 starting on page 22. The algorithm described in this chapter uses another approach to solve this problem.

Ideally, the most appropriate algorithm should be compared to a (commercial) system. However, this was not possible because we do not have such a system available in our laboratory. In (Filipski and Flandrena 1992) a commercial system for vectorizing line drawings is presented. An advantage of this system is that it has several subsystems for text and symbol recognition.

Unfortunately, their vectorization method and clean up editing subsystem are not described. Also, no evaluation of the resulting vectorization is present. Thus, no comparisons could be made.

Sparse-pixel methods

Dori, Liang, Dowell, and Chai (1993) describe a method to vectorize engineering drawings, which does not require one pixel thick lines. This is done by scanning every so-many row and column, thereby avoiding the necessity to address every pixel in the image. After a (line-like) blob of object pixels has been found, a 'zig-zag' algorithm is used which follows the object pixels of the blob row-wise until a non-object pixel is encountered, then it follows the pixels of the blob column-wise until a non-object pixel is encountered, then row-wise, etc. until the end of the blob has been reached. Special provisions have been made for scanning horizontal and vertical lines. To detect junctions in the drawing, the average length of each row and column run is inspected. If a deviation is detected, a junction or change in line-thickness is assumed, and appropriate action is taken.

An advantage of this method is that most arc segments are detected as arc segments (and not as sequences of straight line segments). Also, the authors extend the method to recognize arrows in engineering drawings. However, a disadvantage of this method is that for the vectorization algorithm approximately 12, and for the arrow recognition algorithm approximately 13 thresholds have to be adjusted in advance. It is not specified for most parameters how they should be set. Also, it is difficult to judge the performance since no quantitative measurement is present.

The remainder of this section describes vectorization approaches assuming lines in the input image of one pixel thickness.

Area methods

The Wall-Danielsson method (Wall and Danielsson 1984) is an example of this type of methods. An extension is described in (Wall 1986). The criterion used is the maximum allowed area deviation per unit line length from the vectorization to the approximated curve. The last point on the curve for which this criterion is not violated becomes a node in the vectorization, and this process is repeated until the end of the curve. See figure 4.1.

A principal difficulty is that nodes sometimes do not correspond with corners in the curve because a new edge is only started as soon as the criterion has been violated (Gonzalez and

Figure 4.1: The Wall-Danielsson algorithm in subsequent iterations. The thick lines are the edges from the vectorization, the thin lines are from the original image.

Woods 1992). This may happen just a few pixels after a long straight line turns a corner, and not at the corner itself (cf. point *d*).

Cone intersection methods

These methods, represented by (Williams 1978, Williams 1981) and (Sklansky and Gonzalez 1980), are based on defining a circle around each point of the curve in the drawing. The approximating edge has to intersect all these circles. The name of this method originates from the form of the union of all these circles seen from the start point, which is a cone. In (Williams 1981) the author improves his results obtained in (Williams 1978) by allowing edges to end outside the circles. Thus, a property of this method is that nodes of the approximating edges are not necessarily part of the original curve. This is undesirable from the viewpoint of vectorizing maps.

Minimax methods

These methods, represented by Kurozumi and Davis (1982), are based on the minimization of the maximum distance between the original curve and the approximating edges. Consequently, nodes of the approximating edges are not necessarily part of the original curve as in the previous method.

Tolerance strip methods

Given a number of points and a maximum and minimum strip width, these methods (Dettori 1982, Leung and Yang 1990) try to fit a strip around the points to be approximated. Several approaches can be taken: the number of original image points in a strip or the length of the strip can be maximized, or the width of the strip can be minimized. Combinations are also possible. The resulting edge is the central axis of the strip.

In (Dettori 1982, Leung and Yang 1990) it is not clear how branch points are handled. The algorithms construct a strip from a given start point to the next point until the criterion is violated. When the start point is a branch point, ambiguous situations may arise, especially when the maximum strip width is large.

Run-length methods

After computing the run-length encoding of an image, a line adjacency graph is constructed (see e.g. (Pavlidis 1984, Pavlidis 1986)). This graph is used to determine the edges of the vectorization. This method may not be suitable for vectorizing maps because a slightly slanted line with a jagged boundary may generate far more than one edge. Furthermore, the resulting vectorization may be orientation dependent.

Mark and sweep methods

Using the coordinates of the first point of a curve and the chain code of the contour as input, the method of Sirjani and Cross (1988) is based on marking all the points that may be an end point of a straight line. In the next stage the superfluous marked points are discarded, and the remaining points are the nodes of the vectorization. This method is not suitable for vectorizing maps because the outer contour is used: drawings which have lines fully enclosed by other lines will not be vectorized correctly.

Curvature minima and maxima methods

Points of minimum and maximum curvature in a curve can be used for constructing a vectorization. The methods of Teh and Chin (1989) and Ray and Ray (1992) do not require an input parameter: points are selected on the basis of their region of support. The idea is that these 'dominant points' provide important information for the recognition process of the human visual system. The position of the dominant points strongly depends on the method by which the region of support is determined. If it is determined incorrectly, dominant points may be discarded. In (Teh and Chin 1989), three different methods are used, but it is not clear which one is preferred.

Maximum perpendicular distance methods

The Douglas-Peucker method (Douglas and Peucker 1973) is an example of these methods. The maximum allowed perpendicular distance in pixels t_{dp} from the vectorization to the curve to approximate is used as a criterion. The algorithm starts with two dominant points of the curve as nodes of the vectorization. When the maximum perpendicular distance from this vectorization to the curve is larger than t_{dp} , a new node is added to the vectorization at the place of the maximum deviation. This process is repeated recursively. See figure 4.2.

Figure 4.2: the Douglas-Peucker algorithm in subsequent iterations. The thick lines are the edges from the vectorization; the thin lines are from the original image. The dashed arrow (perpendicular to the approximating edge) gives the maximum (perpendicular) distance. New nodes are inserted until the length of the dashed arrow is less than or equal to t_{dp} .

Other authors using this principle include Leu and Chen (1988), who concentrate on uniqueness of the approximating vectorization and its accuracy, and Ramer (1972).

Because of its strong tendency to put the nodes on the corners of the original image it appears that the Douglas-Peucker method is most suitable for vectorizing maps compared to the other algorithms. Therefore it is chosen as the basis for our adaptive vectorization algorithm.

4.4 Adaptive vectorization algorithm

The outline of the adaptive vectorization algorithm is given in figure 4.3. It consists of three modules: generation of a coarse vectorization, construction of the anchor points from this vectorization, and finer vectorization between the anchor points.

Inputs and outputs to the system

The inputs to the algorithm are the scanned input image, the global line thickness w_{glob} , and a threshold for the refined vectorization algorithm t_{dp} . Outputs are two data structures containing the anchor points and the final vectorization.

Figure 4.3: a scheme of the adaptive vectorization algorithm.

Determination of the global line thickness

The global line thickness (w_{glob}) is determined as follows. First, the small objects are removed from the input image. The number of object pixels (N_{OP}) in the resulting image is counted. Then, after skeletonization, the image is vectorized with the Douglas-Peucker algorithm with $t_{dp} = 1\frac{1}{2}$ pixels. Such a small threshold is used to obtain a precise vectorization. Next, the total Euclidean length of the vectorization T_{EL} is determined (that is: the added lengths of all vectors). The first estimation of the global line thickness is computed as $w_{glob-init} = \frac{N_{OP}}{T_{EL}}$. Next, a correction δ is determined: $\delta = \frac{1}{2} w_{glob-init}^2$. Also, the number of end points (N_E), T-junctions (N_T), and X-junctions (N_X) is determined. Each end point contributes δ to N_{OP} , and each T-junction and X-junction contributes $-\delta$ and -2δ respectively. Eventually, w_{glob} (a floating point value) is computed as

$$w_{glob} = \frac{N_{OP} - N_E\delta + N_T\delta + 2N_X\delta}{T_{EL}}$$

Generation of a skeleton image

An image with one pixel thick lines is produced with a skeletonization algorithm followed by removal of skeleton branches shorter than $2w_{glob}$. The skeletonization is a pseudo Euclidean skeleton (Verwer 1988). This is an improvement over the Hilditch skeleton (Hilditch 1969) because a better (almost Euclidean) metric is used. This ensures that the skeletonization is less sensitive to rotations.

Generation of a coarse vectorization

The skeleton image is vectorized with the Douglas-Peucker algorithm as implemented in the CARV package (Moore 1992), with (large) $t_{dp-coarse} = \lfloor 2w_{glob} \rfloor$ pixels. The result is a coarse vectorization in which the *dominant points* (end points, corners, junctions) are captured. Because of the large threshold, small variations are not captured.

Construction of anchor points

The dominant points are moved to their ‘correct’ location. The correct location is the middle of the intersection of the lines formed by the pixels in the bitmap image: the place where nodes ‘should be’. At this stage they are called *anchor points*, to indicate the idea that they give a coarse outline of the vectorization of the image, and that they do not move in the next module, which refines the vectorization.

Adjusting the dominant points is done using the coarse vectorization. A region of interest is defined around each node in the original image in that vectorization (the node is assumed to be approximately at the correct position). Then, a structuring element is constructed from the node and the edges originating from it. This is matched with maximum threshold morphology on the region of interest. A better match is expected and this process is repeated until no improvements are observed. The construction of the anchor points is explained in detail in section 4.4.1.

Refined vectorization between the anchor points

This is the last module in the vectorization algorithm. Its inputs are the vectorization with anchor points, the skeleton image, w_{glob} , and the threshold for the vectorization algorithm t_{dp} . The purpose of this module is to improve the accuracy by reducing the deviation from the lines in the skeleton image.

To this end, the skeleton image is again vectorized, but now with threshold t_{dp} . For each node, the distance to the closest anchor point is determined. If this distance is $\leq w_{glob}$ pixels, the node is merged with the closest anchor point. If t_{dp} is small ($1\frac{1}{2}$ pixels is a good value), fine details in the image will be captured. This is different from the module to generate the coarse vectorization, in which a large $t_{dp-coarse}$ was used to capture the gross outline. At this stage the details are important.

Our approach is motivated by the idea that the vectorization should represent the lines in the original image. The vectorization may have been distorted by the algorithm used. By comparing it with the original image, inconsistencies can be detected. It seems logical to do this only for the nodes of the coarse vectorization, because these capture the gross outline of the lines in the original image. They also provide important information for the recognition process of the human visual system (Attneave 1954). Another advantage is that it is computationally more efficient to do this only for these nodes. In the next phase, the details can be captured. In our approach, this is done by the refined vectorization between the anchor points.

4.4.1 Construction of anchor points

In the second module in the vectorization algorithm, the inputs are the coarse vectorization, the original input image, and the global line thickness w_{glob} . Nodes in the coarse vectorization are moved to their ‘correct’ location—the intersection of the lines in the original image—using maximum threshold morphology. After that they are called anchor points.

Maximum threshold morphology is a modified version of threshold morphology (van den Boomgaard 1992). A small image, called *structuring element*, is constructed with odd-sized width and height and integer-valued pixels. With threshold morphology, a threshold t_{tm} is set in advance. Each pixel in the binary input image is convolved with the structuring element. If

this results in a pixel value larger or equal than t_{tm} , the pixel in the binary output image becomes 1, otherwise it becomes 0. With *maximum* threshold morphology, each pixel in the binary input image is convolved with the structuring element, resulting in an output image with integer valued pixels. Then, the maximum value of that output image is determined, and the output image is thresholded with that value so that a binary image remains, in which the object pixels are the pixels of maximum value in the integer valued output image.

Determination of the size of the structuring element and the search region

The thickness of the lines in the original image should have a direct influence on the construction and the size of the structuring element, because otherwise the maximum threshold morphology may give wrong results. To improve accuracy, the local line thickness w_{loc} of the lines in the original image is determined for each node in the coarse vectorization. This is done using the original image and a pseudo Euclidean skeleton in a region of interest around the node: $w_{loc} = \frac{N_{OP}}{N_{SP}}$, with N_{OP} the number of object pixels, and N_{SP} the number of skeleton pixels in the region of interest. w_{loc} is a floating point value, just as w_{glob} . This approximation method is used instead of the more precise approximation method for w_{glob} , because it can be computed fast. Also, it is better to use a value which is approximately correct than to use a value (w_{glob}) which may be incorrect. For instance, in figure 4.8 on page 61, the local line thickness at the large blobs is much larger than w_{glob} . Eventually, w_{loc} is used to determine the size of the structuring element $size_{strelm}$:

$$size_{strelm} = \begin{cases} \lfloor 7w_{loc} \rfloor & \text{if } \lfloor 7w_{loc} \rfloor \text{ odd} \\ \lfloor 7w_{loc} \rfloor + 1 & \text{if } \lfloor 7w_{loc} \rfloor \text{ even} \end{cases}$$

The size of the search region is determined as $2size_{strelm} - 1$. This is the same size as the structuring element, enlarged to allow a border to prevent boundary effects.

Construction of the structuring element

The construction of the structuring element is illustrated with an example in figure 4.4. In (a), the candidate anchor point and its edges in the region of interest are drawn in a binary image. This image is dilated for a total of $\lfloor \frac{w_{loc}-1}{2} \rfloor$ iterations, shown in (b), using 8- and 4-connectivity alternately, to largely suppress the effects of grid anisotropy (Rosenfeld and Pfaltz 1968). This number of iterations was taken because then the width of the object in the dilated image is just a bit smaller than the local line thickness of the lines at that point in the original image. The object pixels of (b) are copied into the structuring element, and assigned the value 1, as shown in (e). Next, the outer contour of (b) is determined, shown in (c). These pixels are assigned the value 0 in the structuring element (white pixels—invisible—in (f)). Finally, a border of thickness $\lfloor w_{loc} \rfloor$ is constructed from the contour (again using dilation) shown in (d). This border is copied to the structuring element and its pixels are assigned value -1 . This is shown in grey in (g). Positive valued pixels indicate a positive, negative a negative, and zero valued a don't care match.

Three-valued structuring element

A three-valued structuring element was used because a binary-valued did not suffice. This is illustrated with figure 4.5. In (a) the binary input image (and the search region) for the maximum threshold morphology is given. Both a corner and a T-junction are in the search region, and they are very similar except for the third arm of the T-junction. To find the anchor point for the corner, a structuring element is constructed from the node in the coarse vectorization at

Figure 4.4: an example construction of the structuring element. The top row depicts a temporary binary image, and the bottom row the structuring element itself. Pixels in black have value 1, in white value 0, and in grey value -1. For explanation see the text.

Figure 4.5: a binary valued structuring element does not suffice for the maximum threshold morphology. See the text for details.

that corner and its edges.

This is done for example in (b), by dilating the edges from the coarse vectorization. The result of the maximum threshold morphology on (a) is given in a 3D plot in (c) (the values in the 3D plot represent the integer pixel values of the output image, just before the thresholding operation). There are two distinct, but equal-valued maxima, one for the corner and one for the T-junction. By using a three-valued structuring element, this can be prevented: in (d) a structuring element is shown constructed according to the method described above. The result of the maximum threshold morphology on (a) is shown in (e). Now, there is only one maximum (the left peak). In conclusion, a three-valued structuring element prevents similar but slightly different structures in the search region from generating more than one maximum.

Determination of the anchor points

The determination of the anchor points is illustrated with an example in figure 4.6. In (b) an enlargement of (a) is given. The following is a description of what happens in the dotted circle in (b). In (c) the result of the coarse vectorization is given: in grey the original image, in black the edges of the vectorization, and in white the node of the vectorization.

A structuring element is constructed from node i and its coarsely vectorized edges. The result is depicted in (d). Pixels in black have a positive value (1), pixels in grey a negative value (-1), and the other pixels a zero value. The new point resulting from the maximum threshold morphology with (d) on (b) is given in (e) (point ii). Its edges are also drawn to emphasize that the point is only moved. Change is observed so the procedure is repeated.

A new structuring element is constructed from the edges and the new node ii in (e), shown in (f) (note that (f) is slightly different from (d) because node i has moved to ii). After the maximum threshold morphology, the new point is iii in (g). Again, change is observed so the procedure is repeated.

The new structuring element generated from node iii and its edges is shown in (h). Again, (h) is slightly different from (f) and (d). After the maximum threshold morphology, the new node found is the same as the node in the previous iteration (iii and iv are the same), so no change is observed and the process stops. Finally, node iv is called the anchor point. In (j) the generated points can be compared with each other.

The process not only stops when the points from two subsequent matches are the same, but also when they are 4-connected to each other, or after a fixed number of iterations to prevent repetitive looping. The latter may happen if e.g. a node at location A is moved to location B , in the next match the same node is moved from location B to C , then from C to D , and finally from D back to A .

Figure 4.6: an example illustrating how anchor points are constructed. See the text for explanation.

4.5 Extended adaptive vectorization algorithm

Sometimes, additional postprocessing is desired. For instance, on the 'geo' map in figure 2.2 on page 17, there are very short parallel lines extending from long lines. These are hatches used on some maps to indicate the inside of the lines enclosing buildings. We call them *building hatches*. Because they do not contribute to the topology of the objects, one may prefer to remove them. The algorithm presented in the preceding section offers different possibilities for this kind of processing. Depending on the application, postprocessing modules can be added after each standard module, as follows.

Postprocessing of the coarse vectorization

This may be useful for example with X-crossings. Often these are not vectorized as an X-crossing but as two separate T-junctions connected by a very short edge. Although the construction of anchor points module will probably merge them to one node, computation time is saved if they are merged in advance, as merging nodes is computationally less expensive than maximum threshold morphology.

Postprocessing of the anchor points

Link nodes can be removed if the bend angle α between the two edges is less than a certain threshold, e.g. $|\alpha| \leq 15^\circ$. This can be done when that anchor node does not capture the gross outline of the image.

The problem of removing the building hatches as described above can be solved by removal of very short edges in a module to postprocess the refined vectorization, followed by replacing them with one longer edge. Anchor points should not be removed: this can be implemented using information in the anchor points structure.

4.6 Evaluation

4.6.1 Error measurement method used

For the evaluation of the vectorization, we use the evaluation strategy from (Janssen et al. 1993), described in chapter 2, which defines a *vectorization evaluation criterion* as follows:

The vectorization is considered satisfactory if, when it is plotted in the original image, the original image overlaps the plotted vectorization.

For evaluation the number of nodes and edges in the vectorization, the number of pixels wrong, and the number of lines wrong is reported.

4.6.2 Description of the line drawings used

Different line drawings (mostly maps) on different scales and resolutions were used for evaluation. This is summarized in table 4.1. The maps 'geo' and 'leiden' are cadastral maps, map 'gbkn' is a large scale base map of the Netherlands (abbreviated in Dutch as G.B.K.N.), and 'scheme' is an electrical diagram. The scanner used for 'gbkn' and 'scheme' was a Hewlett-Packard Scanjet IIc.

map	figure	drawing method	x size	y size	# pixels		res. (dpi)	scale	W_{glob} (pix)
					total	object			
geo	2.2 (p. 17)	template	1970	2400	4 728 000	364 198	508	unkn.	5.4
leiden	2.3 (p. 18)	hand	2800	2700	7 560 000	571 297	400	1:1000	4.3
gbkn	4.7	machine	3400	5600	19 040 000	780 983	400	1:500	4.5
scheme	4.8	machine	4011	5192	20 825 112	933 442	400	—	6.3

Table 4.1: general information about the line drawings used for evaluation.

Figure 4.7: section (2000×2000 pixels) of map gbkn.

Figure 4.8: section (2000×2000 pixels) of line drawing scheme.

4.6.3 Experiments

For evaluation, the four different line drawings were vectorized with the algorithms described in the previous sections. These are compared with results in (Janssen et al. 1993) (chapter 2). All images were preprocessed by automatic removal of small objects (e.g. characters, numbers). This was done because the vectorization of small objects does not give an accurate measurement of the performance of the vectorization algorithm.

The experiments are labeled with the name of the line drawing followed by an extension, printed in italics. The extensions are:

- **extension *dp***. After preprocessing, the image is vectorized using the standard Douglas-Peucker algorithm with $t_{dp} = 1\frac{1}{2}$ pixels.
- **extension *adap***. After preprocessing, the image is vectorized with the adaptive vectorization algorithm described in section 4.4. We used $t_{dp} = 1\frac{1}{2}$ pixels in the module to refine the vectorization.
- **extension *ext***. After preprocessing, the image is vectorized with the adaptive vectorization algorithm described in section 4.4 and the postprocessing modules described in section 4.5. All experiments with extension *ext* have the same postprocessing modules for the coarse vectorization and for the anchor points.
 1. **Postprocessing of the coarse vectorization.** Postprocessing of the coarse vectorization merges two T-junctions connected with an edge of length $\leq w_{glob}$ into one X-junction.
 2. **Postprocessing of the anchor points.** Postprocessing of the anchor points consists of two operations: two T-junctions connected with an edge $\leq w_{glob}$ are merged to one X-junction, and link nodes are removed if the bend angle α between the two edges is $|\alpha| \leq 15^\circ$.
 3. **Postprocessing of the refined vectorization.** Postprocessing of the refined vectorization differs for each of the four line drawings as follows. In all of these experiments, the refined vectorization was computed with $t_{dp} = 1\frac{1}{2}$ pixels.
 - * **experiment *geo-ext***. Because the 'geo' map has building hatches, it is expected that too many nodes and edges will be generated. To handle this, the postprocessing module removes edges connected to link nodes with length $\leq 2w_{glob}$, until a non-link or anchor node is encountered. The two extremes are then reconnected with one (longer) edge. Also, non-anchor link nodes are removed if the bend angle α between the two edges is $|\alpha| \leq 5^\circ$.
 - * **experiment *leiden-ext-one***. No postprocessing of the refined vectorization is done.
 - * **experiment *leiden-ext-two***. Non-anchor link nodes are removed if the bend angle α between the two edges is $|\alpha| \leq 5^\circ$.
 - * **experiment *gbkn-ext***. No postprocessing of the refined vectorization is done.
 - * **experiment *scheme-ext***. No postprocessing of the refined vectorization is done.
- **extension *clean***. After preprocessing, the image is vectorized with the adaptive vectorization algorithm described in section 4.4 and the postprocessing modules described in section 4.5.
 1. **Postprocessing of the coarse vectorization.** The postprocessing of the coarse vectorization consists of removing link nodes if the bend angle α between the two edges is $|\alpha| \leq 15^\circ$, and merging the endpoints of an edge of length $\leq \lfloor 2w_{glob} \rfloor$ to a new node in the middle of that edge (and effectively removing that edge). Using this last rule, two T-junctions are merged to one X-junction.
 2. **Postprocessing of the anchor points.** No postprocessing of the anchor points is done.

3. **Postprocessing of the refined vectorization.** The postprocessing of the refined vectorization consists of two parts. To compute the refined vectorization, we used $t_{dp} = 1\frac{1}{2}$ pixels. The first part removes edges connected to non-anchor link nodes and reconnects the end-points of these two edges with a longer edge. This is only done if the error according to the vectorization evaluation criterion is 0 for all edges involved. So the error cannot change using this clean up rule, only the number of non-anchor nodes can change.

The second part moves a node in the eight chain code directions under the condition that the error of the attached edges decreases. At the location of the coordinates of the new node must be an object pixel in the original bitmap. This is done first for non-anchor nodes, and then for anchor nodes.

- **extension icdar93.** These are the results of the vectorization described in (Janssen et al. 1993) (chapter 2). In that paper, the vectorization was refined using special rules, see figures 2.8–2.12 starting on page 22. Only the results for the ‘geo’ and the ‘leiden’ maps can be described because only those maps have been evaluated. In that paper, edges from the vectorization connected to end points are removed. Thus, only polygons remain in the vectorization. This was done to prevent border effects. This explains the difference in the number of pixels of the vectorization. In contrast, in this chapter the full vectorization is evaluated.

4.6.4 Results and discussion

The total number of pixels in the vectorization (N_T), the number of pixels wrong in the vectorization (N_W), the number of nodes and edges, and the number of lines wrong sorted by their length in pixels are shown in table 4.2. The error is smallest with the *clean* experiment, followed by the standard Douglas-Peucker algorithm. The generated number of nodes and edges is for all our experiments less than with the standard Douglas-Peucker algorithm.

The (a-priori) expectation of the result from the vectorization of the ‘geo’ map (a large number of nodes and edges caused by the building hatches) was correct: the performance of experiment *geo-ext* (which used rules to correct for building hatches) was better than experiment *geo-adap*. Also, the number of nodes and edges decreased

By comparing experiments *leiden-ext-one* and *leiden-ext-two* it can be observed that removing non-anchor link nodes, if the bend angle α between the two edges is $|\alpha| \leq 5^\circ$, is risky, but useful: the number of nodes and edges decreases while the error increases slightly for the number of lines wrong (the error for the number of pixels wrong almost doubles).

There is no difference between experiments *gbkn-adap* and *gbkn-ext*, and between experiments *scheme-adap* and *scheme-ext*. Thus, the proposed postprocessing modules in experiments *gbkn-ext* and *scheme-ext* have almost no effect. To improve the results, a different approach must be taken, for example as in experiments *clean*.

The best results are obtained with the *clean* experiments. These experiments have the advantage that the application of the clean up rules for the refined vectorization guarantee that the error only decreases. In figures 4.9–4.12 for each of the four line drawings a very small part (500 × 350 pixels) of the result of the vectorization with the Douglas-Peucker algorithm and with the *clean* experiment can be compared. The original bitmap is given in grey, and the vectorization in black. Nodes are indicated by small ‘+’ signs.

The execution time of the algorithm for the *dp* and *clean* experiments is given in table 4.3. These times were measured on a SUN Sparc 20, with 256 Mb memory. Experiment *scheme-*

map	# pixels			# nodes	# edges	# of lines of length				
	N_T	N_W	%			≥ 1	≥ 2	≥ 3	≥ 5	≥ 10
geo-dp	49 181	17	0.0	1845	1949	17	1	1	0	0
geo-icdar93	45 351	368	0.8	1412	1499	55	32	20	12	5
geo-adap	49 552	445	0.9	1613	1717	49	27	19	11	7
geo-ext	49 315	353	0.7	599	685	45	32	16	11	5
geo-clean	49 520	15	0.0	481	586	2	1	1	1	1
leiden-dp	100 131	89	0.1	2537	2814	30	11	7	5	0
leiden-icdar93	90 574	1119	1.2	1653	1945	315	156	85	49	17
leiden-adap	101 032	620	0.6	2178	2454	82	44	30	17	8
leiden-ext-one	101 042	431	0.4	2183	2459	85	45	28	16	5
leiden-ext-two	101 042	825	0.8	1860	2136	88	50	33	19	9
leiden-clean	100 959	51	0.1	1437	1714	14	4	2	1	0
gbkn-dp	138 379	12	0.0	2384	2469	6	1	1	0	0
gbkn-adap	139 263	154	0.1	2222	2307	55	34	19	5	0
gbkn-ext	139 268	120	0.1	2222	2307	54	32	18	4	0
gbkn-clean	139 226	0	0	1362	1447	0	0	0	0	0
scheme-dp	104 712	158	0.2	982	1059	2	2	2	2	2
scheme-adap	105 381	213	0.2	754	831	10	9	8	4	3
scheme-ext	105 392	213	0.2	736	831	10	9	8	4	3
scheme-clean	105 369	2	0.0	558	635	1	1	0	0	0

Table 4.2: the number of pixels wrong in the vectorization, the number of nodes and edges, and the number of lines wrong sorted on their length in pixels.

map	execution time	
	<i>dp</i>	<i>clean</i>
geo	0' 20"	4' 04"
leiden	1' 13"	8' 32"
gbkn	1' 15"	11' 37"
scheme	1' 16"	15' 22"

Table 4.3: execution time of the dp and clean experiments, in minutes and seconds.

Figure 4.9: fraction of the results of experiment geo-dp (top) and geo-clean (bottom).

Figure 4.10: fraction of the results of experiment *leiden-dp* (top) and *leiden-clean* (bottom).

Figure 4.11: fraction of the results of experiment gbkn-dp (top) and gbkn-clean (bottom).

Figure 4.12: fraction of the results of experiment scheme-dp (top) and scheme-clean (bottom).

clean takes more time to complete than experiment *gbkn-clean*, partly because the ‘scheme’ drawing is larger, but also because w_{glob} for the first experiment is larger than for the latter. This results in a larger size of the structuring element and of the search region, and this will result in more time necessary to compute the maximum threshold morphology.

In designing the algorithm, we emphasized accuracy rather than execution time. Therefore, the algorithm is not very fast. This is caused by the two applications of the Douglas-Peucker algorithm, the number of morphological operations (for each anchor point a few have to be computed), and the time necessary for the clean up rules. However, interactive vectorization is most often slower and (thus) more expensive. To obtain the same speed as the computer, humans should label about 2 to 3 nodes per second for map ‘geo’, ‘leiden’ and ‘gbkn’, and about 1 node per 1.7 second for line drawing ‘scheme’.

The problem with automatic vectorization is the determination of the ‘significance’ of nodes. Some nodes can be moved over a larger distance than others while keeping their ‘identity’ (i.e. the vectorization does not change significantly). Consequently, some nodes have more possible realizations than others. This can be associated with ‘sensitivity’: the lower the sensitivity of a node, the more it can be moved while keeping its ‘identity’. Examples of high-sensitive nodes are dominant points, such as sharp corners, junctions or end points, whereas the nodes in a curve, or link nodes with a small bend angle between the edges have a low sensitivity. An accurate location of low-sensitive nodes will be difficult to find because many ‘correct’ locations are possible. Other solutions may be exploited: if many low-sensitive nodes are found close together, they may be part of the same curve, and a curve segment may be constructed. No research has been done in this direction because the results of our algorithm (especially with the *clean* experiment) were already very satisfactory.

4.7 Robustness and improvements

Influence of global line thickness

Some parameters in the algorithm depend on the global line thickness w_{glob} . For example, nodes closer than w_{glob} pixels from an anchor point are merged with that point in the module which vectorizes between anchor points.

Two additional experiments were done to get an indication of the performance of the algorithm with different values of w_{glob} . Ideally, one should use the same line drawing, drawn with pens of varying thickness, but these drawings were not available. Scanning the same drawing with different resolutions would not work: in that case also the scale would be different. Therefore, we used the same drawing and used erosion and dilation to simulate drawings in which only the thickness of lines was different.

Map ‘geo’ was eroded (experiment *geo-adap-eros*) and dilated (experiment *geo-adap-dil*) one 8-connected iteration, and experiment *geo-adap* was repeated. Both vectorizations were evaluated respectively on the eroded and dilated maps, and both on the original map (experiments *geo-adap-eros-orim* and *geo-adap-dil-orim*). The results of these experiments are given in table 4.4.

Experiment *geo-adap-eros* shows a larger error than *geo-adap*, and this experiment in turn a larger error than *geo-adap-dil*. The first difference may be explained by the algorithm to compute the refined vectorization. There, nodes closer than w_{glob} pixels from an anchor node are merged with that node. In this experiment, that is a very short distance, and if the Douglas-

map	w_{glob}	# pixels			# nodes	# edges	# of lines of length				
		N_T	N_W	%			≥ 1	≥ 2	≥ 3	≥ 5	≥ 10
geo-dp	5.4	49 181	17	0.0	1845	1949	17	1	1	0	0
geo-adap	5.4	49 552	445	0.9	1613	1717	49	27	19	11	7
geo-adap-eros	2.9	49 982	2431	4.9	1768	1851	230	139	103	58	29
geo-adap-eros-orim	2.9	49 982	64	0.1	1768	1851	7	6	4	3	1
geo-adap-dil	7.8	49 393	38	0.1	1490	1587	16	6	4	3	0
geo-adap-dil-orim	7.8	49 393	901	1.8	1490	1587	182	125	75	27	13

Table 4.4: the results of the experiments to investigate the influence of the global line thickness.

Peucker algorithm fails to locate a node within the circle, the number of nodes and edges increases.

Experiment *geo-adap-eros-orim* indicates that the vectorization found is reasonable: the errors are lower than in experiment *geo-adap* but still higher than experiment *geo-dp*. The number of nodes and edges is highest for experiment *geo-dp*, and lowest for experiment *geo-adap*. Again, experiment *geo-adap-eros-orim* is in between. Sometimes, erosion can be a good idea before vectorization at the cost of more nodes and edges.

Experiment *geo-adap-dil* has a smaller error than *geo-adap-dil-orim*. This is so because our vectorization criterion is better satisfied in the former than in the latter experiment.

Influence of scale or resolution change

The influence of scale or resolution change influences the algorithm only because lines may have a different global line thickness (assuming that lines will not become discontinuous by a too low scanning resolution). This has already been discussed above.

Influence of 'magic numbers'

To avoid the use of too many 'magic numbers', most parameters have been made dependent on the global or local line thickness. The size of the structuring element is a certain factor (7) times the local line thickness. This and others have been chosen for efficiency: if the structuring element is larger, the cost for the computation of the morphological operations increases. Efficiency was the guideline for all magic numbers, except for $t_{dp} = 1\frac{1}{2}$ pixels: this value was chosen because it gives an accurate approximation of the lines in the original image. This can be seen from the experiments with extension *dp*: the results are good, at the cost of a larger number of nodes and edges.

Extensions to the algorithm

The vectorization method described in this chapter offers several possibilities for enhancement. The number of lines wrong can also be used for correcting the vectorization: if the wrong line is known, it can be corrected by moving one of its end points (this has been implemented in the experiments with extension *clean*), or by inserting a new node on the location of maximum deviation (this resembles the criterion used in the Douglas-Peucker algorithm).

Other kinds of (a-priori) knowledge can be used. If it is known that certain line drawings have lines which always make an angle of multiples of 90° , our algorithm can be adapted eas-

ily to accommodate this property. Also, if it is known that most lines are parallel, that can be incorporated into the algorithm.

4.8 Conclusions and summary

This chapter presents a novel approach for vectorizing line drawing images. The method is based on a sequence of a standard vectorization algorithm and maximum threshold morphology, which can be iterated until a fitting criterion is met. Postprocessing modules can be added to handle specific properties of the line drawings.

In this chapter, only the sequence (coarse) vectorization, morphological operation to correct nodes found, and final finer vectorization are used. Evaluation is done on different line drawings and results are discussed.

The best algorithm consisted of the following operations. The input image is skeletonized with a pseudo Euclidian skeleton. After the determination of the global line thickness, the skeleton is vectorized with the Douglas-Peucker algorithm with a large threshold. For efficiency, link nodes whose edges make a small bend angle, and very short edges are removed. Then, from this coarse vectorization, the anchor points are determined using maximum threshold morphology. This is followed by a refined vectorization between the anchor points, which is postprocessed using two different rules. The first rule removes edges connected to non-anchor link nodes and reconnects the endpoints of these two edges with a longer edge. This is only done if the error according to the vectorization evaluation criterion is 0 for all edges involved. The second rule moves a node in the eight chain code directions under the condition that the error of the attached edges decreases. The new node must be an object pixel in the original bitmap. This is done first for non-anchor nodes, and then for anchor nodes. The application of these both rules is safe: using the first rule, the error cannot change, and using the second rule, the error can only decrease.

Our algorithm has several advantages over the ones mentioned in section 4.3:

- The algorithm is based on a sequence of a standard vectorization algorithm and maximum threshold morphology, which—in principle—can be iterated any number of times. However, we chose to use the sequence vectorization, morphology, vectorization because it provides a reasonable balance between a satisfactory result and reasonable processing time.
- Due to the modular structure of the algorithm it can be adapted easily for special applications.
- The results resemble those of interactive vectorization closer than some algorithms in section 4.3, because first the gross outline of the vectorization is captured and then refinement among anchor points is performed.

The results of the algorithm in the experiments labeled *clean* are better than with the standard Douglas-Peucker algorithm. Also, our algorithm generates fewer nodes and edges than the Douglas-Peucker algorithm. However, the latter is faster.

The anchor points generated by our algorithm have a cartographic meaning because they give the gross outline of the line drawing. They may be useful in extracting features for an interpretation system.

Model-based interpretation of two types of maps

5

This chapter describes the concept of model-based interpretation. The technique is first implemented for the interpretation of cadastral maps. Then, to show that the method can be applied to other maps, an interpretation system for large scale base maps is described. The systems are evaluated according to the principles discussed in chapter 2.

To avoid confusion, throughout this chapter it is assumed that maps are interpreted.

Keywords: Model-based Interpretation, Evaluation.

5.1 Introduction

The disadvantage of completely bottom-up (or top-down) interpretation methods is that a-priori knowledge cannot be used extensively, and that recognized objects on higher levels cannot be used easily to solve detection problems on lower levels (or vice versa for top-down). Also, it can be very difficult to change an interpretation algorithm for one type of application to a similar, but slightly different, other type of application.

In contrast, our model-based approach combines the bottom-up and top-down strategies. A-priori knowledge about the images or the objects in the images is used at various places: on a low level e.g. to group pixels in meaningful objects (blobs from connection signs, numbers, etc.), and on a higher level to guide the interpretation (parcels can be constructed from connection signs and numbers).

If errors are detected (e.g. a parcel does not have a number) the top-down link allows us to influence low level processes, for example by starting a renewed search for objects which must be present at some place (in each polygon of the parcel a search is done to find a parcel number, e.g. by changing parameters locally or hypothesizing that the number is connected to a line in the image).

The a-priori knowledge must be specified explicitly in some way. We choose to represent knowledge in two different ways: as parameters input to the program, and as statements in C and C++ code. Another method could have been to define some kind of high level language allowing us to specify that e.g. connection signs consist of several blobs in a serpentine like shape that cross a line. This was not implemented because new problems different from the interpretation problem (such as how to represent the knowledge in the high level language, and how to translate that knowledge into C and/or C++ code) would then have been introduced.

Another disadvantage of designing a new high level language is that making such a language

requires a major effort, but it does not really benefit the *development* of a model-based interpretation strategy: a lot of high level languages already exist. For our purposes C or C++ is of sufficiently high level. Also, changes may be implemented faster because there is no intermediate language. Therefore, a high level language was not used.

Another point of model-based interpretation is that with a change to a similar application, models should be easy to change, and that it should be possible to re-use parts (this may also be true for bottom-up or top-down interpretation). We have implemented this for the interpretation of two types of maps by introducing a model of the interpretation flow (which is the same for both types of maps), and separate models for each type of map. Some objects in both maps are the same (e.g. lines, characters), and the same procedures are used to find these.

In this chapter, a structure for model-based interpretation is proposed. The implementation details are given for interpretation of two types of maps: cadastral maps and large scale base maps (GBKNS). Cadastral maps were introduced in chapter 2, GBKNS will be introduced below. Results and a discussion are presented.

5.1.1 Introduction to GBKNS

GBKNS are large scale base maps of the Netherlands. In Dutch, these are called 'Grootchalige basiskaarten van Nederland', and this is abbreviated as G.B.K.N. Examples of these maps are shown in figure 4.7 on page 60 and in figure 5.1, and later on in this chapter. Details as scale are given in section 5.4.2 on page 92. GBKNS are made by the Dutch cadastre to provide a single, uniform topographically correct map which can be used as a basis for making more detailed maps by other organizations. For example, utility companies will save costs when making their own maps, because the basic topography was already measured and drawn in a map. They only have to add the information they desire (electricity cables, pipelines, etc.).

Because GBKNS are a basis for making other maps, they do not contain a lot of information: more information on the map makes it more expensive for the customers, and leaves less space for other information. The information that GBKNS provide is the location of the 'hard' topography: blocks of buildings and pavement. Blocks of buildings can be recognized because their outline contains one or more building numbers. Pavement can be recognized by the name of the street or by the special pavement symbols (see figure 5.2). Other objects which are present are gridmarks. They give the intersection of the lines of the grid. An example is given in figure 5.15 on page 90.

The main difference between cadastral maps and GBKNS is that the former only give the boundary of the parcels and the buildings (if present), while the latter give the location of the buildings but not the official boundaries of each parcel. GBKNS provide additional information such as the kind of pavement, and unlabeled information such as the size of the sidewalks, lawns, parking spots, etc. (only if present). The unlabeled information can be labeled by the customer if desired, but if they do not care they do not have to pay for that kind of information. For instance, for utility companies it is useful to know where the pavement is and where the buildings can be found, but other information is not really relevant.

Figure 5.1: section (2000 × 2000 pixels) of map houten.

Figure 5.2: examples of pavement symbols. (a) indicate closed pavement (e.g. asphalt), (b) open pavement (e.g. bricks or stones).

5.2 Models used

Our model-based interpretation structure is based on the principle 'both object description and interpretation method based on a model', as discussed in chapter 1. There, the following models are defined: the model of the interpretation flow, the model of the map, and the model of the object. Since the model of the object is closely intertwined with the model of the map, the model of the object will be discussed from the viewpoint of the model of the map, i.e. there is no real distinction made during the presentation of the algorithm between the model of the map and the model of the object.

One of the interesting engineering problems is to find out what can go wrong (we considered this part of the learning procedure), and trying to make modules which correct for this. Ideally, the interpretation process should not crash if the designer did not anticipate something, e.g. parcel numbers connected to the lines of the parcel while this is not allowed according to the drawing rules. The implementation described below is reasonably robust because it can correct for drawing mistakes.

The following sections describe the model of the interpretation flow and the different models of the map. We chose to use two different types of maps: cadastral maps (see e.g. figures 2.2 on page 17 and 2.3 on page 18) and GBKNS (see e.g. figure 4.7 on page 60 and figure 5.1).

For both the cadastral maps and the GBKNS, a variation in the objects on the map and the way they are drawn can be seen. For instance, on the cadastral maps, there is a difference in the way parcel numbers are drawn, and for the GBKNS that in one GBKN all lines have the same thickness, while in another blocks of buildings are outlined by lines thicker than the other lines in the image. This difference is caused not only by the drawing method (hand or machine), but also by different rules used.

We have chosen to have one model of the map for each kind of map. An alternative could have been (for example considering GBKNS) to make a different model for each GBKN, or to make a 'super-model' containing the common characteristics of the GBKNS to interpret, and for each GBKN a separate 'sub-model' which describes the specific properties of that GBKN. We did not follow this latter approach because in that case it is necessary to make a separate model for each (new) GBKN. It may also be possible that for interpretation of a new GBKN the 'super-model' has to be changed because it does not allow certain characteristics of that GBKN. This might give rise to a cumbersome process of rewriting the 'super-model' and all 'sub-models', until they are (again) consistent with each other. We preferred a more general solution ("it should work with a 'minimal' model"). In our system, the only changes necessary for going from one GBKN to another are the values of certain parameters (e.g. of the size of the characters on the map, for details see later on).

5.2.1 Model of the interpretation flow

In the model of the interpretation flow, after an initial subdivision into different kind of objects, an initial interpretation is obtained. The results of this interpretation are then checked against the model of the map to see if they are consistent (the model of the map also specifies how inconsistencies can be resolved). This will result in new, modified, or deleted objects, which in turn will change the interpretation. If no more inconsistencies can be found the interpretation flow stops.

The model of the interpretation flow in this chapter is illustrated in figure 5.3. The scanned

Figure 5.3: the model of the interpretation flow in this chapter.

map is represented in *vector objects* (objects which can be represented with vectors) and in *pixel objects* (a pixel object is a group of connected pixels, a connected component). An advantage of using vectors vs. pixel objects is that vector based operations can be used. Because the maps used are based on polygons these are formed from the vector objects.

5.2.2 Model of the cadastral map

For the model of the cadastral map, we chose to represent four different kinds of pixel objects:

- COSI objects: representing connection signs;
- CHAR objects: representing characters and numbers;
- LINE objects: representing lines; and
- UNKNOWN objects: representing unknown objects (not yet classified or classification unknown).

The drawing rules for cadastral maps are guidelines for the model of the map: each parcel has exactly one number, and polygons of one parcel are connected with connection signs. The parcel numbers must be written in the middle of one of its polygons, and numerals may not touch the side of the polygon or each other (Minister van VROM 1989). The check against the model is verifying this: if a polygon is not labeled as being part of a parcel, first an attempt is made to certify that a connection sign has not been missed. A connection sign can be missed if it is attached to a line, or if the blobs are too large and labeled as e.g. UNKNOWN (for an example see figure 5.4).

If no new connection sign can be found, an attempt is made to certify that a parcel number has not been missed. A parcel number can be missed if it is attached to a line, or if two or more characters are not separated but instead form one object. For an example see figure 5.5.

Figure 5.4: an example of using model knowledge to find missing connection signs. In (a) the original image is given. The only part of a connection sign that can be found is shown in black in (b) (the other part cannot be found because it is connected to the lines of the image). Since it consists of only one part, it is not used, and a parcel consisting of one polygon is constructed, shown in light shading in (c) (this satisfies the definition of 'parcel having one number and no connection signs'). In the 'check against model'-part, the not-labeled polygon is detected. Since it is not a parcel, something must have gone wrong (a connection sign may have been missed). From this polygon a search is done for a part of a connection sign (the model specifies that the other part may be connected to the lines of the image). The search region generated (a black rectangle) is shown in (d). Indeed, a part of a connection sign is found, and a valid connection sign can be constructed. The new parcel is shown in (e).

Figure 5.5: an example of using model knowledge to find missing parcel numbers. In (a) the original image is given. The connection signs found are shown in black in (b). However, a parcel cannot be constructed because a parcel number is missing (it is connected to the lines of the image, therefore it could not be found, and the model requires that a parcel has a parcel number). To find a parcel number, in each polygon of the candidate parcel a search is done for a parcel number. The search is in a region around each branch point of the vectorization (the model specifies that a parcel number may be connected to the lines of the image, and this will influence the vectorization by inserting an extra node). In (c), a search region in the leftmost polygon is shown. In the black rectangle, it shows a connection between the lines of the image and the parcel number. With this parcel number and the connection signs a parcel can be constructed as shown in light shading in (d).

Figure 5.6: the model of the interpretation flow for cadastral maps.

A detailed description of how pixel objects can be found, and how the check against the model is done, is presented in section 5.3. The model of the map and the model of the interpretation flow for interpretation of cadastral maps are given together in figure 5.6.

5.2.3 Model of the GBKN

For the model of the GBKN, we chose to represent five different kinds of pixel objects:

- STREET objects: representing the symbols indicating the kind of pavement on the street and the street names;
- CHAR objects: representing numbers in the blocks of buildings (and initially street names);
- LINE objects: representing lines;
- GRIDMARKS: representing gridmarks; and
- UNKNOWN objects: representing unknown objects (not yet classified or classification unknown).

We chose to interpret three different parts from the GBKN. The first are the blocks of buildings. These can be recognized because they have one or more numerals written in them. The second are the streets. These can be recognized by the special pavement symbols, or because a

street name is written in it. The last category are polygons of which no interpretation can be determined because there is no unambiguous method of determining what they represent. The check against the model is verifying if there are no STREET objects in the blocks of buildings, and no CHAR objects in the streets, or that no unassigned STREET or CHAR objects remain. Errors could have been made if e.g. (part of) a street name erroneously was labeled as UNKNOWN or CHAR. An example how this is corrected is shown in figure 5.7.

A detailed description how pixel objects can be found, and how the check against the model is done, is presented in the next section. The model of the map and the model of the interpretation flow for interpretation of GBKNs are given together in figure 5.8.

Figure 5.7: an example of using model knowledge to find missing STREET objects. In (a) the original image is given. In (b) objects found compatible with type STREET are given in black, and of type CHAR in light shading. The 'O' has been incorrectly labeled as CHAR. This is detected because a CHAR object is found in the street, and that is not allowed according to the model. Because the 'O' is very close to 'oienvaarsbek' (which is of type STREET), they are grouped together as shown in (c). Note that the dot of the 'i' is missing. This dot is labeled as UNKNOWN, and therefore does not cause an error in the interpretation process.

5.3 Map interpretation algorithm

In this section, first the common elements necessary to interpret cadastral maps and GBKNs are described. This is followed by elements specific for each kind of map. The actual values of the different parameters for each map are given in table 5.4 (page 99), introduced in section 5.4.2.

Figure 5.8: the model of the interpretation flow for GBKNs.

5.3.1 Common map interpretation algorithm part

Preprocessing of the scanned image

Objects of size $\leq obj_{minsize}$ pixels are removed from the image. This is done by counting the number of pixels in each connected component.

Non-modifiable bitmap and modifiable bitmap

The check against the model may cause changes in the bitmap, as can be seen in figure 5.3. This could have been implemented by changing the bitmap, and propagating the changes into the vectorization and the pixel objects by recomputing the vectorization and all the pixel objects. However, since the division in pixel objects is computationally very expensive, this is implemented differently.

A distinction is made between a 'non-modifiable' bitmap, and a 'modifiable' bitmap. The first is the preprocessed input image, and the latter a copy of this preprocessed image. During the interpretation process, changes are incorporated in the modifiable bitmap. The vectorization is recomputed after the changes from this modifiable bitmap.

However, after the division in pixel objects is done from the non-modifiable bitmap at the start of the interpretation process, changes necessary during the interpretation process are applied directly to the pixel objects involved (i.e. new pixel objects are generated directly and old pixel objects are changed, instead of recomputing all the pixel objects). This is computationally more efficient.

In the current implementation the bitmap can only be changed by the model of the cadastral map, and not by the model of the GBKN. This is because the check against the model module for the GBKN had no need to modify the bitmap.

Preprocessing of the vectorization and vectorization

This is done according to the (best) algorithm described in chapter 4. Before vectorization, the image is enclosed in a rectangle, so that polygons can be constructed easily. Also, small objects are removed automatically because these are not necessary for the construction of polygons from lines (section 2.2, page 25).

Construction of polygons

For each edge in the vectorization is determined to which polygons it belongs. This is explained with figure 5.9, showing parts of a few polygons. Lines are numbered, the side of the lines are labeled with *A* and *B*, angles are given with Greek letters, and the other symbols are labels assigned to vectors during the construction process.

Constructing a polygon is done by marking an unlabeled side of a vector, say vector 1, side *B* with label +, going to the next vector with smallest angle to this vector (this is vector 2 with angle α), marking the same side (*B*) of the new vector with the same label + as the previous vector, going to the next vector with smallest angle (vector 3 with angle γ), marking the same side (*A*) with +, and repeating this process until the start vector has been reached. Next, another unlabeled side of a vector is labeled (e.g. vector 1, side *A*, angle ε , mark Δ), until all sides of all vectors have been labeled. The result of the labeling process for the example is presented in the figure.

Eventually, polygons are constructed from the labeled vectors. Polygons touching or intersecting the boundary are marked. This is done because in some cases these polygons cannot be used (e.g. in the construction of parcels from polygons: polygons intersecting the boundary may be missing information necessary for the interpretation).

Only for cadastral maps, polygons with perimeter $< poly_{minperim}$ pixels are marked because they disturb the construction of parcels from polygons (very small polygons may be caused by gaps in the bitmap). For GBKNs this is not necessary because unlabeled polygons correspond to a (valid) label 'cannot label unambiguously'.

Division in pixel objects: UNKNOWN objects

Before labeling the pixel objects, all are labeled UNKNOWN. The subsequent labeling operations try to relabel. If that does not succeed, the pixel object still has the label UNKNOWN object.

Division in pixel objects: CHAR objects

This module finds characters and numbers, and subsequently groups them if they are close enough. Objects are labeled as CHAR objects if the width and the height of the minimum bounding rectangle satisfy

$$\begin{aligned} \max(0, char_{globwidth} - char_{init} \times char_{globwidth}) < width < char_{globwidth} + char_{init} \times char_{globwidth} \\ \max(0, char_{globheight} - char_{init} \times char_{globheight}) < height < char_{globheight} + char_{init} \times char_{globheight} \end{aligned}$$

with $char_{init}$ a factor determining whether an object is a CHAR object or not. See figure 5.10 for an illustration.

Figure 5.9: example illustrating the construction of polygons.

Figure 5.10: thresholds used in finding characters.

Next, for each object labeled CHAR, the two closest of the same type are found (possibly one on the left and one on the right), of which the first may be at most $char_{maxblob2blob}$ pixels away (say, on distance d , with $d \leq char_{maxblob2blob}$), and the second may be at most $d + char_{maxblob2blobvar}$ pixels away (the second closest may not be much farther away than the closest). These are grouped to a new (larger) CHAR object.

Division in pixel objects: LINE objects

This module labels lines. If the first method fails, a second method is tried. Objects are labeled as LINE objects if the distance between the two extreme nodes of the (Douglas-Peucker) vectorization from the object is $> 2d$ pixels, with $d = 2 \times char_{globwidth} + 2 \times char_{globheight}$. The thresholds $char_{globwidth}$ and $char_{globheight}$ describe respectively the global width and height of a character, and thus d the average perimeter length of the bounding rectangle of a character. The two extreme points must be at least on distance $2d$ to be a LINE object.

If the criterion is not satisfied, the vectorization of the object is transformed to a polygon by removing all edges having an end point. From the remaining polygons (if any), the length of the perimeter is measured, and the longest is taken. If this length is $> 2d$, the object is labeled as a LINE. Otherwise, or if it is not possible to determine the perimeter because no polygons remained, the object is not labeled (it remains labeled as UNKNOWN object).

The Douglas-Peucker algorithm is used in the vectorization step instead of the one developed in chapter 4, because it is accurate enough for this purpose and faster (this is shown in chapter 4).

5.3.2 Interpretation part for cadastral maps

Division in pixel objects: COSI objects

This module constructs connection signs from a series of blobs. Objects are labeled COSI objects if they satisfy a number of properties (see figure 5.11).

First, small blobs (the separate blobs of each connection sign) are labeled COSI if the width and the height of the minimum bounding rectangle of each separate blob satisfy

$$\max(0, w_{glob} - cosi_{init} \times w_{glob}) < \text{width}, \text{height} < w_{glob} + cosi_{init} \times w_{glob}$$

w_{glob} is the global line thickness in pixels, and $cosi_{init}$ a variance in determining the size of a blob of a connection sign.

Next, small blobs are grouped (to locate all the blobs of a connection sign at the same side of a line) by finding from each COSI blob the two closest of the same type (possibly on both sides of the blob), of which the first may be at most $cosi_{maxblob2blob}$ pixels away (say on distance d), and the second may be at most $d + cosi_{maxblob2blobvar}$ pixels away (the second closest may not be much farther away than the closest). These are grouped to one larger COSI object. The result is called: *part of a connection sign*.

Finally, two parts of a connection sign are grouped to one *full connection sign* (or connection sign if no confusion arises) if the distance from one part to the nearest line $< cosi_{maxpart2line}$ pixels, and the distance from one part to the closest other part through a line is $< cosi_{maxpart2part}$.

Figure 5.11: thresholds used in finding connection signs.

Interpretation

In this module parcels are formed from polygons, full connection signs, and/or numbers. This is done by determining which full connection signs intersect two or more polygons, and constructing a candidate parcel from them. Next, for each set of numerals the enclosing polygon is determined. If such a polygon is part of a candidate parcel formed in the previous step, the set of numerals is incorporated in that candidate parcel. Otherwise, a new candidate parcel is constructed from the polygon and the set of numerals. Finally, for the remaining polygons (neither intersecting with a connection sign, nor enclosing a set of numerals), also a candidate parcel is constructed. This is done to aid the interpretation process as a 'remaining' category.

To make a distinction between the different kinds of candidate parcels, these are labeled:

- FULL parcel:** (parcel if no confusion arises) candidate parcel having one parcel number and the appropriate number of connection signs, i.e. a parcel conforming to the definition of 'parcel';
- BOUNDARY parcel:** candidate parcel of which one or more of its polygons touch or intersect the boundary of the image. For this parcel objects necessary for the interpretation may be on the other side of the boundary, so a complete interpretation is not always possible;
- TINY parcel:** candidate parcel formed from one polygon labeled 'too small' by the polygon construction algorithm;
- UNKNOWN parcel:** candidate parcel not satisfying one of the labels above.

Check against the model of the cadastral map

The check against the model tests whether every candidate parcel conforms to the definition of FULL parcel or not. In the latter case, an analysis is made what can be done to make it conform to the definition. To obtain this, the labels assigned to the candidate parcels are used.

Candidate parcels having the label FULL parcel are conforming to the definition, and are not considered any more. BOUNDARY parcels may conflict with the definition, but are not considered because information necessary for the interpretation may be on the other side of the boundary. However, whether this is true or not cannot be known in advance. Also, TINY parcels are not checked because they consist of a polygon which was too small.

The remaining candidate parcels (with label UNKNOWN parcel) are checked to see if the interpretation can be improved. The following cases are distinguished, and are tried in the order given. First case 1 is applied to all UNKNOWN parcels if applicable, then the changes generated are incorporated in the various data structures used, for the remaining UNKNOWN parcels case 2 is applied where applicable, and finally case 3. This is summarized in table 5.1.

pixel object	parcel	case 1: missing cosi	case 2: missing parnr	case 3: cosi is CHAR	no solution can be found
CHAR	1	0	0	[2, ∞ >	[0, ∞ >
COSI	[0, ∞ >	[0, ∞ >	[0, ∞ >	[0, ∞ >	[0, ∞ >
label	FULL parcel	UNKNOWN parcel	UNKNOWN parcel	UNKNOWN parcel	BOUNDARY parcel, TINY parcel, UNKNOWN parcel

Table 5.1: 'truth table' for checking the candidate parcels. The numbers in the table give the number of objects of that type necessary for choosing that case. Hypotheses are generated from left to right. The abbreviations used are 'cosi' for connection sign, and 'parnr' for parcel number.

Case 1. Observation: 0 parcel numbers, ≥ 0 connection signs.

Hypothesis: the algorithm missed a connection sign. Try to find one.

For each polygon of the candidate parcel, each edge is considered to find an unused part of a connection sign. If such a part is found within $\leq \text{cosi}_{\text{maxpart2midline}}$ pixels distance from the edge of the polygon, on the other side of the edge a search region is created (size dependent on w_{glob}), in which (hopefully) the other part can be found, but connected to the edge itself (this is the situation shown in figure 5.4).

If in this search region a cut line can be found which satisfies

$$\frac{1}{2} w_{\text{glob}} \leq \text{length cut} \leq 1 \frac{1}{2} w_{\text{glob}},$$

that cut is made, and the resulting object is a new pixel object (see figure 5.12). Next, this pixel object is labeled using the methods described above, and if it is a COSI object and the new and the old part of the connection sign satisfy the definition of connection sign, a new connection sign is constructed and used for the construction of a new parcel.

The interpretation flow starts over again.

Case 2. Observation: 0 parcel numbers, ≥ 0 connection signs.

Hypothesis: the algorithm missed a parcel number. Try to find one.

For each unused pixel object the bounding rectangle is determined, and if that object is inside of one of the polygons of this candidate parcel, a check is done to see if the height of that object satisfies the global height of a character $\text{char}_{\text{globheight}}$.

Figure 5.12: thresholds used for finding connection signs connected to lines. This is an enlargement of figure 5.4(d)

If that is true, it is assumed that it is a string of characters connected to each other not detected before because its width was too large, and the object is labeled as CHAR object. The interpretation flow starts over again.

If there are no separate objects inside one of the polygons of the candidate parcel, or the height of those objects does not satisfy the global height of a character, then for each polygon in the candidate parcel each node in the vectorization having more than two branches is checked. A search region is constructed around that node pointing to the inside of the polygon, because it may be possible that a parcel number is connected to the lines of the image (this is the situation shown in figure 5.5).

If in this search region a cut line can be found which satisfies

$$\frac{1}{2} w_{glob} \leq \text{length cut} \leq 1 \frac{1}{2} w_{glob},$$

and which also does not intersect the two other edges part of the polygon at that node, that cut is made, and the resulting object is a new pixel object (the same algorithm is used as for cutting connection signs, see figure 5.13). The new pixel object is labeled using the methods described above, and if it is a CHAR object, a new parcel number is constructed and used for the construction of a new parcel.

The interpretation flow starts over again.

Case 3. Observation: ≥ 2 parcel numbers, ≥ 0 connection signs.

Hypothesis: the algorithm labeled part of a connection sign as CHAR object. Try to find out if that is true, and if so, relabel.

Sometimes, parts of connection signs are mislabeled as CHAR objects (they look like a '1'). To correct for this, all the CHAR objects in the candidate parcel are checked with

Figure 5.13: thresholds used for finding parcel numbers connected to lines. This is an enlargement of figure 5.5(c)

the procedure to find CHAR objects as described above, but with the difference that the global width of the character $char_{globwidth}$ is set to w_{glob} (the expected width of a '1'). If such objects can be found, they are relabeled to UNKNOWN object, and the interpretation flow starts over again.

5.3.3 Interpretation part for GBKNS

Division in pixel objects: STREET objects

This module labels objects representing streets. Objects are labeled STREET objects if the height and width of the minimum bounding rectangle from the pixel object satisfy

$$\begin{aligned} pav_{globheight} &\leq \text{height} \leq 3 \times pav_{globheight} + 2w_{glob} \\ 2 \times pav_{globwidth} &\leq \text{width} \leq 3 \times pav_{globwidth} \end{aligned}$$

with $pav_{globwidth}$ the global width, and $pav_{globheight}$ the global height of one 'brick' in the open pavement, or one 'diamond' in the closed pavement symbols. w_{glob} is the global line thickness. See figure 5.14.

Division in pixel objects: GRIDMARK objects

Gridmarks which are not connected to other objects are labeled using the criterion that the length of the arms of the cross satisfy

$$cross_{globsize} - cross_{globsizevar} < \text{length arm} < cross_{globsize} + cross_{globsizevar}$$

See figure 5.15. GRIDMARK objects are marked but not used for the interpretation.

Division in pixel objects: CHAR objects

Objects are labeled CHAR objects as described above. However, GBKNS have the additional rule that blobs grouped from five or more characters are supposed to be street names. This is a sim-

Figure 5.14: thresholds used in finding pavement symbols.

Figure 5.15: threshold used in finding gridmarks.

plication rule added by us to prevent the use of a character recognition system for making a distinction between street names and numbers of blocks of buildings. Street names can now be distinguished from numbers of blocks of buildings because street names are given a STREET object label instead of a CHAR object label.

Interpretation

In this module blocks of buildings and streets are formed from polygons, street names, pavement symbols, and/or numbers. This is done by determining which objects are enclosed by which polygons. For each polygon, one list with street names and pavement symbols, and one list with numbers is constructed. Both lists may be empty.

To make a distinction between the different kinds of polygons, they are labeled:

- BLOCK polygon: polygon having an empty list of STREET objects and a non empty list of CHAR objects. The polygon corresponds to a block of buildings;
- STREET polygon: polygon having a non empty list of STREET objects and an empty list of CHAR objects (street names have a STREET label). The

- NO-BLOCK-STREET polygon: polygon having an empty list of STREET objects and an empty list of CHAR objects. This polygon represents neither a block of buildings, nor a street, but cannot be labeled otherwise because there is no unambiguous method of determining what it represents (this is different from UNKNOWN polygon);
- UNKNOWN polygon: polygon not satisfying one of the labels above (i.e. with a non empty list of STREET objects and a non empty list of CHAR objects).

Check against the model of the GBKN

The check against the model tests whether every polygon conforms to either a BLOCK polygon, a STREET polygon or a NO-BLOCK-STREET polygon. If not, it is analyzed what can be done to make it conform to one of these. Therefore, if the label assigned to a polygon is UNKNOWN, it is checked to see if and how the interpretation can be improved.

The following cases are distinguished, and are tried in the order given. First case 1 is applied to all UNKNOWN polygons if applicable, then the changes generated are incorporated in the various data structures used, and for the remaining UNKNOWN polygons case 2 is applied where applicable. This is summarized in table 5.2.

pixel object	block of buildings	street	no block, no street	case 1: STREET object as CHAR object	case 2: try to label anyway	no solution can be found
STREET	0	[1, ∞ >	0	[1, ∞ >	[1, ∞ >	[1, ∞ >
CHAR label	[1, ∞ >	0	0	[1, ∞ >	[1, ∞ >	[1, ∞ >
	BLOCK polygon	STREET polygon	NO-BLOCK-STREET polygon	UNKNOWN polygon	UNKNOWN polygon	UNKNOWN polygon

Table 5.2: ‘truth table’ for checking the polygons. The numbers in the table give the number of objects of that type necessary for choosing that case. The order of generating hypotheses is from left to right.

Case 1. Observation: ≥ 1 STREET objects and ≥ 1 CHAR objects.

Hypothesis: the algorithm has erroneously labeled a STREET object as a CHAR object. Check if this is true.

For each CHAR object, a search is done in the polygon to the closest from the STREET list. In doing this, we try to find missing (parts of) street names (see figure 5.7). If the closest is on distance < $char_{maxblob2blob}$ pixels, the objects involved are grouped and the lists of CHAR objects and STREET objects are changed accordingly.

The interpretation flow starts over again.

Case 2. Observation: ≥ 1 STREET objects and ≥ 1 CHAR objects.

Hypothesis: the algorithm has labeled something wrong (and it was not corrected with case 1). We want to label it anyway if possible, so try that.

Rather than leaving a polygon labeled UNKNOWN polygon, we choose to determine the majority of STREET and CHAR objects, and label the polygon accordingly (the objects

map	figure	drawing method	x size y size		# pixels		res. (dpi)	scale
			x size	y size	total	object		
<i>training set</i>								
geo	2.2 (p. 17)	template	1970	2400	4 728 000	364 198	508	unknown ¹
leiden	2.3 (p. 18)	hand	2800	2700	7 560 000	571 297	400	1:1000
gbkn	4.7 (p. 60)	machine	3400	5600	19 040 000	780 983	400	1:500
<i>test set for cadastral maps</i>								
geonew		template	4000	1750	7 000 000	377 093	508	unknown ¹
leidennew		hand	1325	3300	4 372 500	331 721	400	1:1000
marconi	5.16	hand	2700	3200	8 640 000	95 568	400	1:1000
marsman	5.17	hand	2400	1500	3 600 000	184 213	400	1:1000
multatuli	5.18	hand	2200	2600	5 720 000	231 250	400	1:1000
<i>test set for GBKNs</i>								
gbknnew		machine	2750	2600	7 150 000	227 962	400	1:500
houten	5.1 (p. 75)	machine	3000	3000	9 000 000	630 067	400	1:1000
hoeve	5.19	machine	2250	2850	6 412 500	316 202	400	1:1000
haag	5.20	machine	2150	2100	4 515 000	331 234	400	1:1000

Table 5.3: general information about the maps used.

from the other category are relabeled to UNKNOWN object). If the number of STREET and CHAR objects is equal, the label of the polygon is not changed. The interpretation flow starts over again.

5.4 Evaluation

5.4.1 Error measurement method used

For the performance evaluation of the cadastral maps, the evaluation strategy from (Janssen et al. 1993) (described in chapter 2 on page 25) was used.

For GBKNs three different kinds of objects are found: blocks of buildings, streets, and NO-BLOCK-STREET polygons. The following symbols are used: N_T (total number of objects, the 'ground truth'), N_C (number of correctly found objects by the system), N_I (number of insertions or false positives), and N_D (number of deletions or false negatives). The percentage correctly found objects is calculated according to $\frac{N_C}{N_T} \times 100\%$, and the percentage corrections necessary is calculated according to $\frac{N_I + N_D}{N_T} \times 100\%$.

5.4.2 Description of the maps used

For evaluation, some maps from previous chapters were chosen to be able to make comparisons. Also, parts from these same maps that were not previously used, and some new maps were chosen to compare the performance on independent maps. This is summarized in table 5.3. The entry 'template' in the column 'drawing method' indicates that the map was drawn by hand, but that the characters and numbers were written using a template.

¹ The scale is not written on the map. Unfortunately, its location is also unknown, thus it is not possible to determine the scale by measurements in the real world and comparing this with measurements on the map.

Figure 5.16: section (2000 × 2000 pixels) of map marconi.

Figure 5.17: section (2000 × 1500 pixels) of map marsman.

Figure 5.18: section (2000 × 2000 pixels) of map multatuli.

Figure 5.19: section (2000 × 2000 pixels) of map hoeve.

Figure 5.20: section (2000 × 2000 pixels) of map haag.

The maps 'geo' and 'leiden' were the training set for the experiments on cadastral maps. 'Geonew' and 'leidennew' are not previously used parts from the respective paper maps. Using these gives an indication of the performance of the algorithm on similar maps it was trained on. The other three maps, 'marconi', 'marsman' and 'multatuli', are cadastral maps from Delft, The Netherlands. Evaluating on these maps gives an indication of the performance of the algorithm on independent maps. The last three maps were scanned from separate paper maps with a Hewlett-Packard Scanjet IIc scanner. The map 'marconi' has only a few parcels because it is from an industrial zone which has relatively large parcels.

The map 'gbkn' was the training set for the experiments on GBKNS. 'Gbknnew' is a part of the same paper map, but this part was not used previously. This gives an indication of the performance of the algorithm on similar maps it was trained on. The maps 'houten', 'hoeve' and 'haag' are different GBKNS, scanned from different paper maps, but all from Houten, The Netherlands. This gives an indication of the performance of the algorithm on independent maps. All the GBKNS were scanned with a Hewlett-Packard Scanjet IIc.

Training of our algorithm consisted of determining the model of the map and the interpretation flow, and determining accurate descriptions of the various symbols on the maps and how they are related to each other. Also, some parameters have to be set in advance, for example t_{dp} , which was set to the given value because it produced an accurate vectorization (see chapter 4). Training also consisted of determining what can go wrong and how it can go wrong, and constructing modules to correct for this.

Then, in the testing phase of our algorithm, the values of various parameters were determined as given in table 5.4. The values w_{glob} , $char_{globwidth}$, $char_{globheight}$, $pav_{globwidth}$, $pav_{globheight}$, and $cross_{globsize}$ were measured from the image (for w_{glob} see page 53). Other values were chosen because they produced a good result on the training set: they are a reasonable limit.

The results do not change if the values are changed a little bit, for example consider the 10 different connection signs given in figure 2.4 on page 19 and the figure with thresholds 5.11 on page 86. For all experiments, $cosi_{maxblob2blob}$ is relatively large compared to the 'real' distance, and the same is true for $cosi_{maxblob2blobvar}$, $cosi_{maxpart2line}$ and $cosi_{maxpart2part}$. Similar arguments hold for the other parameters. Extensive experiments in depth to determine the optimal values for all the parameters were not performed since these would result in a combinatorial explosion (see the Extensions section at the end of this chapter).

The parameters for the maps 'geonew', 'leidennew' and 'gbknnew' were the same as for the respective experiments 'geo', 'leiden' and 'gbkn'.

5.4.3 Results and discussion on cadastral maps

Evaluation of the parcels found

For the evaluation results of the parcels found, see table 5.5. If the results of the 'geo' and 'leiden' maps are compared with table 2.3 (page 27), it can be observed that the new results are significantly better. This is also valid for the not previously used parts of those maps. Both are caused by explicit use of model knowledge, which allows the system to correct the interpretation if it is not consistent.

The errors that still occur have several causes: for all maps except for the 'marconi' map, parts of connection signs are sometimes connected to the bitmap, and in some cases, the algorithm did not succeed to isolate them because the part at the other side of the line did not conform to

name	T	value					name	T	value			
		geo	leiden	marcomi	marsman	multatuli			gbkn	houten	hoeve	haag
t_{dp}	s	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	t_{dp}	s	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
w_{glob}	m	5.4	4.3	4.1	4.1	4.6	w_{glob}	m	4.5	4.4	3.4	4.8
$obj_{minsize}$	s	5	5	5	5	5	$obj_{minsize}$	s	5	5	5	5
$poly_{minperim}$	s	80	80	80	80	80	$pav_{globwidth}$	m	33	33	33	35
$cosi_{maxblob2blob}$	s	20	20	20	20	20	$pav_{globheight}$	m	20	20	20	20
$cosi_{maxblob2blobvar}$	s	10	10	10	10	10	$cross_{globsize}$	m	82	87	76	80
$cosi_{maxpart2line}$	s	20	20	20	20	20	$cross_{globsizevar}$	s	5	5	5	5
$cosi_{maxpart2part}$	s	30	30	30	30	30	pav_{init}	f	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
$cosi_{maxpart2midline}$	s	40	40	40	40	40	$char_{maxblob2blob}$	s	20	20	20	20
$cosi_{init}$	f	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	$char_{maxblob2blobvar}$	s	10	10	10	10
$char_{maxblob2blob}$	s	20	20	20	20	20	$char_{globwidth}$	m	25	20	20	20
$char_{maxblob2blobvar}$	s	20	20	20	20	20	$char_{globheight}$	m	40	40	40	40
$char_{globwidth}$	m	20	18	25	25	20	$char_{init}$	f	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4
$char_{globheight}$	m	45	25	35	30	30						
$char_{init}$	f	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5						

Table 5.4: left: parameter values for cadastral maps, right: parameter values for GBKNs. All values are in pixels, except for the factors $cosi_{init}$, $char_{init}$, and pav_{init} , which do not have a unit. The column 'T' gives the 'type' of the parameter: s is set, m is measured from the image, and f is a factor.

map	N_T	N_C	%
geo	40	37	92.5
leiden	104	83	79.8
geonew	38	35	92.1
leidennew	73	58	79.5
marconi	9	9	100
marsman	33	28	84.8
multatuli	33	27	81.8

Table 5.5: the evaluation of the parcels found.

the definition of COSI (sometimes it was labeled as CHAR object). Or, a part at one side of a line was labeled COSI object, but on the other side of the line the other part (not connected to the bitmap) was labeled something else. Another reason that connection signs are not found in the 'marsman' and 'multatuli' maps is that building hatches are confused with connection signs. In all these cases, a connection sign could not be found.

A different cause of error occurs if lines are discontinuous: then the algorithm to construct polygons joins the polygons 'separated' by the discontinuous line. In one occasion in the 'leiden' map, a parcel did not have a parcel number, thus it is impossible for the algorithm to label it as a parcel (it does not satisfy the parcel definition).

Evaluation of the parcel numbers found

For the evaluation results of the parcel numbers, see table 5.6. The results are the same for the 'geo' map when compared to table 2.4 on page 29 (both only one insertion), and for the 'leiden' map the results are slightly better (the distribution of insertions and deletions is different). The performance on the 'geonew' map is comparable with the performance of the 'geo' map, but the performance on the 'leidennew' map is slightly worse than on the 'leiden' map.

map	N_T	N_C	%	necessary		
				N_I	N_D	corrections %
geo	40	40	100	1	0	2.5
leiden	103	94	91.3	8	9	16.5
geonew	38	38	100	0	0	0
leidennew	73	62	84.9	5	11	21.9
marconi	9	9	100	0	0	0
marsman	33	33	100	0	0	0
multatuli	33	31	93.9	5	2	21.2

Table 5.6: the evaluation of the parcel numbers found.

Errors have several causes. For the 'geo', 'leiden', 'leidennew' and 'multatuli' maps, some insertions were caused by parts of connection signs erroneously labeled as CHAR object. For the 'leiden', 'leidennew' and 'multatuli' maps, deletions were caused by parcel numbers of which all separate numerals touch, *and* the whole also touches the boundary of the parcel on two or more different positions (this happened somewhat more in 'leidennew'). This is in fact twice a violation of the drawing rules: according to them numerals should neither touch each other, nor touch the boundary (Minister van VROM 1989).

For map 'leiden', the total number of parcel numbers is one smaller than the number of parcels (table 5.5). This is due to a (human) drawing error in the map: one parcel does not have a number (this is a violation of the drawing rules).

5.4.4 Results and discussion on GBKNS

Evaluation of the blocks of buildings found

For the evaluation results of the blocks of buildings found, see table 5.7. A distinction has been made between blocks completely in the field of view, and blocks connected to, or touching the

map	N_T	N_C	%	N_I	N_D	necessary corrections %
gbkn, blocks not connected to boundary	7	7	100	0	0	0
gbkn, blocks connected to boundary	6	5	—	2	1	—
gbknnew, blocks not connected to boundary	3	3	100	0	0	0
gbknnew, blocks connected to boundary	3	2	—	1	1	—
houten, blocks not connected to boundary	19	17	89.5	0	2	10.5
houten, blocks connected to boundary	7	6	—	1	1	—
hoeve, blocks not connected to boundary	9	9	100	0	0	0
hoeve, blocks connected to boundary	3	2	—	1	0	—
haag, blocks not connected to boundary	9	9	100	0	0	0
haag, blocks connected to boundary	3	2	—	0	1	—

Table 5.7: the evaluation of the blocks of buildings found.

boundary of the image. The former are in fact the only ones which can be evaluated because all attributes are known. However, from the latter important information can be learned, which may be useful in interpreting other parts of the map (at the other side of the boundary). Doing this, an initial interpretation is available, which can be changed if necessary.

For the 'houten' map, two blocks of buildings were missed because they had only one number which was a '1' and was too thin to be detected as CHAR object. No other numbers were present to start a local search to correct this (most blocks have more than one number).

Evaluation of the streets found

For the evaluation results of the streets found, see table 5.8. Streets will often intersect or touch the boundary of an image, so a distinction as in the previous subsection cannot be made. The insertions in the 'gbkn', 'houten', 'hoeve' and 'haag' map are caused by polygons intersecting the boundary of the image. At that boundary, a very small line was the only remaining part of a polygon continuing in the other image. The remainder of this polygon did satisfy the definition of STREET object, and the polygon enclosing that polygon was erroneously labeled as street. A rule to correct this (which was not implemented because otherwise learning on test set was done), could be to check if candidate STREET objects intersect the boundary of the image. If that is so, they should be relabeled to UNKNOWN object.

map	N_T	N_C	%	N_I	N_D	necessary corrections %
gbkn	13	13	100	1	0	7.7
gbknnew	4	4	100	0	0	0
houten	27	26	96.3	3	1	14.8
hoeve	21	15	71.4	2	6	38.1
haag	17	15	88.2	3	2	29.4

Table 5.8: the evaluation of the streets found.

The deletions of the 'houten' and the 'haag' map, and two deletions for the 'hoeve' map, were caused by a STREET object connected to the lines, and therefore the object was not found. Because this did not happen in the learning set, a procedure to correct this was not made.

For the 'hoeve' map, two other types of errors appeared, each causing two deletions. The first type was that a street name consisted of two words ('Het Kant'), which both were labeled as CHAR object. The CHAR labeling module for GBKNS relabels street names to STREET object if the length of the string is ≥ 5 characters (to avoid the use of a character recognition system), so this was to be expected. One polygon was labeled with the majority voting rule (case 2 in section 5.3.3) to BLOCK polygon, because it contained two CHAR objects and one STREET object (this happened to be a BLOCK polygon intersecting the boundary so it did not affect the performance). Another polygon was labeled UNKNOWN polygon because it contained an equal number of CHAR objects and STREET objects.

The other type of error in the 'hoeve' map were two STREET objects which were not found because they were just too small. The STREET module has to be changed to correct for this.

Evaluation of the NO-BLOCK-STREET polygons and UNKNOWN polygons

For the evaluation results of the NO-BLOCK-STREET polygons found, see table 5.9. The number of remaining UNKNOWN polygons is given in table 5.10. For all experiments, except for one UNKNOWN polygon from map 'hoeve', no UNKNOWN polygons remained at the end of the interpretation. Thus, the insertions from tables 5.7 and 5.8 are the deletion in table 5.9, and vice versa. For a discussion of the errors, see these subsections. For map 'hoeve', one UNKNOWN polygon remained, as was discussed in the previous paragraph.

map	N_T	N_C	%	N_I	N_D	necessary corrections %
gbkn	158	157	99.4	1	3	2.5
gbknnew	38	37	97.4	1	1	5.3
houten	158	154	97.5	4	4	5.1
hoeve	80	78	97.5	4	2	7.5
haag	48	45	93.8	3	3	12.5

Table 5.9: the evaluation of the NO-BLOCK-STREET polygons found.

map	N_T	N_I
gbkn	0	0
gbknnew	0	0
houten	0	0
hoeve	0	1
haag	0	0

Table 5.10: the number of remaining UNKNOWN polygons.

5.5 Robustness and improvements

Same model of the map for each type of map

As discussed in section 5.2, one model was chosen for each different type of map. The algorithm seems robust to this: both the two cadastral maps are different to each other, and the two GBKNS are different to each other, but the interpretation is not really influenced by this.

Same model of the map for both types of maps

One could consider to use one model of the map for both cadastral maps and GBKNS. Although it might be possible to create such a model, it will be very obscure: the main difference between cadastral maps and GBKNS is that the first contain objects which intersect different polygons to form one interpretation object (i.e. connection signs connecting polygons forming parcels), while these types of objects do not exist in GBKNS. Creating the same model for two different types of maps which have a basic structure so different, will not result in a very structured model.

Representation of objects by their models

Recognition of the objects (connection signs, parcel numbers, pavement symbols, street names, blocks of buildings, numbers and gridmarks) is fairly good, otherwise the performance on finding parcels, streets and blocks of buildings would not be so high. From this outcome, it can be concluded that the models of the objects are capable of describing objects whose appearance in real images vary widely, and also in sufficient detail to ensure that robust location of objects is possible. This is especially true for the connection signs and the parcel numbers since these have a large variance for each class.

Ability of coping with missing or incomplete data

For the cadastral maps, it appeared that the system was able to cope with missing or incomplete data, because connection signs sometimes did not meet the specifications. Our system was able to correct for this. The same is true for parcel numbers. For the GBKNS, sometimes a pavement symbol was connected to the lines of the image, and then the symbol was not detected. Because it happened only once in the training set, an additional check to correct this was not made.

5.6 Extensions

Initialization of the parameters and learning (acquisition of knowledge)

In the current algorithm, initialization of parameters (average height/width of characters, connection signs, etc.) is determined by hand and used as a-priori knowledge in the algorithm. The algorithm may be improved by using these a-priori sizes as initial values, and refining these values during the interpretation. This may be done by initially providing the algorithm with some samples of characters, connection signs, etc., and using the system. After the interpretation has finished, all objects of the same class are considered and statistics are computed. These can then be used in a new estimate of the values, and then the algorithm can be run again. The value to optimize is the number of parcels detected for cadastral maps, or the number of blocks of buildings and streets for GBKNS.

It is a problem however that there are so many parameters (15 for cadastral maps, and 13 for GBKNS). The optimal solution will be solving a problem in a 15- or 13-dimensional space, which is a problem of considerable complexity.

Although initializing parameters and a learning process is a very interesting problem, no research was done in this area because it is beyond the scope of this thesis.

Separate high level language to construct models or to describe models

A high level language to construct models or to describe models would be an interesting extension of the algorithm. Why this was not implemented was discussed in the Introduction of this chapter. The high level language should allow to easily specify the various objects found on the map. Ideally, after specifying the interpretation flow, the system should be capable of interpreting the map. Some approaches in this direction have been taken in the KADS system (Schreiber et al. 1993), described in chapter 1.

5.7 Conclusions and summary

In this chapter, a model-based interpretation system for two kinds of maps is described. The two kinds are cadastral maps and GBKNS. For each kind of map, one separate model is used. Each model consists of two parts: the model of the interpretation flow, describing the interpretation flow in the system, and the model of the map, specifying the different objects on the map, the relations, how objects can be detected, and how the interpretation can be checked for consistency. If the check fails, methods are provided to correct for this.

The system is modular, which is shown by the small changes necessary when changing the application from cadastral maps to GBKNS. Results compare favorably with our initial system described in chapter 2.

General conclusions

In this chapter, an extended survey of the conclusions of the different chapters will be given. The relations among the various chapters are indicated. Suggestions are given for further research in model-based map interpretation.

Chapter 1, Introduction to 'model-based' and its vocabulary

This chapter is the general introduction to the thesis. It gives a (coarse) classification of model-based strategies, a discussion on the proposed model structure, and a common vocabulary.

The classification of model-based strategies distinguishes between authors who describe the objects to interpret with a model, authors who base the interpretation method on a model, and authors who combine these two. From the literature review we conclude that many different notions of model-based exist. This may give rise to confusion when discussing model-based issues or model-based systems.

Therefore, a common vocabulary to be used in model-based image processing is proposed at the end of chapter 1. 'Simple' words as 'model' or 'knowledge' can be interpreted in many ways, and therefore meanings and definitions of phrases in this thesis are defined in this chapter.

A model structure is proposed. It consists of three different models: the *model of the interpretation flow*, the *model of the map*, and the *model of the object*. This model structure can be classified as a method in which both the objects to interpret and the interpretation method are based on a model. This approach has been taken because objects of a large variability can be represented and because a structured interpretation process simplifies the design of the system.

Model-based strategies can be found at various places in this thesis: in chapter 3 and 4 on a detailed level, and in chapter 5 on a global level. Chapter 2 is more or less the origin of this thesis: during development of a first (base line) interpretation system for cadastral maps various problems arose, and it seemed advantageous to use model-based image processing to solve some of these problems.

Chapter 2, Evaluation method for an automatic map interpretation system for cadastral maps

In this chapter, a (bottom-up) base line system for automatic map interpretation for cadastral maps and a method for evaluating such a system are presented. During the development of the interpretation system, it appeared that all kinds of artefacts disturb the interpretation process

and do not allow us to make a reasonably simple and straightforward interpretation system. These artefacts originate from several sources and can be classified as complicating the vectorization or complicating the interpretation.

The artefacts which complicate the vectorization process have to do with the input image (e.g. pixels having a 'wrong' value, causing gaps in the lines of the bitmap), with the skeletonization (small, unnecessary lines), and with the Douglas-Peucker vectorization algorithm used (in some cases too many nodes and edges). Some of these problems are solved using a median filter on the input image. We chose to solve most of these problems using special 'clean up' rules processing the vectorization: to correct gaps in the vectorization, to remove link nodes whose bend angle is approximately 180° , and (under certain conditions) to remove small edges in corners, T-junctions and in X-junctions.

The net effect of these clean up rules has been evaluated by comparing the 'raw' vectorization (no clean up rules applied), and the 'refined' vectorization (clean up rules applied). The number of nodes and edges decreased significantly, but the number of wrong pixels and the number of wrong lines increased slightly. This small increase in error was caused for example by vectorization of a slightly curved line. One of the clean up rules removed some edges in this curve because the angle between successive edges was approximately 180° . At such particular curves, edges should not be removed because they represent the curvature.

This small increase in error is not always acceptable. Therefore, a new (adaptive) vectorization algorithm was developed, described in chapter 4. The main difference between the vectorization with clean up rules and the adaptive vectorization algorithm is that the latter uses the input image to improve and correct the vectorization.

Other artefacts which do not allow us to make a reasonable simple and straightforward interpretation system and which complicate the interpretation process have to do with the representation of objects. For example, connection signs are drawn in many different ways, and parcel numbers sometimes touch each other.

In evaluating the interpretation system, it appeared that some connection signs were not found because e.g. parts were connected to the lines of the image or they had a shape which was not anticipated. Some parcel numbers were not found because they were connected to the boundaries of the parcels. This was caused by the large variation in these types of objects.

Rather than solving these problems in this bottom-up system, a different approach was taken as described in chapter 5.

Chapter 3, Compilation of mosaics from separately scanned line drawings

One of the problems in automatic line drawing interpretation is the finite size of scanners, or that scanners of the required size are not available. This is a problem, because sometimes objects necessary for the interpretation are on the other—invisible or unknown—side of the boundary. This chapter describes a solution for this problem. Using separately scanned line drawings which have to have an overlap, points common in both coordinate systems are found and used in a geometric transformation to transform the coordinate system of one line drawing into the coordinate system of the other. The model used is on a low level: edges in the vectorization are matched with each other.

The resulting system was evaluated by computing the deviation and distance in pixels between the projection of one line drawing and the projection of the reference line drawing. Results are good: the errors are mostly one pixel distance from the desired position.

Sometimes, there are no objects in the overlap area, or the edges in the overlap area have the same number of neighbors on both sides and subsequently cannot be used for the matching procedure. One solution is to use a special marker which can be placed in the overlap area, and to remove this marker after scanning. This will only work if several scans from the same (paper) map are made, because otherwise an accurate position of the marker may be difficult to obtain. Another possibility is to match using a series of other drawings overlapping the first two drawings at a different place.

This chapter relates to other chapters in this thesis because the method presented can be applied as a preprocessing step in one of the map interpretation systems in chapter 2 or 5: it allows us to present a larger line drawing to the algorithm instead of several smaller ones, and thus avoid boundary problems.

Chapter 4, Adaptive vectorization of line drawing images

This chapter describes a novel method for vectorization of line drawing images. It consists of different modules: coarse vectorization, determination of the anchor points, and refined vectorization between the anchor points. Because of its modularity, postprocessing can be done after each module.

Several experiments were done to find the best configuration of the postprocessing modules. The best vectorization method used postprocessing modules independent of the type of line drawing: the coarse vectorization was postprocessed by removing link nodes if the bend angle between the two edges is small and merged endpoints of short edges. The postprocessing of the refined vectorization removed edges connected to non-anchor link nodes if the error is 0 for all edges involved and moved nodes in the eight chain code directions under the condition that the error of the attached edges decreased.

This vectorization algorithm is called adaptive because it uses the original line drawing to correct and improve the vectorization. In fact, it is model-based at a detailed level, but it is not called 'model-based' to avoid confusion with the model-based notion from chapters 1 and 5.

This method was developed because the standard Douglas-Peucker vectorization produces a large number of nodes and edges which are not always necessary for a good representation of the line drawing. The vectorization using clean up rules from chapter 2 is not always satisfactory because it may give a small increase in error compared to the Douglas-Peucker algorithm. The adaptive vectorization algorithm always produces less nodes and edges and a smaller error (except in one case) than the standard Douglas-Peucker algorithm and the vectorization using clean up rules from chapter 2.

The anchor points produced by the algorithm may be used for other purposes: for example as control points in the algorithm to construct mosaics from separately scanned line drawings in chapter 3. They may be suitable for this since their position is accurately determined using maximum threshold morphology.

The adaptive vectorization algorithm is used to vectorize the line drawings and for the construction of polygons in the model-based map interpretation algorithm in chapter 5. Since the algorithm produces less nodes and edges than the Douglas-Peucker algorithm or the vectoriza-

tion algorithm from chapter 2, polygons with less edges will be constructed. This is computationally more efficient.

Chapter 5, Model-based interpretation of two types of maps

Using the concept of model-based introduced in chapter 1, an interpretation system for cadastral maps is built. Then, using the same model of the interpretation flow, it is extended to a system for interpretation of large-scale base maps. The approach is flexible: the transition from one type of map to another type of map does not cause a complete redesign of the interpretation system.

The advantage of using a model-based approach compared to a bottom-up approach as in chapter 2 is that a-priori knowledge can be used more effectively. This can be seen when comparing the system in chapter 2 with the cadastral map interpretation system in this chapter. The former system has two separate paths in the interpretation flow. In principle, these might be usable to improve the algorithm since parcels found in one path may be used to correct parcel numbers found in the other path, and vice versa (this was only investigated in a pilot study). However, changes in the algorithm to exploit this as much as possible may be complicated, and the resulting algorithm will be cumbersome.

On the other hand, the algorithm described in this chapter uses a model of the interpretation flow and a separate model of the map allowing the incorporation of consistency checks much more easily. In case of an inconsistency, the vector and/or pixel representation of an object permits us to correct for this. The changes are fed back to the lower levels of the system and the interpretation is redone for the inconsistent objects. Another advantage of the methodology in this chapter is that modules can be re-used in other interpretation systems.

The performance of the system in this chapter is better than the performance of the system in chapter 2. This is caused by e.g. connection signs connected to the lines of the image, connection signs labeled incorrectly, or by parcel numbers connected to the lines of the image which could not be corrected by the algorithm of chapter 2. Sometimes, the algorithm in this chapter does not succeed in finding a connection sign if part of it is labeled incorrectly.

The performance of the algorithm for the interpretation of large-scale base maps is good, but improvements are possible in detecting the streets. The streets were sometimes not found because the pavement symbols were connected to the lines of the image, or because part of a polygon touched the boundary of the image and was labeled incorrectly as pavement symbol.

Considerations for further research in model-based map interpretation

The model-based map interpretation system for cadastral maps from chapter 5 can be improved by a more accurate search for parcel numbers and connection signs. Sometimes, parts of connection signs were not found because they were confused with building hatches. Since this did not happen in the learning set, this could not be anticipated. Parcels are sometimes not found because a line of the parcel boundary is broken. A more elaborate reconnection mechanism may solve this (possibly in connection with the adaptive vectorization algorithm).

The model-based map interpretation system for large-scale base maps from chapter 5 can be improved by a better module to find pavement symbols, which were sometimes not found.

Just as with the parcel numbers or connection signs in the cadastral maps, a module to separate a pavement symbol from the lines of the image will improve the performance. Since this did not happen in the learning set, this was not anticipated.

A very interesting research issue is the acquisition of the a-priori knowledge and the representation of that knowledge. As discussed in the Extensions section of chapter 5, we have chosen to determine the initialization values of the parameters by hand, and to use that as a-priori knowledge in the algorithm. The model-based interpretation algorithm may be improved by using some predefined values (for example derived from prototype objects) to detect the various objects in the image, and refining these values automatically during the interpretation process.

An other extension can be a combination of the mosaic construction algorithm with the model-based interpretation methodology of chapter 5. The absence of objects in the overlap area may be compensated by matching (and interpreting) through a series of contiguous line drawings.

The adaptive vectorization algorithm and the mosaic construction algorithm may be combined to form mosaics from line drawings without overlap, as proposed in the Extensions section of chapter 3. If this is combined with the model-based interpretation strategy of chapter 5, errors in the vectorization, in the construction of mosaics, or in the interpretation may be corrected using knowledge from the various levels. However, the resulting system may be complicated since having many relations and consistency checks between the various levels can make it difficult to design in a modular way.

References

- Alberda, J.E. (1983). *Inleiding landmeetkunde*. Delftse Uitgevers Maatschappij B.V. ISBN 90-6562-009-5. In Dutch.
- Attneave, F. (1954). Some informational aspects of visual perception. *Psychological Review* 61(3), 183-193.
- Chang, Y.-L. and J.-J. Leou (1992, Oct.). A model-based approach to representation and matching of object shape patterns. *Pattern Recognition Letters* 13, 707-714.
- Cooper, D.H., N. Bryson, and C.J. Taylor (1989, Feb.). An object location strategy using shape and grey-level models. *Image and Vision Computing* 7(1), 50-56.
- den Hartog, J.E., T.K. ten Kate, and J.J. Gerbrands (1995). Knowledge-based interpretation of utility maps. Accepted for publication in *Computer Vision, Graphics and Image Processing: Image Understanding*.
- Denisov, D.A. and A.K. Dudkin (1994). Model-based chromosome recognition via hypotheses construction/verification. *Pattern Recognition Letters* 15(3), 299-307.
- Dettori, G. (1982). An on-line algorithm for polygonal approximation of digitized plane curves. In *Proc. 6th IAPR Int. Conf. Pattern Recognition (Munich, Germany, Oct. 19-22, 1982)*, Volume 2, pp. 739-741.
- Dori, D., Y. Liang, J. Dowell, and I. Chai (1993). Sparse-pixel recognition of primitives in engineering drawings. *Machine Vision and Applications* 6(2-3), 69-82.
- Douglas, D.H. and T.K. Peucker (1973, Dec.). Algorithms for the reduction of the number of points required to represent a digitized line or its caricature. *The Canadian Cartographer* 10(2), 112-122.
- Duncan, J.S., R.L. Owen, L.H. Staib, and P. Anandan (1991). Measurement of non-rigid motion using contour shape descriptors. In *Proc. IEEE Conf. on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (Lahaina, Hawaii, June 3-6, 1991)*, pp. 318-324. IEEE Computer Society Press.
- Ejiri, M., S. Kakumoto, T. Miyatake, S. Shimada, and K. Iwamura (1990). Automatic recognition of engineering drawings and maps. In R. Kasturi and M. M. Trivedi (Eds.), *Image analysis applications*, Chapter 3, pp. 73-126. Marcel Dekker Inc.
- ESRI (1992). *Understanding GIS: the ARC/INFO method* (6th ed.). Redlands: ESRI.
- Filipski, A.J. and R. Flandrena (1992, July). Automated conversion of engineering drawings to CAD form. *Proceedings of the IEEE* 80(7), 1195-1209.

- Fontana/Collins (1986). *The Fontana Dictionary of Modern Thought* (7th ed.). Fontana/Collins. A. Bullock and O. Stallybrass (Eds.). ISBN 0-00-636740-2.
- Goetcherian, V. (1980). From binary to grey tone image processing using fuzzy logic concepts. *Pattern Recognition* 12(1), 7-15.
- Gonzalez, R.C. and R.E. Woods (1992). *Digital Image Processing*. Addison Wesley. ISBN 0-201-50803-6.
- Hickin, B.W., D.J. Maguire, and A.J. Strachan (1991). *Introduction to GIS: the ARC/INFO method*. Midlands Regional Research Laboratory, Leicester.
- Hilditch, C.J. (1969). Linear skeletons from square cupboards. In B. Meltzer and D. Mitchie (Eds.), *Machine Intelligence* 4, Chapter 22, pp. 403-420. Univ. Press Edinburgh.
- Houghton Mifflin Company (1985). *American Heritage Dictionary* (2nd ed.). Houghton Mifflin Company. ISBN 0-395-32944-2.
- Houghton Mifflin Company (1988). *Roget's II — The new Thesaurus*. Houghton Mifflin Company. ISBN 0-395-48317-4.
- Janssen, R.D.T., R.P.W. Duin, and A.M. Vossepoel (1993). Evaluation method for an automatic map interpretation system for cadastral maps. In *Proc. 2nd IAPR Int. Conf. on Document Analysis and Recognition (Tsukuba Science City, Japan, Oct. 20-22, 1993)*, pp. 125-128. IEEE Computer Society Press.
- Janssen, R.D.T. and A.M. Vossepoel (1994). Compilation of mosaics from separately scanned line drawings. In *Proc. 2nd IEEE Workshop on Applications of Computer Vision (Sarasota, U.S.A., Dec. 5-7, 1994)*, pp. 36-43. IEEE Computer Society Press.
- Janssen, R.D.T. and A.M. Vossepoel (1995). Adaptive vectorization of line drawing images. Submitted for publication in *Computer Vision, Graphics and Image Processing: Image Understanding*.
- Kise, K., K. Momota, M. Yamaoka, J. Sugiyama, N. Babaguchi, and Y. Tezuka (1990). Model based understanding of document images. In *IAPR Workshop on Machine Vision Applications (Tokyo, Japan, Nov. 28-30, 1990)*, pp. 471-474.
- Kise, K., M. Yamaoka, N. Babaguchi, and Y. Tezuka (1992). Model based system for analyzing document images. In *Proc. 11th IAPR Int. Conf. Pattern Recognition (The Hague, The Netherlands, Aug. 30 - Sept. 3, 1992)*, Volume 2, pp. 647-650. IEEE Computer Society Press.
- Kurozumi, Y. and W.A. Davis (1982). Polygonal approximation by the minimax method. *Computer Graphics and Image Processing* 19, 248-264.
- Lammerts van Bueren, G.M. (1993). Scannen + vectoriseren of digitaliseren? Een vergelijking. *Geodesia* 35(3), 114-118. In Dutch.
- Leu, J.-G. and L. Chen (1988, Apr.). Polygonal approximation of 2-D shapes through boundary merging. *Pattern Recognition Letters* 7(4), 231-238.
- Leung, M.K. and Y.-H. Yang (1990). Dynamic two-step algorithm in curve fitting. *Pattern Recognition* 23(1/2), 69-79.
- Maderlechner, G. and H. Mayer (1994). Automated acquisition of geographic information from scanned maps for GIS using frames and semantic networks. In *Proc. 12th IAPR Int.*

- Conf. Pattern Recognition (Jerusalem, Israel, Oct. 9–13, 1994)*, Volume II, pp. 361–363. IEEE Computer Society Press.
- Marr, D. and H.K. Nishihara (1978). Representation and recognition of the spatial organization of three-dimensional shapes. *Proc. of the Royal Society London B* 200, 269–294.
- Mayer, H., C. Heipke, and G. Maderlechner (1992). Knowledge-based interpretation of scanned large-scale maps using multi-level modelling. In *Int. Archives of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing, Proc. 17th ISPRS Congress (Washington, U.S.A., Aug. 2–14, 1992)*, Volume XXIX (B3), pp. 578–585. Int. Society for Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing.
- Minister van VROM (1989). *Instructie kadaster*. Ministerie van VROM, Dienst van het kadaster en de openbare registers. In Dutch.
- Moore, L.R. (1992). Software for cartographic raster-to-vector conversion. In *Int. Archives of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing, Proc. 17th ISPRS Congress (Washington, U.S.A., Aug. 2–14, 1992)*. Int. Society for Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing.
- Niemann, H., G. Sagerer, S. Schröder, and F. Kummert (1990). ERNEST: A semantic network system for pattern understanding. *IEEE Tr. on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence* 12(9), 883–905.
- Pavlidis, T. (1984). A hybrid vectorization algorithm. In *Proc. 7th IAPR Int. Conf. Pattern Recognition (Montreal, Canada, July 30–Aug. 2, 1984)*, pp. 490–492. IEEE Computer Society Press.
- Pavlidis, T. (1986). A vectorizer and feature extractor for document recognition. *Computer Vision, Graphics and Image Processing* 35, 111–127.
- Preston, K. and M.J.B. Duff (1984). *Modern cellular automata*. Advanced applications in pattern recognition. Plenum Press. ISBN 0–306–41737–5.
- Puliti, P. and G. Tascini (1993, Apr.). Knowledge-based approach to image interpretation. *Image and Vision Computing* 11(3), 122–128.
- Ramer, U. (1972). An iterative procedure for the polygonal approximation of plane curves. *Computer Graphics and Image Processing* 1, 244–256.
- Ray, B.K. and K.S. Ray (1992, June). Detection of significant points and polygonal approximation of digitized curves. *Pattern Recognition Letters* 13(6), 443–452.
- Rich, E. (1988). *Artificial Intelligence* (7th ed.). McGraw-Hill. ISBN 0–07–Y66508–7.
- Rohr, K. (1994). Towards model-based recognition of human movements in image sequences. *Computer Vision, Graphics and Image Processing: Image Understanding* 59(1), 94–115.
- Rosenfeld, A. and J.L. Pfaltz (1968). Distance functions on digital pictures. *Pattern Recognition* 1, 33–61.
- Schreiber, G., B. Wielinga, and J. Breuker (Eds.) (1993). *KADS, a principled approach to knowledge-based system development*, Volume 11 of *Knowledge-based systems*. Academic Press. ISBN 0–12–629040–7.
- Serra, J. (1982). *Image analysis and mathematical morphology*. Academic Press. ISBN 0–12–637242–X.
- Sirjani, A. and G.R. Cross (1988, June). An algorithm for polygonal approximation of a digital object. *Pattern Recognition Letters* 7(5), 299–303.

- Sklansky, J. and V. Gonzalez (1980). Fast polygonal approximation of digitized curves. *Pattern Recognition* 12, 327–331.
- Slama, C.C. (Ed.) (1980). *Manual of photogrammetry* (4th ed.). American Society of Photogrammetry. ISBN 0–937294–01–2.
- Staib, L.H. and J.S. Duncan (1989). Parametrically deformable contour models. In *Proc. IEEE Conf. on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (San Diego, U.S.A., June 4–8, 1989)*, pp. 98–103. IEEE Computer Society Press.
- Suzuki, S. and T. Yamada (1990). MARIS: map recognition input system. *Pattern Recognition* 23(8), 919–933.
- Teh, C.-H. and R.T. Chin (1989, Aug.). On the detection of dominant points on digital curves. *IEEE Tr. on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence* 11(8), 859–872.
- van den Boomgaard, R. (1992). *Mathematical morphology: extensions towards computer vision*. PhD. Thesis, University of Amsterdam.
- Verwer, B.J.H. (1988). Improved metrics in image processing applied to the Hilditch skeleton. In *Proc. 9th IAPR Int. Conf. Pattern Recognition (Rome, Italy, Nov. 14–17, 1988)*, pp. 137–142. IEEE Computer Society Press.
- Verwer, B.J.H. (1991). Local distances for distance transformations in two and three dimensions. *Pattern Recognition Letters* 12(11), 671–682.
- Wall, K. (1986). Curve fitting based on polygonal approximation. In *Proc. 8th IAPR Int. Conf. Pattern Recognition (Paris, France, Oct. 27–31, 1986)*, pp. 1273–1275. IEEE Computer Society Press.
- Wall, K. and P.-E. Danielsson (1984). A fast sequential method for polygonal approximation of digitized curves. *Computer Vision, Graphics and Image Processing* 28, 220–227.
- Williams, C.M. (1978). An efficient algorithm for the piecewise linear approximation of planar curves. *Computer Graphics and Image Processing* 8, 286–293.
- Williams, C.M. (1981). Bounded straight-line approximation of digitized planar curves and lines. *Computer Graphics and Image Processing* 16, 370–381.

Summary

The application of model-based image processing to the interpretation of maps

This thesis describes various aspects of model-based image processing.

One aspect is a model-based interpretation system for two types of maps, presented in chapter 5. There, and in chapter 1, a model-based interpretation methodology is proposed which consists of three different models. The *model of the interpretation flow* describes the flow of the interpretation process, the functionality of the modules, and their connections. The *model of the map* describes map specific information: which objects can be found, what are the relations between the various objects, where can they be found, what can go wrong, and how to correct errors. The third model, the *model of the object*, describes how the object can be found.

This methodology is used for interpreting two types of maps. The approach is reasonably flexible, as can be seen from the transition from an interpretation system for cadastral maps, to an interpretation system for large-scale base maps. The basic interpretation flow and some modules remain the same, a few modules have to be removed and some others have to be added, but it is not necessary to redo the whole interpretation system.

The performance of the model-based cadastral map interpretation system is compared to a bottom-up interpretation system, described in chapter 2. The first performs better than the latter, and that is caused by the model knowledge which allows us to correct for the errors made.

The bottom-up system was the base line system for investigating a map interpretation system. It also served to investigate the vectorization problem. It appears that during vectorization, problems may arise because some lines are broken or because too many nodes and edges are generated. This was not only caused by the vectorization algorithm used (the Douglas-Peucker algorithm), but also by the preprocessing necessary to obtain one pixel thick lines, or by distortions already present in the (paper) input image.

In the base line system, rules were devised to correct for this, and indeed the number of nodes and edges decreased considerably, while the error only increased slightly. Although the rules worked well, it was not a satisfactory solution because a slight increase in error is not always acceptable.

Therefore, in chapter 4 an adaptive vectorization algorithm was developed which used the input line drawing to improve and to correct the vectorization. This adaptive vectorization al-

gorithm performed better than the standard Douglas-Peucker algorithm, and it also performed better than the Douglas-Peucker algorithm with the 'clean up' rules from chapter 2. This adaptive vectorization algorithm is the second aspect in model-based image processing in this thesis. It was called 'adaptive' to avoid confusion with the model-based notion in chapters 1 and 5.

In chapter 3 a system to compile mosaics from separately scanned line drawings is presented. This system automatically finds matching edges, and from these corresponding points in two separately scanned line drawings. These corresponding points are used in a geometric transformation to transform the coordinate system from one line drawing to the other. Thus, the model used is on a low level. Such a system can be used as a submodule before the actual interpretation algorithm: it permits us to present a larger line drawing to the algorithm instead of several smaller ones, and thus avoid boundary problems. For instance, an interpretation system for cadastral maps cannot find parcels on the boundary of the image, because objects necessary for the interpretation (e.g. parcel numbers) may be on the other—invisible or unknown—side of the boundary.

The notion 'model-based' is often only used for high level systems. However, we believe that the *principle* of model-based (expectations of reality used to guide the interpretation, and if necessary, to correct it) can be found on all levels, as illustrated in this thesis.

Rik D.T. Janssen

Samenvatting

De toepassing van modelgestuurde beeldbewerking op interpretatie van kaarten

Dit proefschrift beschrijft verschillende aspecten van modelgestuurde beeldbewerking.

Eén van de aspecten is een modelgestuurd interpretatiesysteem voor twee soorten kaarten, beschreven in hoofdstuk 5. In dat hoofdstuk en in hoofdstuk 1, wordt een modelgestuurde interpretatiemethodologie voorgesteld die bestaat uit drie verschillende modellen. Het *model van de interpretatievolgorde* beschrijft de volgorde van de modules in het interpretatieproces, de functionaliteit van de modules, en hun verbindingen. Het *model van de kaart* beschrijft kaart-specifieke informatie: welke objecten kunnen gevonden worden, wat zijn de relaties tussen de verschillende objecten, waar kunnen ze gevonden worden, wat kan fout gaan, en hoe moeten fouten verbeterd worden. Het derde model, het *model van het object*, geeft aan hoe het object gevonden kan worden.

Deze methodologie wordt gebruikt voor het interpreteren van twee soorten kaarten. De aanpak is redelijk flexibel, zoals gezien kan worden aan de hand van de overgang van een interpretatiesysteem voor kadastrale kaarten naar een interpretatiesysteem voor grootschalige basiskaarten. Het model van de interpretatievolgorde blijft hetzelfde, sommige modules blijven hetzelfde, een paar modules moeten verwijderd worden, en een paar moeten toegevoegd worden, maar het is niet nodig om het hele interpretatiesysteem opnieuw te ontwerpen.

De testresultaten van het modelgestuurde kadastrale kaartinterpretatiesysteem worden vergeleken met het bottom-up interpretatiesysteem uit hoofdstuk 2. Het eerste systeem werkt beter dan het tweede systeem, en dat wordt veroorzaakt door de modelkennis die toelaat om eventuele fouten automatisch te verbeteren.

Het bottom-up systeem was het eerste (basis)systeem voor het onderzoeken van een kaartinterpretatiesysteem. Het diende tevens voor het onderzoeken van de vectorisatie. Het bleek dat tijdens de vectorisatie verschillende problemen kunnen optreden omdat sommige lijnen onderbroken zijn of omdat veel nodes en vectoren gegenereerd worden. Dit werd niet alleen veroorzaakt door het gebruikte vectorisatiealgoritme (het Douglas-Peucker algoritme), maar ook door de preprocessing nodig voor het verkrijgen van één pixel dikke lijnen, of door verstoringen die al op de te scannen (papieren) kaart aanwezig zijn.

Voor het basissysteem werden regels ontwikkeld om dit te corrigeren, en hierdoor nam het

aantal nodes en vectoren inderdaad behoorlijk af, terwijl de fout slechts een klein beetje toenam. Alhoewel deze regels goed werkten, was het geen bevredigende oplossing omdat een lichte toename in fout niet altijd acceptabel is.

Daarom werd een nieuw adaptief vectorisatiealgoritme ontwikkeld, beschreven in hoofdstuk 4. Het gebruikt de input lijntekening om de vectorisatie nauwkeuriger te maken en te corrigeren. Dit adaptieve vectorisatiealgoritme werkt beter dan het standaard Douglas-Peucker algoritme, en het werkt ook beter dan het Douglas-Peucker algoritme met opschoonregels uit hoofdstuk 2. Het adaptieve vectorisatiealgoritme is het tweede aspect van modelgestuurde beeldbewerking in dit proefschrift. Het wordt 'adaptief' genoemd om verwarring met het modelgestuurde begrip uit de hoofdstukken 1 en 5 te vermijden.

In hoofdstuk 3 wordt een systeem beschreven om mozaïeken te construeren uit apart gescande lijntekeningen. Het systeem vindt automatisch bij elkaar passende vectoren in twee apart gescande lijntekeningen, en hieruit corresponderende punten. Deze corresponderende punten worden gebruikt in een geometrische transformatie om het coördinatenstelsel van één lijntekening naar het andere te transformeren. Het gebruikte model zit dus op een laag niveau. Zo een systeem kan gebruikt worden als een submodule voor het eigenlijke interpretatiealgoritme: het staat toe om één grote lijntekening aan het algoritme te presenteren in plaats van verschillende kleinere, en vermijdt dus zo het randprobleem. Een interpretatiesysteem voor kadastrale kaarten kan geen percelen op de rand van het beeld vinden omdat objecten die voor de interpretatie nodig zijn (bijvoorbeeld perceelnummers) aan de andere —onzichtbare of onbekende— kant van de rand van het beeld staan.

Het begrip 'modelgestuurd' wordt vaak alleen gebruikt bij hoog-niveau systemen. Het *principe* van modelgestuurd (verwachtingen over de werkelijkheid om de interpretatie te sturen en indien nodig te verbeteren) kan ons inziens echter gevonden worden op alle niveaus, zoals geïllustreerd in dit proefschrift.

Rik D.T. Janssen

Acknowledgements

When the KGB was founded on August 22, 1991, we were happy that the original KGB had ceased to exist: this allowed us, members of the first hour, to create a discussion group on 'KennisGestuurde Beeldbewerking' (in English: knowledge based image processing). The members of the first hour were: Albert Vossepoel, Bob Duin, Eric Backer, Jan Gerbrands, Ton ten Kate, Jurgen den Hartog, and Rik Janssen.

I would like to thank them —and the later members— for the hours of fruitful discussions, for the (additional) research to be done after such a meeting, and also, for the research which was not necessary to be done because it appeared that it had been done before.

Also, I would like to thank prof.dr. Ted Young for his critical remarks on the concepts of this thesis. They have led to many clarifications and improvements.

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Curriculum vitae

Rik D.T. Janssen was born in Utrecht, The Netherlands, on November 6, 1966. In 1984, he obtained his Atheneum B diploma from the Scholengemeenschap de Breul in Zeist. Subsequently, he studied Computer Science at the University of Utrecht, where he obtained his Masters Degree in 1991. His specialization was in Neural Networks, Artificial Intelligence, and Automatic Speech Recognition. This study was completed with a thesis 'Perceptrons en automatische spraakherkenning' (English: 'Perceptrons and automatic speech recognition').

From May 1990 until February 1991, he worked as Visiting Researcher with prof.dr. R.A. Cole at the Oregon Graduate Institute of Science and Technology, Beaverton, Oregon, U.S.A., where he did research in developing accurate speaker-independent speech recognition systems. This led to two publications:

- R.D.T. Janssen, M. Fanty, and R.A. Cole (1991), Speaker-independent phonetic classification in continuous English letters. In *Proc. Int. Joint Conf. on Neural Networks (Seattle, U.S.A., July 8–12, 1991)*, pp. II-801–II-808. IEEE Computer Society Press.
- R.A. Cole, M. Fanty, M. Gopalakrishnan, and R.D.T. Janssen (1991), Speaker-independent name retrieval from spellings using a database of 50,000 names. In *Proc. Int. Conf. on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (Toronto, Canada, May 14–17, 1991)*, pp. 325–328. IEEE Computer Society Press.

In June 1991, he joined the Pattern Recognition Group at the Faculty of Applied Physics of the Delft University of Technology as a Ph.D. student (Onderzoeker in Opleiding). In co-operation with the TNO Institute of Applied Physics (TPD), he did research in model-based image processing.

He was a reviewer for the 11th (1992) and 12th (1994) Int. Conf. on Pattern Recognition, published several papers (in extended version included in this thesis), and gave various presentations in Japan, the U.S.A., and in the Netherlands. Also, he visited three conferences: the 11th Int. Conf. on Pattern Recognition (The Hague, The Netherlands, Aug. 30–Sept. 3, 1992), the 2nd Int. Conf. on Document Analysis and Recognition (Tsukuba, Japan, Oct. 20–22, 1993), and the 2nd IEEE Workshop on Applications of Computer Vision (Sarasota, U.S.A., Dec. 5–7, 1994).

The application of model-based image processing to the interpretation of maps

Nederlandse samenvatting voor de niet-specialist

Rik D.T. Janssen

Inleiding

Dit proefschrift onderzoekt een nieuwe computergestuurde interpretatietechniek (het onderzoekt een nieuwe techniek om met een computer zinvolle informatie uit een beeld te halen). Om de techniek te ontwikkelen is een bepaald soort kaarten gekozen. Er is gekozen voor interpretatie van kaarten (i.p.v. bijvoorbeeld luchtfoto's) omdat ze getekend zijn volgens vaststaande regels en omdat interpretatie een interessant probleem is.

Computergestuurde interpretatie van kaarten is een interessant probleem omdat er tegenwoordig nog erg veel kaarten op papier of film staan. Op zo'n kaart kan slechts een beperkt aantal veranderingen aangebracht worden. Daarna moet de kaart opnieuw getekend worden. Dit kost erg veel tijd en het is erg eentonig werk. Bovendien kunnen (nieuwe) fouten ontstaan bij het overtekenen. Een ander probleem van papieren kaarten is dat ze makkelijk scheuren of dat er vlekken op kunnen komen.

Indien een kaart via de computer beschikbaar is, heeft dit een aantal voordelen. Het wijzigen kan veel eenvoudiger en sneller (met een tekenprogramma kunnen makkelijk lijnen verplaatst worden). Bovendien kan de kaart vanaf verschillende plaatsen tegelijkertijd geraadpleegd worden (door het gebruik van computers in een netwerk).

Deze tekst geeft een samenvatting van het proefschrift voor de niet-specialist. Het doel is niet volledigheid, maar om de rode draad in begrijpelijk Nederlands weer te geven. De pagina-, figuur- en tabelnummers verwijzen naar de pagina's, figuren en tabellen in het proefschrift. Allereerst volgen er een paar definities:

- Pixel* Afkorting van 'picture element', kleinste deel van een beeld. Er wordt onderscheid gemaakt tussen *objectpixels* (pixels die de objecten in het beeld weergeven) en *achtergrondpixels* (overige pixels).
- Binair beeld* Beeld waarin de pixels twee waarden kunnen hebben: één (de objecten in het beeld) of nul (de achtergrond).
- Vector* Een gericht lijnstuk dat wordt weergegeven door een begin- en eindpunt. Begin- en eindpunt worden *node* genoemd.
- Vectoriseren* Het omzetten van 'lijnen' in een binair beeld (deze 'lijnen' zijn in feite pixels die achter en naast elkaar liggen, zonder onderlinge relatie) naar vectoren. Het voordeel hiervan is, dat een gestructureerde weergave van het beeld ontstaat: er kunnen vergelijkingen van lijnen gemaakt worden. Hierdoor kan met standaard wiskundige formules onder andere het snijpunt van verschillende lijnen bepaald worden evenals de afstand tussen twee lijnen. Voor een voorbeeld zie figuur 4.9 (pagina 65), waar in grijs de 'lijnen' in het binaire beeld zijn weergegeven en in zwart de vectoren. '+'-tekens geven de plaats van de nodes aan.
- Scanner* Een apparaat dat een beeld dat op papier staat omzet naar een verzameling pixels. Deze pixels vormen het beeld dat als invoer voor een computerprogramma dient.

Kaarten in dit proefschrift

In dit proefschrift worden voor de interpretatie twee soorten kaarten gebruikt: kadastrale kaarten en grootschalige basiskaarten van Nederland.

Kadastrale kaarten

Op kadastrale kaarten (figuur 2.2 en 2.3, vanaf pagina 17) worden onder andere *percelen* getekend. Een perceel is een afgebakend stuk grond dat één *perceelnummer* heeft. Door dit nummer kan onder andere worden nagegaan wie het eigendomsrecht heeft. Soms bestaat een perceel uit verschillende stukken (ook wel polygoon genoemd), bijvoorbeeld als er bebouwing op staat. Om aan te geven dat die verschillende stukken bij één perceel horen worden ze verbonden door *bijpijlingstekens* (figuur 2.4). Bijvoorbeeld, perceel 1145 in figuur 2.2 heeft drie polygoon, twee bijpijlingstekens en één perceelnummer. Het perceelnummer wordt in het midden van een van de polygoon van het perceel geschreven. Sommige kadastrale kaarten hebben *binnenkant-bebouwingstekens* (figuur 2.5): korte streepjes die naar de binnenkant van een gebouw wijzen dat op een perceel staat.

Grootschalige basiskaarten van Nederland

Grootschalige BasisKaarten van Nederland (GBKN's) worden door het kadaster gemaakt om een topologisch correcte kaart aan de klanten te kunnen aanbieden. Het is een basiskaart, de exacte locatie van de basistopologie als straten en gebouwenblokken is er op aangegeven, terwijl klanten (bijvoorbeeld een energiebedrijf) zelf op de kaart hun eigen informatie (zoals pijpleidingen) kunnen intekenen. Voor de klanten is het voordeel dat ze kosten besparen omdat ze alleen hun eigen informatie hoeven in te tekenen.

Een voorbeeld van een GBKN is gegeven in figuur 5.1 (pagina 75). Een GBKN is opgebouwd uit polygoon. *Gebouwenblokken* bestaan uit polygoon met een reeks van getallen die *huisnummers* aangeven in dat blok. *Bestrating* bestaat uit polygoon met *straatnamen* of speciale *bestratingssymbolen* (gesloten en open bestratingssymbolen, zie figuur 5.2). Straatnamen worden voor het gemak vanaf nu ook bestratingssymbolen genoemd. Andere symbolen die voorkomen op een GBKN zijn *paskruizen*, zoals in figuur 5.15 (pagina 90).

1 Hoofdstuk 1: Introductie tot 'modelgestuurd' en het jargon

Dit hoofdstuk geeft een algemene inleiding tot het proefschrift. In de literatuur bestaat geen éénduidige betekenis van het woord 'modelgestuurd'. Hierdoor ontstaat vaak verwarring. Om hier duidelijkheid in te brengen wordt in hoofdstuk 1 een ruwe onderverdeling gemaakt tussen de verschillende omschrijvingen. Ook is een verklarende woordenlijst opgenomen. Verder wordt een inleiding gegeven tot de in dit proefschrift gebruikte modelgestuurde interpretatiestructuur.

1.1 Onderverdeling tussen omschrijvingen van 'modelgestuurd'

Aan de hand van een literatuurbespreking wordt een indeling gemaakt naar de verschillende omschrijvingen van 'modelgestuurd'. Er wordt onderscheid gemaakt tussen auteurs die objecten weergeven met een model, auteurs die de interpretatiemethode bepalen met een model, en auteurs die zowel de objecten als de interpretatiemethode bepalen met een model.

Auteurs die de te interpreteren objecten in het beeld weergeven met een model, doen dit omdat vorm of andere eigenschappen van een object moeilijk met vaste instellingen van variabelen beschreven kunnen worden. Soms zijn de eigenschappen van objecten te ingewikkeld om te beschrijven en is een vereenvoudiging gewenst. Voorbeelden zijn chromosomen die beschreven worden door vorm en lengte, of een auteur die een mens tot 14 cilinders 'vereenvoudigt' (voor hoofd, lichaam, armen en benen).

Andere auteurs verwijzen met het begrip 'modelgestuurd' naar een interpretatiemethode die op een model gebaseerd is. Vaak wordt dit gedaan om de structuur van het interpretatiesysteem te verduidelijken. Het interpretatiesysteem wordt dan onderverdeeld in verschillende lagen, die samenhangen met de complexiteit van de objecten en bewerkingen in die laag. Op een laag niveau wordt er met 'eenvoudige' objecten (zoals pixels) gewerkt en op een hoog niveau met gecompliceerde ('abstracte') objecten. Abstracte objecten zijn onder meer samengesteld uit verschillende 'eenvoudige' objecten (zoals bijvoorbeeld percelen van een kadastrale kaart die een perceelnummer hebben, maar dit is geheel afhankelijk van het te interpreteren beeld).

Weer andere auteurs combineren beide zienswijzen. In dat geval worden objecten in het beeld met een model weergegeven en is de interpretatiemethode gebaseerd op een model. Deze aanpak combineert de voordelen van beide bovenstaande benaderingen: een grote variatie in de verschijningsvorm van objecten van het zelfde type (zoals bijvoorbeeld bijpijlingstekens) kan ondervangen worden en er is een gestructureerde opbouw van het interpretatiesysteem.

1.2 Waarom modelgestuurd?

Het onderzoek naar modelgestuurde beeldbewerking is opgezet omdat de 'klassieke' interpretatiemethoden niet meer geheel voldeden. Deze lieten niet gemakkelijk toe dat gebruik werd gemaakt van voorkennis over datgene wat geïnterpreteerd moest worden. Soms was het moeilijk om consistentietests uit te voeren. (Een consistentietest is een test om te onderzoeken of datgene wat door de computer gevonden wordt, klopt met wat verwacht wordt.) Bij modelgestuurde interpretatie zijn deze bezwaren er niet.

Voorkennis bij interpretatie van kadastrale kaarten is bijvoorbeeld dat al vóór het ontwerpen van een interpretatiesysteem bekend is dat er één nummer per perceel kan zijn (dit is een tekenregel voor kadastrale kaarten). Een voorbeeld van een consistentietest is dat na interpretatie het aantal perceelnummers per perceel geteld wordt. Volgens de voorkennis zou er voor elk perceel één perceelnummer moeten zijn.

Als er een 'perceel' gevonden wordt dat nul of juist meer dan één perceelnummer heeft, dan komt dat niet overeen met de voorkennis en moet er een fout in de interpretatie zijn. Door van te voren te bedenken hoe het komt dat een perceelnummer niet gevonden wordt (bijvoorbeeld omdat de getallen die het nummer vormen vastzitten aan de lijnen die het perceel omsluiten, waardoor de computer het nummer niet als zodanig herkent) kan het automatisch gecorrigeerd worden. Met modelsturing kan dit resultaat (perceelnummer niet gevonden) eenvoudig teruggekoppeld worden naar een lager niveau (pixels), zodat het nummer van de lijn 'losgesneden' kan worden (lossnijden is een bewerking op pixels, dus dit moet op een laag niveau gebeuren).

Het model wordt dus gebruikt om verwachtingen over de werkelijkheid (voorken-

nis) in op te slaan; het biedt mogelijkheden voor vereenvoudiging en verduidelijking, en het brengt structuur in het interpretatiesysteem aan. Modelgestuurde beeldbewerking is gebaseerd op het principe: 'als er feiten bekend zijn over de te interpreteren objecten, gebruik die dan ook en probeer die kennis zo veel mogelijk uit te buiten'. Hierdoor kunnen consistentietests uitgevoerd worden: klopt hetgeen gevonden is nu echt met wat verwacht wordt? Zo niet, dan kan het model aangeven hoe dat aangepast en/of gecorrigeerd moet worden.

De modelgestuurde interpretatiestructuur in dit proefschrift bestaat uit de volgende drie verschillende modellen (dit is een zeer beknopte weergave van hoofdstuk 1 en 5):

Model van de interpretatievolgorde Dit model geeft aan hoe de verschillende delen van het interpretatiesysteem met elkaar verbonden zijn en wat ze moeten doen (maar niet hoe ze dat moeten doen).

Model van de kaart

Dit model geeft aan welke objecten voorkomen op de kaart, waar ze gevonden kunnen worden, welke fouten tijdens de interpretatie —eventueel— kunnen optreden en hoe die gecorrigeerd kunnen worden.

Model van het object

Dit model geeft aan hoe het object gevonden kan worden. Voor elk verschillend object bestaat een model van het object. Dit model is nauw verbonden met het model van de kaart.

Bovenstaande interpretatiestructuur representeert zowel de objecten in het beeld als de interpretatiemethode met een model. In het proefschrift komen modellen op verschillende plaatsen voor: in hoofdstuk 3 en 4 op een gedetailleerd niveau en in hoofdstuk 5 op een globaal niveau. Het onderzoek in hoofdstuk 2 is min of meer de oorzaak van het ontstaan van het proefschrift: tijdens het ontwikkelen van een allereerste interpretatiesysteem voor kadastrale kaarten ontstonden verscheidene problemen en het leek handig om een aantal van deze problemen op te lossen met modelgestuurde beeldbewerking.

2 Hoofdstuk 2: Evaluatiemethode voor een automatisch kaartinterpretatiesysteem voor kadastrale kaarten

Hoofdstuk 2 beschrijft een allereerste bottom-up systeem (interpretatie *alleen* van laag naar hoog niveau) voor automatische interpretatie van kadastrale kaarten. Het bleek dat —ondanks de relatieve eenvoud van kadastrale kaarten— het niet gemakkelijk was om zo'n systeem te maken. Problemen ontstonden zowel bij de vectorisatie als bij de interpretatie.

2.1 Vectorisatie en opschoonregels

Voor vectorisatie wordt de standaard Douglas-Peucker methode gebruikt. Deze werkt als volgt (zie figuur 4.2 op pagina 52). De curve (dunne lijn) moet gevectoriseerd worden. Een eerste benadering hiervan is de dikke lijn in de linker figuur. Vervolgens wordt de maximale loodrechte afstand van de curve tot aan de benadering bepaald (gestreepte

pijl). Als deze afstand groter is dan een vooraf ingestelde waarde, wordt op het punt van de maximale afwijking een nieuwe node gemaakt (middelste figuur). Vervolgens wordt het proces herhaald voor beide —nu ontstane— delen van de benadering. In het middelste figuur gebeurt dat alleen voor het linker deel van de curve omdat de maximale waarde voor het rechter deel al kleiner of gelijk is aan de vooraf ingestelde waarde (de dikke lijn loopt 'over' de dunne, dus de maximale loodrechte afstand voor het rechter deel is nul).

Problemen bij de vectorisatie

De hierboven beschreven vectorisatiemethode geeft een nauwkeurige vectorisatie. Echter, er ontstaan vaak 'te veel' (lees: overbodige) vectoren. Om het aantal vectoren te reduceren zijn opschoonregels gemaakt. Er wordt onderscheid gemaakt tussen regels om gaten in de vectorisatie te dichten (figuur 2.8, pagina 22), regels om nodes te verwijderen waarvan de vectoren een hoek maken van ongeveer 180° (dan zijn die nodes eigenlijk overbodig, zie bijvoorbeeld node *i* in figuur 2.9), en regels om vectoren bij hoeken, T-splitsingen en kruisingen van lijnen te verbeteren (er zijn vaak korte overbodige vectoren, zie respectievelijk figuur 2.10, 2.11 en 2.12).

Om het effect van deze opschoonregels te kunnen beoordelen werd een evaluatiemethode ontwikkeld. De vectorisatieresultaten van vóór en na de opschoonregels werden met elkaar vergeleken. Het bleek dat de opschoonregels er inderdaad voor zorgen dat het aantal vectoren aanzienlijk daalt. De afwijking neemt echter een beetje toe. Soms is dat niet toelaatbaar. Daarom is een nieuwe vectorisatiemethode ontwikkeld die dat nadeel niet heeft. Deze methode wordt beschreven in hoofdstuk 4.

2.2 Interpretatie

De eerste stap in het interpretatiesysteem is het vinden van bijpijlingstekens. Hoe dit gedaan wordt is geïllustreerd in figuur 2.13. Vervolgens wordt de vectorisatie gebruikt om alle polygonen te bepalen. Tenslotte wordt bepaald welke bijpijlingstekens welke polygonen verbinden, waaruit dan de percelen volgen. De interpretatie is redelijk goed: het merendeel van de percelen en de perceelnummers wordt gevonden (tabel 2.3 en 2.4).

Problemen bij de interpretatie

De interpretatie gaat soms fout door de variatie in de vorm van de objecten. Bijpijlingstekens kunnen op talloze manieren getekend worden, zie bijvoorbeeld figuur 2.4. Soms worden ze niet gevonden omdat een deel ervan aan een lijn van het perceel vastzit. Perceelnummers worden soms om dezelfde reden niet gevonden.

Er is voor gekozen om deze problemen niet in dit (bottom-up) interpretatiesysteem op te lossen, maar op een modelgestuurde manier zoals beschreven is in hoofdstuk 5.

3 Hoofdstuk 3: Constructie van mozaïeken uit apart gescande lijntekeningen

Eén van de problemen in automatische interpretatie van lijntekeningen (bijvoorbeeld kaarten op A0 kaartbladen) is de beperkte grootte van scanners, of het niet beschikbaar

zijn van scanners van het juiste formaat (bijvoorbeeld omdat ze te duur zijn). Omdat de lijntekening dan in stukken gescand moet worden, kunnen objecten die nodig zijn voor de interpretatie, net buiten het beeld vallen (dit heet het *randprobleem*). Hoofdstuk 3 beschrijft een systeem om apart gescande lijntekeningen aan elkaar te leggen tot één doorlopende, grotere lijntekening. Dit wordt het *construeren van mozaïeken* genoemd. Het systeem kan gebruikt worden voorafgaand aan het interpretatiesysteem. Hierdoor wordt het randprobleem vermeden of tenminste verkleind.

Het construeren van mozaïeken wordt getoond in figuur 3.1 op pagina 33: de twee apart gescande kaarten boven in de afbeelding worden gevectoriseerd, vervolgens worden *paren van controlepunten* bepaald die gebruikt worden om de transformatie van het coördinatenstelsel van kaart II naar kaart I te berekenen, waarna de hele kaart II getransformeerd wordt. Het resultaat is onderaan in die afbeelding te zien.

Een paar van controlepunten bestaat uit twee punten, waarvan één in kaart I ligt en één in kaart II. Deze punten moeten op elkaar vallen als de kaarten naar hetzelfde coördinatenstelsel getransformeerd zijn. Ze worden gevonden door beide kaarten te vectoriseren en alle vectoren uit beide vectorisaties met elkaar te vergelijken. De paren van controlepunten voor de kaarten in figuur 3.1 zijn in figuur 3.2 gegeven door zeshoeken die paarsgewijs met elkaar verbonden zijn door gestreepte pijlen. Het gebruikte model is op een laag niveau, want het vergelijkt vectoren met elkaar. Het construeren van mozaïeken blijkt erg goed te werken: maar ongeveer 1% van de objectpixels wordt niet goed getransformeerd, en ligt dan slechts op een afstand van één pixel van de goede plek (tabel 3.2 en 3.3).

4 Hoofdstuk 4: Adaptieve vectorisatie van lijntekeningen

Hoofdstuk 4 beschrijft een nieuwe methode voor adaptieve vectorisatie. Deze methode werd ontwikkeld omdat de opschoonregels in hoofdstuk 2 wel het aantal vectoren reduceerden, maar niet de afwijking.

De nieuwe methode wordt adaptief genoemd omdat het (binaire) input beeld gebruikt wordt voor het verbeteren van de vectorisatie (de methode zou ook modelgestuurd genoemd kunnen worden). De adaptieve vectorisatiemethode berust op het onderscheiden van twee soorten punten: 'ankerpunten' (bijzondere punten zoals hoekpunten, splitsingen en eindpunten), en overige punten (nodig voor het nauwkeurig maken van de vectorisatie).

De adaptieve vectorisatie bepaalt eerst het globale verloop van de lijnen in het binaire beeld. Dit wordt gedaan met de standaard Douglas-Peucker (afgekort: *DP*) vectorisatiemethode, waarbij de maximum toegestane loodrechte afstand van de curve tot aan de benadering (gestreepte pijl in figuur 4.2 op pagina 52) ingesteld wordt op een grote waarde. Daardoor zal de vectorisatie 'grof' zijn.

Vervolgens wordt voor iedere node in de globale vectorisatie een nauwkeurige positie bepaald. Dit gebeurt met een methode die 'maximum threshold morphology' heet en die het binaire input beeld gebruikt om de nodes uit de globale vectorisatie naar een betere plaats te schuiven. Zie voor een voorbeeld figuur 4.6 op pagina 58. Punt *i* in 4.6(c) is de node uit de globale vectorisatie en deze schuift langzaam op via node *ii* naar node *iii* (node *iv* is hetzelfde als node *iii*, dus stopt het proces). In de afbeelding zijn

de bij de nodes horende vectoren zwart en het binaire beeld grijs gekleurd. Node *iii* en de andere aldus bepaalde punten worden 'ankerpunten' genoemd, omdat ze in het volgende deel van het vectorisatiesysteem niet meer verplaatsen.

Het volgende deel van het vectorisatiesysteem bestaat uit een nauwkeurige vectorisatie *tussen* de ankerpunten. Hiervoor wordt (opnieuw) de DP vectorisatiemethode gebruikt, maar nu is de maximale toegestane loodrechte afstand ingesteld op een veel kleinere waarde. Hierdoor wordt een gedetailleerde vectorisatie verkregen die de ankerpunten als basis heeft.

De adaptieve vectorisatiemethode is modulair opgebouwd. Hierdoor kunnen tussen de bovengenoemde bouwstenen (bepaling van de globale vectorisatie, bepaling van de ankerpunten en bepaling van de nauwkeurige vectorisatie) 'opschoon'- of 'verbeterings'-modules geplaatst worden. Er zijn een aantal experimenten gedaan, waarna voor elk experiment het aantal vectoren en de afwijking (volgens de evaluatiemethode uit hoofdstuk 2) bepaald is. Het aantal vectoren bij het best presterende systeem was altijd lager dan het aantal vectoren verkregen met de DP vectorisatie, en ook lager dan het aantal vectoren verkregen met de DP vectorisatie met opschoonregels uit hoofdstuk 2. Ook was de afwijking altijd lager.

Ook de ligging van de vectoren verkregen met de adaptieve vectorisatie is beter ('mooier') dan met de DP vectorisatie: zie figuur 4.9 tot en met 4.12 (vanaf pagina 65). In deze figuren is de bovenste helft een stuk uit de DP vectorisatie en de onderste helft een stuk uit de adaptieve vectorisatie. In alle figuren is het binaire beeld in grijs weergegeven en de vectorisatie in zwart. '+'-tekens geven de plaats van de nodes aan.

De ankerpunten die door de adaptieve vectorisatie gevonden worden kunnen ook voor andere doeleinden gebruikt worden: bijvoorbeeld als controlepunten voor het construeren van mozaïeken in hoofdstuk 3.

5 Hoofdstuk 5: Modelgestuurde interpretatie van twee soorten kaarten

In hoofdstuk 5 wordt een modelgestuurd interpretatiesysteem voor kadastrale kaarten beschreven, dat is gebaseerd op de (modelgestuurde) interpretatiestructuur uit hoofdstuk 1. Om de flexibiliteit van deze modelstructuur aan te tonen, wordt dit systeem daarna uitgebreid tot een systeem dat GBKN's kan interpreteren. Beide systemen gebruiken hetzelfde model voor de interpretatievolgorde en hebben elk een apart model voor de kaart.

5.1 Gemeenschappelijk interpretatiedeel

Het model van de kadastrale kaart en het model van de GBKN hebben een aantal gemeenschappelijke delen zoals bijvoorbeeld het berekenen van de adaptieve vectorisatie (hoofdstuk 4), de constructie van polygonen en het vinden van cijfers en letters.

5.2 Interpretatie van kadastrale kaarten

Naast de delen zoals beschreven in paragraaf 5.1, bevat het model van de kadastrale kaart delen die specifiek bij een kadastrale kaart horen: modules voor het vinden van bijpijlingstekens en modules voor het combineren van bijpijlingstekens, getallen en polygonen tot percelen.

Een belangrijk onderdeel van het model van de kadastrale kaart is de consistentietest: voldoen alle gevonden 'percelen' inderdaad aan de definitie van perceel? Als een object één perceelnummer heeft voldoet het aan de definitie. Anders moet er actie ondernomen worden om dit te corrigeren:

Geval 1. *Observatie*: er zijn nul perceelnummers.

Hypothese 1: het systeem heeft een bijpijlingsteken gemist.

Actie: dit is de situatie zoals in figuur 5.4 (pagina 78). Er wordt lokaal naar een (deel van een) bijpijlingsteken gezocht. Indien dit gevonden wordt kan een nieuw bijpijlingsteken geconstrueerd worden en vervolgens een perceel.

Hypothese 2: het systeem heeft een perceelnummer gemist.

Actie: dit is de situatie zoals in figuur 5.5 (pagina 79). Er wordt lokaal naar een perceelnummer gezocht. Indien dit gevonden wordt kan een nieuw perceel geconstrueerd worden.

Geval 2. *Observatie*: er zijn twee of meer perceelnummers.

Hypothese: een deel van een bijpijlingsteken is (per abuis) gemarkeerd als perceelnummer.

Actie: dit kan gebeuren als een blob (onderdeel) van een bijpijlingsteken relatief lang is: deze lijkt dan op een '1'. Als na een test met de module die letters en cijfers herkent, blijkt dat dat inderdaad zo is, wordt het object hermarkeerd als 'onbekend object' en kan het vervolgens dienen als deel van een bijpijlingsteken.

5.3 Interpretatie van GBKN's

Naast de delen zoals beschreven in paragraaf 5.1, bevat het model van de GBKN delen die specifiek bij een GBKN horen: modules voor het vinden van bestratingssymbolen en paskruizen, en modules voor het combineren van bestratingssymbolen, straatnamen, huisnummers en polygonen tot bestrating en gebouwenblokken.

Een belangrijk onderdeel van het model van de GBKN is de consistentietest: voldoen alle gevonden objecten aan de definitie van bestrating en gebouwenblokken? Een gebouwenblok heeft één of meer huisnummers en nul bestratingssymbolen, en bestrating nul huisnummers en één of meer bestratingssymbolen. Een object dat nul huisnummers en nul bestratingssymbolen heeft wordt gemarkeerd als 'onbekend object': hier is geen informatie over bekend (dit is een toegestaan label want het komt regelmatig in een GBKN voor, zie bijvoorbeeld de lege polygonen in figuur 5.1).

In het geval dat een object zowel één of meer huisnummers als één of meer bestratingssymbolen heeft, moet er actie ondernomen worden om dit te corrigeren:

Geval 1. *Observatie*: een object heeft zowel één of meer bestratingssymbolen als één of meer huisnummers.

Hypothese: het systeem heeft een bestratingssymbool als huisnummer herkend.

Actie: dit is de situatie zoals gegeven in figuur 5.7 (pagina 81). Er wordt gekeken of een huisnummer in de buurt van een bestratingssymbool staat. Zo ja, dan wordt het opnieuw gelabeld tot bestratingssymbool en wordt het hele object opnieuw gelabeld tot bestrating.

Geval 2. *Observatie:* een object heeft zowel één of meer bestratingssymbolen als één of meer huisnummers.

Hypothese: er is iets fout gegaan en dit werd niet gecorrigeerd nadat geval 1 uitgeprobeerd was.

Actie: er wordt bepaald of bestratingssymbolen dan wel huisnummers het meeste in het object voorkomen. Als bestratingssymbolen het meeste voorkomen wordt het object opnieuw gelabeld als bestrating, als de huisnummers het meeste voorkomen wordt het object opnieuw gelabeld als gebouwenblok, en anders (beide komen even vaak voor) verandert er niets. Dit is te zien als een noodgreep: laten we toch maar iets proberen.

5.4 Evaluatie van het modelgestuurde interpretatiesysteem

Het modelgestuurde interpretatiesysteem is getest op een aantal kadastrale kaarten en GBKN's. In hoofdstuk 2 is een interpretatiesysteem voor kadastrale kaarten beschreven. Het systeem uit hoofdstuk 5 geeft betere resultaten dan het systeem uit hoofdstuk 2. Resultaten voor interpretatie van GBKN's zijn goed (tabel 5.5 tot en met 5.10).

Het blijkt dat objecten zoals bijpijlingstekens en bestratingssymbolen goed beschreven worden met hun respectieve modellen. Er is een enorme variatie (zelfs in dezelfde kaart) tussen de verschillende bijpijlingstekens (zie de kadastrale kaarten in hoofdstuk 2 en 5 of figuur 2.4), maar ze worden toch goed gevonden.

Door het gebruiken van een modelgestuurde strategie is het relatief eenvoudig om consistentietests in te bouwen en hiermee de interpretatie te verbeteren. Tevens is een dergelijke methode flexibel: er zijn weinig veranderingen nodig om een interpretatiesysteem voor kadastrale kaarten om te zetten naar GBKN's.

6 Conclusie en samenvatting

Dit proefschrift beschrijft verschillende aspecten van modelgestuurde beeldbewerking. Eén van de aspecten is een modelgestuurd interpretatiesysteem voor twee soorten kaarten, beschreven in hoofdstuk 5. In dat hoofdstuk (en in hoofdstuk 1) wordt een modelgestuurde interpretatiestructuur gedefinieerd die bestaat uit drie verschillende modellen. De interpretatiesystemen ontworpen volgens deze structuur blijken goed te werken.

De testresultaten van het modelgestuurde kadastrale kaartinterpretatiesysteem worden vergeleken met het bottom-up interpretatiesysteem uit hoofdstuk 2. Het modelgestuurde systeem werkt beter dan het bottom-up systeem en dat komt door de modelkennis die toelaat dat eventuele fouten automatisch verbeterd worden.

Het bottom-up systeem was het allereerste systeem voor het onderzoeken van kaartinterpretatie. Het diende tevens voor het onderzoeken van de vectorisatie. Het bleek dat tijdens de vectorisatie verschillende problemen kunnen optreden omdat sommige lijnen onderbroken zijn of omdat (erg) veel vectoren ontstaan. Er werden regels ont-

wikkeld om dit te corrigeren en hierdoor nam het aantal vectoren inderdaad behoorlijk af terwijl de afwijking slechts zeer weinig toenam. Alhoewel deze regels goed werkten, was het geen bevredigende oplossing omdat een lichte toename in de afwijking niet altijd acceptabel is.

In hoofdstuk 4 is een nieuwe adaptieve vectorisatiemethode ontwikkeld, welke het binaire input beeld gebruikt om de vectorisatie nauwkeuriger te maken en indien nodig te corrigeren. Deze adaptieve vectorisatie werkt beter dan de Douglas-Peucker vectorisatie en hij werkt ook beter dan de Douglas-Peucker vectorisatie met opschoonregels uit hoofdstuk 2.

Hoofdstuk 3 beschrijft een systeem om mozaïeken te construeren van apart gescande lijntekeningen. Het systeem vindt automatisch paren van controlepunten, die gebruikt worden om het coördinatenstelsel van één lijntekening naar het andere te transformeren. Zo'n systeem kan voorafgaand aan het interpretatiesysteem gebruikt worden: hierdoor wordt één grote lijntekening geïnterpreteerd in plaats van verschillende kleinere en wordt het randprobleem vermeden (of althans verkleind).

Het begrip 'modelgestuurd' wordt vaak alleen gebruikt bij hoog-niveau systemen. Het *principe* van modelgestuurd (verwachtingen over de werkelijkheid om de interpretatie te sturen en indien nodig te verbeteren) kan mijns inziens echter gevonden worden op alle niveaus, zoals is geïllustreerd in dit proefschrift.

17

7
2 Gemeten
1 Gem: 150 Roen.

8
K
2 Gemeten
100 Roen

A
9 Gemeten
50 Roen.

F
3 Gemeten
75 Roen.

H O E K

De Bouda Meets groot
2 Gemeten 150 Roen.

De Groote Plas
De Roo Hays

1 Gemet 35
100 Roen

De Bot We
3 Gemeten
Verlaet
Ouden Oost

De Sleys waze
Ouden land